

945358-BIGPICTURE

Central Repository for Digital Pathology

WP5 - Regulatory framework for digital slides and AI-based methods

D5.01 Overview of the legal frameworks of all countries involved in BIGPICTURE

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Abstract

The objective of this report is to identify legal rules applicable to the initial contributors (Data Submitters; for this and further definitions and abbreviations, please refer to Glossary and Abbreviations section below) of Whole Slide Images (“**WSI**”) and accompanying Metadata in the BIGPICTURE project in the scope that those rules may impact their provision and use within the project. The initial Data Submitters of the WSIs are located in the following 8 jurisdictions: Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Sweden and UK and the report outlines the main areas of legal interest on EU and national level. Those areas include: protection of personal data, laws applicable to non-clinical WSIs (animal WSIs), ethical requirements, rules relating to biobanks, intellectual property (“**IP**”) protection, open data and contractual limitations. The outcomes of the analysis are presented in corresponding sections of the Summary report (Appendix 1). Detailed analysis of regulatory environments in the Data Submitters jurisdictions are attached as country reports.

The findings of this report should be treated as starting point and legal input for development of the framework of BIGPICTURE data repositories. The work done within the first 9 months of the project will be complemented by further efforts of WP5, in particular T5.2.1, with the aim of investigating and developing the legal and contractual framework for sustainable BIGPICTURE repository covering (nearly) all EEA countries and Switzerland.

Methods

The Summary report provides an overview on the responses collected from the country experts from the relevant jurisdictions.

In order to prepare this report, the first task was the identification of the initial Data Submitters’ jurisdictions, as those were not defined in the DoA. Thus, the list of the jurisdictions involved had to be determined based on the following list of initial Data Submitters provided by WP3.

Data Submitter	Abbreviation	Country	Node
Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht	UMC UTRECHT	Netherlands	Cancer
Stichting Katholieke Universiteit	RUMC	Netherlands	Cancer
Azienda Ospedaliera Per L’Emergenza Cannizzaro	AOEC	Italy	Cancer
Technical University of Munich	TUM	Germany	Cancer
Philipps Universitaet Marburg	UMR	Germany	Clinical trial
The Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust	LHTNHS	UK	Liver
Helsingin Ja Uudenmaan Sairaanhoidopiirin Kuntayhtymä	HUS	Finland	Lung
Medizinische Universitat Graz	MUG	Austria	Lung
<i>DECIPHEX*</i>	<i>DECIPHEX</i>	<i>Ireland</i>	<i>Non-clinical</i>
Medical University Vienna	MUW	Austria	Renal
Ostergotlands Lans Landsting	RO	Sweden	Skin
<i>Linköping University*</i>	<i>LiU</i>	<i>Sweden</i>	<i>Skin</i>

Universite de Liege	ULIEGE	Belgium	Skin
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After further investigation, Ireland was excluded from the list based on the subsequent clarification that DECIPHEX will not be in the role of a Data Submitter. Similarly, LiU will not be participating in the role of a Data Submitter, at least during the initial period, and neither is LiU part of the skin node. For this reason, the LiU legal unit has not provided input to this document.¹ Thus the list of initial Data Submitters jurisdictions comprised the following countries: Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Sweden and the UK.

In parallel, TIME.LEX began mapping the areas of law which should be examined and discussing with other contributors (LYGATURE and BBMRI-ERIC) involvement of country experts. TIME.LEX developed a questionnaire for the local experts which was consulted within the task group. To ensure consistency in the level of detail and the content of the responses, TIME.LEX together with input from RO completed a report for Sweden. Next, the questionnaire and model responses were sent to identified country experts for their input.

As task leader TIME.LEX prepared an analysis of EU data protection law (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR) and EU intellectual property law (copyright and database protection rights) and drafted the main body of the study based on own legal research and previous assessments, such as AEGLE project², EC reports³ and available literature. In addition, inputs from relevant experts and partners were collected and an assessment of overarching themes and requirements was prepared to the extent they are relevant to the BIGPICTURE repository as a whole.

The country reports were prepared for Data Submitters jurisdictions in which a legal expert/respondent was available. This included respondents from the BBMRI-ERIC ELSI network covering: Italy, Finland and Belgium (jointly with the TIME.LEX team). Where no ELSI contact was available, partners from the relevant jurisdictions provided their contribution: Sweden (RO), UK (I-HD), the Netherlands (LYGATURE) and Germany (UMR).

Limitations applicable to the report:

- The report focuses on legal rules regarding the provision by the Data Submitters of WSIs and Metadata for BIGPICTURE project. As BIGPICTURE will deal with WSIs (digital slides), the report does not cover legal conditions regarding handling the glass slides themselves, including obtaining or transferring such original slides with Specimen.
- The report is not meant as an exhaustive publication regarding all legal issues connected with the project. The focus has been put on the legal areas outlined above. General legal considerations (e.g., on the set up of entities involved in the process, employment, general compliance rules etc.) were not examined in this report.
- Many of the discussions regarding the set-up of the BIGPICTURE project are ongoing. Thus in many cases the precise answers on legal constrains depend on outcome of these discussions and will need to be further worked out in the process of development of the project.
- Generally, the aim of the document was to assist the Data Submitters in providing their WSIs and Metadata to the project. Some parts of the report (in particular relating to data protection) also provide additional insight into internal requirements of the BIGPICTURE infrastructure, which will in turn enable the Data Submitters to take their own decisions and meet their own requirements (e.g., demonstrate a sufficient degree of data protection).

¹ Hence, both DECIPHEX and LiU have been marked with a “*” in the table above.

² <http://www.aegle-uhealth.eu/en/>

³ For example “Assessment of the EU Member States’ rules on health data in the light of GDPR” (https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/default/files/ehealth/docs/ms_rules_health-data_en.pdf)

- The summary report is meant to provide high level comments on overarching themes and conclusions, with illustrative examples for relevant jurisdictions. Please refer to detailed responses in the country reports for more specific guidance. In the avoidance of doubt, those reports (Appendix 2-8) should be viewed as taking precedence over the Summary report (Appendix 1).
- The report does not constitute legal advice or binding interpretation of any of the discussed laws. Data Submitters are encouraged to consult their own legal teams before taking part in BIGPICTURE and making their decisions regarding sharing of the Data.

Results

Based on the reports on legal assessment performed so far, following recommendations and directions for further work can be made to the BIGPICTURE consortium:

- BIGPICTURE will most likely not be able to provide tools or guidance which will provide assurance for the anonymity of Data (“Data” meaning WSI and related Metadata jointly) for all jurisdictions in scope. These tools may be provided as means of assistance to the Data Submitters. However, the assessment whether the goal in terms of sufficiently anonymized or pseudonymized Data was reached will be always on the Data Submitter (as controller).
- Notwithstanding the above, BIGPICTURE repository should be designed to be able to handle personal data in line with the GDPR requirements, in particular pseudonymized Data.
- Privacy notices should be drafted and made available to the data subjects (including via Data Submitters), unless a specific exemption applies. This includes preparing privacy information about processing of data in the context of BIGPICTURE which would be available on the platform.
- The BIGPICTURE consortium must agree on how the process of handling Data Subject Rights (“DSR”) will be handled internally and how the BIGPICTURE infrastructure may technically enable the exercise of the DSR rights, where legally required.
- Discussions regarding the Metadata accompanying the WSI must take into account the rule of data minimization, in particular in alignment with the research objectives for the creation of the repository. The motivation for the scope of the data should be documented.
- BIGPICTURE must take and document steps to ensure that WSIs are of representative quality (as agreed within the consortium and required for the AI training) and contain accurate personal data in the accompanying Metadata. There should also be a process of removing and correcting incorrect or misleading Data, in particular at the legitimate request of data subjects (unless exception applies).
- BIGPICTURE data controllers need to define a storage period for the pseudonymized WSI.
- Localization of the controllers of data in certain jurisdictions may trigger the applicability of their biobank laws to the BIGPICTURE collection of WSIs. This should be considered in the context of sustainability work.
- Designing and implementing appropriate organizational and technical measures to protect the personal data contained in the WSIs should be a central consideration for the project. BIGPICTURE should make the description of the safeguards available to Data Submitters and be mindful of the requirements which are provided in local legislation, to ensure that Data Submitters from those countries can participate. Some jurisdictions have concrete expectations on the measures which should be applied, while others refer to general requirements of the GDPR.
- The partners responsible for hosting the repository should be required to confirm that they appointed a data protection officer (“DPO”) and if not - that they are exempted from this requirement. Details of DPOs should be exchanged and available for the controllers and processors of BIGPICTURE data.
- Roles of the partners (controller, joint controller and processor, no role under GDPR) need to be well understood and defined, with appropriate rights and obligations allocated via data

sharing agreements, including data processing agreements, joint controller arrangements or controller-to-controller agreements, as appropriate. These roles will need to be reflected in other privacy documentation of the project, including (but not limited to) data protection impact assessment (“**DPIA**”), privacy notices, data registers and notifications.

- BIGPICTURE should conduct a DPIA exercise to evaluate all relevant aspects of sharing of WSIs within the project, in line with the GDPR requirements. This DPIA should become a reference source that will feed into and contribute to own assessments conducted by the Data Submitters (acting as controllers).
- BIGPICTURE should carefully consider whether to mandate the Data Submitters to provide WSIs which contain Metadata on specific categories of health data (genetic data, rare diseases, Covid-19). Provision of this Metadata should be marked as optional, which may be provided that the Data Submitter may share this information in line with the national law. Data containing such information may need additional layer of ethical approval or special consideration.
- BIGPICTURE must engage in discussions with concrete Data Submitters on the approach of their ethical committees to delegating to Data Access Committee (“**DAC**”) authorization of access to WSIs and Metadata.
- BIGPICTURE License(s) should be drafted to contain license (or transfer of rights) for the use of intellectual property rights to the submitted WSIs for the purpose of the BIGPICTURE project. License requirements should also be included in the contract (or terms and conditions) of the use of Data by researchers accessing the repository.

Moreover, the initial list of responsibilities which should be addressed by the Data Submitters includes the following:

- Data Submitters should indicate whether they are submitting pseudonymized or anonymized Data. For pseudonymized Data, the Biological Being ID mapping key (which allows the Data to be re-identified) must be kept separately, in particular it should not be provided to BIGPICTURE repository. Moreover, the key must be protected by technical and organisational measures (e.g. on the premises of Data Submitter).
- If the Data Submitter is contributing anonymized data, it should evaluate that the patient would not be identifiable from the submitted Metadata or the WSI itself. In particular, the Data Submitter must confirm that it performed an assessment that with reasonable effort the patient cannot be re-identified from the Data (e.g., due to number of different data points in the Metadata or their unique combination), despite certain patient identifiers (such as name or ID number) being removed and despite the assigned Biological Being ID being a “random” value which is not mapped against the actual patient record by the Data Submitter.
- Data Submitter assures that it has the appropriate legal basis to contribute the Data (WSIs and accompanying Metadata) to BIGPICTURE. The applicable legal basis must comply with the GDPR and with Data Submitter’s national law and practice on re-use of health data for research purposes and take into consideration that the submitted Data may be made available to other researchers via BIGPICTURE repository in line with the project’s objectives.
- If Data Submitter obtained consent from data subjects, Data Submitter assures such consent fulfils the requirements of the GDPR for explicit consent.
- Data Submitter assures that the submission of any Data derived from clinical trials is in line with any consent obtained from the individual and/or information provided to them during the clinical trial.
- Data Submitter confirms that the Data that it makes available to BIGPICTURE do not contravene any of their national laws restricting the disclosure of specific types of personal or health information, such as national ID number or information about certain diseases.
- Data Submitter must verify if data subjects need to be informed about the contribution of their Data and if yes, confirms informing them about it.
- Data Submitter verifies whether they are obligated to ensure that data subjects may exercise their DSR and informs BIGPICTURE about it.

- Data Submitter checks whether the safeguards offered by BIGPICTURE fulfil their requirements.
- Data Submitter confirms that they appointed a DPO and provides DPO's contact details. If no DPO was appointed, Data Submitter must confirm that they are exempted from this requirement.
- Data Submitter confirms that they obtained any required ethical approval for participating in BIGPICTURE and that submission of Data and making WSI and Metadata available to researchers via the repository is allowed in line with the conditions of such approval.
- Data Submitter confirms whether the WSI and related Metadata are submitted in pseudonymized or anonymized form, as defined by laws, regulations and organizational policies that govern the Data Submitter, and that the data have been de-identified in line with any requirements or guidance that BIGPICTURE may produce.
- Data Submitter confirms that they have removed any non-personal information from WSI and Metadata to the extent required to protect the IP rights or other proprietary information of the Data Submitter (e.g., constituting trade secrets of the Data Submitter or required by the national law).
- Data Submitter states that it is not subject to any special rules under national biobank law which would restrict the use of WSIs and Metadata in BIGPICTURE. Data Submitter indicates whether it is under a requirement for concluding material transfer agreement (MTA).
- Data Submitter confirms that they have cleared any third-party IP rights to Data, in particular that the Data Submitter has obtained such rights, either by virtue of law or by contract (e.g., by an agreement with the researcher).
- Data Submitter confirms that they are not subject to open-data laws which would constitute an obstacle in providing the WSIs to the project nor that they impose any conditions for Data use in the context of BIGPICTURE.
- Data Submitter agrees to conditions of the data transfer agreement which may be developed by the project, including to conditions of processing of the submitted personal data (if the WSI have been pseudonymized) and the BIGPICTURE License terms for the use of WSI which are agreed on during submission.

The lists above are to be considered as preliminary, to be further developed in more granularity as the project progresses.

Completed country reports summarizing legal frameworks in Belgium, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Sweden and UK are provided in Appendix 2-8 to this document. Based on the country reports, a Summary report was prepared and is attached as Appendix 1. Summary report follows the outline as indicated in the table of content above.

Discussion

The title of the deliverable (D5.1: Overview of the legal frameworks of all countries involved in BIGPICTURE) is misleading. Further to the elaboration of the work in T5.1, the object of the report was to provide a summary the rules *applicable to the Data Submitters initially involved in the project* and not all the countries involved in the project. As a result of prioritization of the countries to be examined and availability of legal experts, detailed assessments of 7 (seven) Data Submitters' jurisdictions were made. This initial report will be extended during the work of WP5 to cover the regulatory frameworks of (nearly) all EEA countries plus Switzerland.

Conclusion

The summary report clearly demonstrates that many legal requirements for the BIGPICTURE project stem from the EU and applicable national rules on processing and re-use of health data for scientific purposes. These obligations are fragmented and vary to a great extent, depending on the country of the Data Submitter, type of the Data Submitter and the context of collection of the initial slide and

sometimes even on the local interpretation of the law. While the Data Submitters may be advised on the existence of the laws, the decision on what is the appropriate manner to address them must be left to the Data Submitters as the initial controllers and data holders.

Moreover, the ethical requirements for submitting personal data contained in the pseudonymized clinical WSI to publicly accessible repositories are not well defined by law and often depend on the decision of the ethics committee. There are very limited rules relating specifically to the use of WSIs and related Metadata and thus the legal principles have to be deducted from often very general laws and provisions. This results in vague and often conflicting requirements stemming from various legal acts. Determining the applicable details will in our view inevitably entail engaging in discussions with particular Data Submitters and “one model fits all” solutions will be difficult to find.

Despite these variances, some legal aspects, even though regulated by different national laws, can be summarized into overarching themes. This results in the recommendations provided in Results section above. They will be further developed and implemented to BIGPICTURE throughout the work done by WP5.

Attachment list

- Appendix 1: Summary Report
- Appendix 2: Belgium Country Report
- Appendix 3: Finland Country Report
- Appendix 4: Germany Country Report
- Appendix 5: Italy Country Report
- Appendix 6: Netherlands Country Report
- Appendix 7: Sweden Country Report
- Appendix 8: UK Country Report

Appendix 1

Summary report on overview of the legal frameworks of the Data Submitters initially involved in the BIGPICTURE project

Glossary and Abbreviations

The definitions and abbreviations provided below relate to this deliverable only. The terms marked with “*” have been aligned with definitions of *D1.04 - Initial Data Management Plan*.

“**Biological Being**”* represents a patient or an animal from whom/which specimen are acquired to produce slides or associated data (genetics, laboratory measurements, clinical history, etc.).

“**Whole Slide Image (WSI)**”* refers to the scanned copy of a glass slides. For the purpose of the deliverable, WSI are split into “clinical WSIs” of human origin Specimen and “non-clinical” WSIs of animal Specimen.

“**Metadata**” means “data about data.” In the context of this document it refers to any and all data linked to the WSI, consisting of data relevant to the project such as technical data, license, ethical and legal compliance data, biological data (e.g., target, organ, animal, study id...), compound data (e.g., compound ID, structure, ...), slide annotation data, and other associated data (e.g., study reports and protocols, clinical data, clinical pathology and biomarker data, macroscopic examination report, ...).

“**Data**” means WSI and Metadata jointly.

“**Data Access Committee (DAC)**” means organisation, individual or a group of individuals which is authorized to decide on the access requests to the contributed Data.

“**Data Subject Rights**” mean the rights referred to in Articles 15-21 General Data Protection Regulation.

“**Data Submitter**” refers to the party (contributor) providing the Data by uploading WSI and Metadata to the repository.

“**General Data Protection Regulation**” means Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC

“**Specimen**”* refers to biological material that is being extracted from the person/animal (Biological Being). The term does not refer to the container in which those parts are placed, and sometimes parts from different anatomical locations are placed together in such a container, making the origin of a given Specimen ambiguous. Hence, Specimen must always only be derived from one specific anatomical location.

“**Slide**”* refers to the microscope (glass) slide as a physical object from which a WSI is generated.

“**BIGPICTURE License**”* refers to the legal arrangement (terms of use) between the Data Submitter and the end-user, or the place the Data will be deposited, specifying what users can do with the Data defined at Data submission. There are likely to be several types of BIGPICTURE Licenses to be chosen from by the Data Submitter.

The terms defined in the GDPR, such as “**personal data**”, “**controller**”, “**processor**”, “**data subject**”, “**pseudonymization**” will be used in the meaning of this act, however will not be capitalized in this document.

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DAC	Data Access Committee
DoA	Description of Action under GA945358
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment

DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSR	Data Subject Rights
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
WP	Work Package
WSI	Whole Slide Image

Background

Based on the DoA and reconfirmed thorough discussions with WP3, the following facts and assumptions were taken into considerations when preparing the report⁴:

- The clinical part of the BIGPICTURE data repository will consist of digital scans of slides of human tissues or biological samples (WSI, whole slide images). The original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies. Thus, the original slides will not be collected directly and primarily for the purpose of digitization for the BIGPICTURE data repository.
- The BIGPICTURE data repository will also include WSI from animal tissues (non-clinical WSIs) that are also going to be digitized slides from existing collections. The BIGPICTURE repository will only include digital slides (WSIs), not the glass originals or biological samples.
- The WSI will be accompanied by Metadata (i.e. not only image will be stored). Scope of the metadata may vary, depending on the type of WSI. Metadata parameters will be defined by the Metadata & Nomenclature Task Force.
- The purpose of BIGPICTURE is to store WSI and related Metadata (“**Data**”) and facilitate access to Data for scientific and research purposes.
- The Data Submitters will have or will digitize Slides generated as part of clinical diagnostic work that, in some instances, will also have been used in clinical studies. Some Data Submitters may also contribute medical data which was generated as part of the research projects which involved the collected samples. There may be additionally data from archives⁵.
- No animal experimentation will be performed for the purpose of data collection in the project.
- Additional patient information may accompany WSI in the Metadata. The final list will be provided at a later stage, as outlined in D3.2. Results from genomic investigation may be used as associated data in some WSI collections.

1. Protection of personal data

Initial Data Submitters are located in the Member States of the European Union (EU), with the exception of one submitter (i.e. LTHTNHS) located in the United Kingdom (UK). Therefore, in this part of the report we will discuss the rules resulting from the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/67910 (“**GDPR**”)⁶ and the national laws applicable to protection of personal data.

The GDPR provides the basic provisions constituting the general legal framework applicable in all Member States of the European Economic Area in relation to the protection of personal data. In the

⁴ Please note that these assumptions have been updated to reflect the project’s progress, when compared to the background information provided initially to the country experts (as seen in the country reports). The updates and purpose of BIGPICTURE have been however discussed with the country experts during collection and refining of the reports.

⁵ E.g. results from blood tests, diagnoses, treatment, etc. that are kept as patient records in the hospital information system and/or in a Research database (RDA, <https://www.meduniwien.ac.at/web/mitarbeiterinnen/it-hilfe-support/it4science/plattformen/rda/>).

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1–88).

UK, the GDPR is retained in domestic law as the “UK GDPR.” For now, the rules of the (EU) GDPR discussed below are also in place in the UK under the UK GDPR. However, for the future, UK will have the independence to revise its framework.

When considering the legal frameworks relating to protection of data in the EU and UK, also national laws of the Data Submitters jurisdictions need to be examined. As observed by the study “Assessment of the EU Member States’ rules on health data in the light of GDPR” conducted recently by the European Commission in the context of preliminary preparations for the creation of EHDS (“**EC Health Data Study**”), the laws are very fragmented and vary from country to country. The authors of the study state: “*The GDPR provides that Member State legislators may adopt legislation to allow for use of data for research in accordance with Article 9(2)(j) and 89(1). It is clear from the responses provided by the correspondents that the Member States have not implemented such legislation in a homogenous way, **resulting in a complex and fragmented landscape for researchers to navigate**. Consequently, differences between Member States in the way the GDPR is implemented and interpreted in the area of scientific research has made data exchange between Member State and EU bodies for research purposes difficult and in some cases highly technical.*”⁷ Furthermore, according to the combined evaluation roadmap/Inception Impact Assessment⁸ for the EDHS initiative while the GDPR sets out the EU data protection rules, the “*Member States may **further specify some aspects in specific areas, such as health data, which they have done to a large extent**. As a result, the processing of personal health data in Member States is fragmented, leading to obstacles and to limited access of researchers and public institutions, that in turn reduces the EU competitiveness and innovation potential at a global level.*”

Being aware of the varying national rules on the (re)use of health data, a number of questions (Q1-Q7) in the questionnaire for the country respondents focused on those rules. Summary of the findings from the received responses will be provided below. However, in order to discuss those rules, it is pivotal to assess whether and to what extent the WSI and related Metadata should be considered as “personal data” under GDPR, thereby triggering its applicability. After this discussion, we will outline the principles of the data protection, which will need to be considered in the project, with the focus on the specific rules of national laws which are applicable to BIGPICTURE Data Submitters.

1.1. Definition of “personal data” in the context of WSI

The term “**personal data**” is broadly defined in the GDPR as any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (data subject).⁹ An identified or identifiable natural person for the purposes of the GDPR is “one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.”¹⁰ Thus, the term personal data comprises not only directly identifiable information (such as names, addresses, contact information, national ID number), but also indirectly identifiable information (such as pseudonymous information where data can only be linked to a specific semantically meaningless number, such as alphanumeric code).

The information must make that person “**identified or identifiable**.” An **identified person** is distinguishable from other members in a group. A person described by a data record is considered to be **identifiable** if any actor exists at present or in the future who is able to identify the data subject by using any realistically available additional information and linking methodology.¹¹ Identification can be direct – meaning that the initial data record and information available to the actor are linked without the use of additional information - or indirect – meaning that initial data record needs to be linked with

⁷ Assessment of the EU Member States’ rules on health data in the light of GDPR (https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/default/files/ehealth/docs/ms_rules_health-data_en.pdf), further referred to as “EC Health Data Study”, pg. 58.

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12663-Digital-health-data-and-services-the-European-health-data-space_en

⁹ Article 4(1) GDPR.

¹⁰ *Ibidem*.

¹¹ This definition and further analysis of concepts of identified or identifiable person in: “Towards a Better Understanding of Identification, Pseudonymization, and Anonymization” (<https://www.datenschutzzentrum.de/artikel/1372-.html>).

additional information and then with information available to the actor¹², thus multiple pieces of information must be put together.

In this context it is important to delineate two terms, which relate to the definition of personal data: pseudonymization and anonymization.

Article 4(5) GDPR defines **pseudonymization** as “the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.”

“**Anonymous information**” is one which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable (recital 26 GDPR). When putting together information to make a person identifiable, recital 26 to the GDPR provides that the threshold is that it must concern “means reasonably likely to be used.” In assessing such *reasonableness*, “account should be taken of all objective factors, such as the costs of and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments.” Important to note is that this notion of *reasonableness* can evolve over time. It may occur that at the start of a processing operation the state of technology does not make identifiability of a person reasonably likely. However, if the processed information is stored for a certain duration, technology may become available during that time that does make identification reasonably likely. Given the rapid development of data mining tools, it is therefore very likely that data previously not considered as personal data may sooner or later become personal data. This means that any kind of information should be assessed on a case-by-case basis to ascertain whether it renders a natural person identified or reasonably likely to be identifiable.

Based on the information received from the country reports, human WSI with patient Metadata will be considered as personal data if this Metadata will allow linking the WSI back to the patient. In particular, the **German** report notes that: “*it should be noted that WSI represent high-resolution images of a tumor. The use of tumor images for research and education has not been restricted by data protection regulations(...) it is not possible to identify the patient from an image of his/her tumor, therefore images represent anonymous information. If the tumor image is linked to other biological datasets of an individual (e.g., via metadata which are part of additional datasets), more complex regulation¹³ are relevant.*” Also, in **Belgium**: “*Associated data, more specifically personal data related to health, are collected alongside samples, hence, in the context of HBM [HBM meaning “human body material” - comment by TLX] procurement, the data protection rules apply too. Images of human body samples are “data” (“personal data” if the person concerned is identifiable).*”

In BIGPICTURE, as described in *D3.2 Minimal dataset deliverable*, each WSI’s Metadata (either from human or an animal) will contain a “Biological Being ID” which is “a unique identifier of the Biological Being”, for example “PAT0001.” While this is not the deciding criterium (see further comments below), yet for human WSIs, if the controller (Data Submitter) or any other party will be able to trace back the Biological Being ID to the individual from which the Specimen was taken, this would indicate that the WSI is “identifiable” information. This would in particular be the case, if the Data Submitter keeps a key mapping of the Biological Being IDs with the patients’ identities at its premises.¹⁴

Furthermore, if the WSI will contain also Metadata about the diagnosis of the person (defined in D3.2 as “diagnosis that is associated to the entire image”, either in English or based on established coding system), WSI would contain “data concerning health” which is a special category of personal data

¹² “Towards a Better Understanding...”, pg. 25.

¹³ The said regulations are consent rules which are applicable to personal data.

¹⁴ At the time of preparing of this report, we are aware that some of the Data Submitters will be mapping the IDs and then providing anonymous data. For instance, RÖ plans to submit anonymous data only, with no possibility to link submitted data back to patient identities, which is indeed all that the ethical review approval that they obtained for this activity allows. Biological Being ID will be randomly assigned, and only guaranteed to be consistent inside each dataset or study.

under GDPR¹⁵. These data would be pseudonymized, assuming that key which maps the Biological Being ID codes with the patient data will be kept separately by the Data Submitter and protected by technical and organisational measures and that the remaining Metadata or WSI itself would not allow to identify the patient. This is because data are not pseudonymous if a specific person is identifiable from the data solely without additional information. This could happen when indirect identifiers and exceptional records enable identification, even if direct identifiers (e.g., names) are stored separately and securely. Pseudonymisation is also unsuccessful if an outside person is able to determine the original values based on the pseudonyms.

Even when the Data Submitter assigns the Biological Being ID randomly and does not keep a list of the IDs mapped against the identity of the patient, this may not by itself be sufficient to state that the Data is anonymous. This because Data are anonymous and fall outside of the scope of the GDPR only if - considering all the circumstances¹⁶ - the threshold of “identifiable” information is not met. This threshold is particularly difficult to reach for health data, while retaining its usefulness for the research which is to be conducted, not to mention complying with arising obligations of using quality data in research (e.g., for AI training¹⁷). In particular, in its guidance on Ethics & Governance of Artificial Intelligence for Health¹⁸, World Health Organization points out that *“Anonymization may not be possible during health data collection. For example, in predictive AI, time-course data must be collected from a single individual at several times, obviating anonymization until data at all time points are collected. Furthermore, **while anonymization may minimize the risks of (re-)identification of a person, it can reduce the positive benefits of health data, including re-assembly of fragments of an individual’s health data into a comprehensive profile of a patient, which is required for some forms of AI such as predictive algorithms of mortality. Furthermore, anonymization may undermine a person’s right to control their own data and how it may be used. (...)**”*

Also, a paper published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) and European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) on “10 misunderstandings related to anonymisation” states that it is a common misunderstanding that anonymization of data is always possible. Moreover, those authorities observe that *“it is not always possible to lower the re-identification risk below a previously defined threshold whilst retaining a useful dataset for a specific processing.”*¹⁹

In this context, an important note is to be found in Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (WP29)²⁰ in its Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymization Techniques (WP216). WP29 stated that *“when a data controller does not delete the original (identifiable) data at event-level, and the data controller hands over part of this dataset (for example after removal or masking of identifiable data), the resulting dataset is still personal data”*²¹. Following this interpretation, if the decision was taken on anonymization of data, the Data Submitter would need to delete the medical records containing WSI from their systems²². Moreover, also in its opinion the Article 29 Working Party admits that truly anonymous information is rare. Many so-called anonymization techniques can be reversed, or still result in information that could be coupled with other information to make a natural personal reasonably identifiable.

¹⁵ Under Article 4(15) GDPR ‘data concerning health’ means personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status. Article 9 GDPR provides additional rules for processing of special categories of personal data, including data concerning health.

¹⁶ Some practical examples can be found in <https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/en/services/data-management-guidelines/anonymisation-and-identifiers/>.

¹⁷ According to Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts (COM/2021/206 final) available here: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0206>, data sets used to train high-risk AI systems will need to fulfil quality criteria described in Article 10 (2)-(5), which include, inter alia, that they must be relevant, representative, free of errors and complete, and have appropriate statistical properties.

¹⁸ <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240029200>

¹⁹ https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/publications/papers/aepd-edps-joint-paper-10-misunderstandings-related_en

²⁰ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party is now replaced by the European Data Protection Board, however the position papers of WP29 are still often referred to, even without formal endorsement decision.

²¹ https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp216_en.pdf

²² Please note that this WP29 interpretation is not legally binding and is often contested by researchers as the correct approach (e.g., Khaled El Emam, Cecilia Álvarez, A critical appraisal of the Article 29 Working Party Opinion 05/2014 on data anonymization techniques, International Data Privacy Law, Volume 5, Issue 1, February 2015, Pages 73–87, <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipu033>). Moreover existing repositories of medical images often claim that the data is provided as “anonymous”.

In the context of BIGPICTURE, the responses from the legal experts confirm that **there is neither universal understanding or threshold for anonymization of health data nor conclusive guidelines issued by relevant authorities.** For instance, as noted by the **UK** report “*generally speaking, whether the data should be considered anonymous is evaluated from the perspective of the recipient of the data. Ultimately, it is the hospital which decides whether the data is anonymous or not (...).*” While the **Finnish** expert notes that “*The level of de-identification of data that would fulfil the criteria of anonymous data further to understanding adopted by the Finnish data protection authorities (in line with the WP29 opinion on data anonymization) may be difficult to achieve in relation to health data, in particular WSI.*”

This factor is likely to impact the BIGPICTURE project. Moreover, if the human WSI will include a Metadata identifier which will allow any party (including the Data Submitter) to link the WSI to the individual patient (for instance because the Data Submitter will keep a key which links the assigned Biological Being IDs with patient names), they would not be viewed as anonymous in the light of the GDPR. However, as noted above, even lack of linking of the Data to the patient via mapped Biological Being ID does not necessarily mean that the Data is anonymous.

All in all, given the aims of the project, the repository should be built to have the capability to process sensitive personal data contained in the contributed WSIs and Metadata, however this does not imply that all WSIs will be personal data, as some Data Submitters may chose to provide anonymous information.

Conclusion: BIGPICTURE will most likely not be able to provide tools or guidance which will provide assurance for the anonymity of slides for all jurisdictions in scope. These tools may be provided as means of assistance to the Data Submitters. However, the assessment whether the goal in terms of sufficiently anonymized or pseudonymized data was reached will always be on the Data Submitter (as the controller).

Conclusion (2): If the Data Submitter is contributing pseudonymized data, the Biological Being ID mapping key must be kept separately by the Data Submitter (in particular the key should not submitted to BIGPICTURE) and protected by technical and organisational measures (e.g., secured at the Data Submitter’s premises). It must be checked that the disclosed Metadata does not allow patient identification even without access to the key.

Conclusion (3): If the Data Submitter is contributing anonymized data, they should verify that the patient would not be identifiable from the Data, even if Biological Being ID is a “random” value which is not mapped against the actual patient record. In particular, Data Submitter must evaluate that the patient cannot be identified due to number of different data points in the Metadata or their unique combination, despite certain identifiers (such as name or ID number) being removed.

Please note that further comments in section 1 below are provided based on the assumption that (some of) the clinical WSIs will be provided as pseudonymized data and thus GDPR will apply to them.

1.2. GDPR key requirements in the context of BIGPICTURE

The GDPR implies compliance with seven key principles:²³

- lawfulness, fairness and transparency – meaning that a legal basis for any data processing (including but not limited to consent) must be available, and that the persons concerned must be appropriately informed of how their data will be used;
- purpose limitation – meaning that data must be collected for specific purposes, and may thereafter only be used for compatible purposes;

²³ As enshrined in Article 5 (1) and (2) GDPR.

- data minimisation – meaning that data collected and used in the project must be as minimal as possible, taking into account the intended purposes;
- accuracy – meaning that measures must be taken to ensure the quality and accuracy of the data, and that measures must be available to detect and remedy problems;
- storage limitation – meaning that data may only be retained for as long as necessary given the intended purposes, and that it must thereafter be deleted or anonymised;
- integrity and confidentiality – meaning that data must be protected by appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure its confidentiality, integrity and availability;
- accountability – meaning that responsible entities must be identified, and that appropriate controls (such as logs) are available to ensure that any problems can be attributed to the correct entity.

While a detailed discussion of all the principles is beyond the scope of this report, below we discuss the key considerations for BIGPICTURE Data contribution and repository set up, as provided in the GDPR and country expert reports. The report does not aim to provide an exhaustive list of all potential privacy issues which need to be dealt with within this project. For instance, given the scope of the project, other matters which need to be addressed and accounted for should include:

- transfers of personal data outside of EEA (in compliance with Chapter V GDPR),
- detection and reporting of data breaches (in compliance with Articles 33 and 34 GDPR),
- consultations with supervisory authorities (in particular, in circumstances foreseen under Article 36 GDPR).

1.2.1. Lawfulness

Under the GDPR the concept of “processing” is very broadly defined²⁴ and thus submission of the clinical WSIs containing personal information (as noted above) to the BIGPICTURE project would be considered “processing of personal data”. Thus, the main question for Data Submitters (acting as controllers) contributing the clinical WSIs is determining whether they can substantiate a legal basis for the WSIs and Metadata to be submitted and used.

Articles 6 and 9 GDPR provide the following legal basis for processing of personal data.

<p>Article 6.1</p>
<p>1. Processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies:</p> <p>(a) the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes;</p> <p>(b) processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract;</p> <p>(c) processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject;</p> <p>(d) processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person;</p> <p>(e) processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller;</p>

²⁴ Article 4(2) GDPR 'processing' means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction;

(f) processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.

Point (f) of the first subparagraph shall not apply to processing carried out by public authorities in the performance of their tasks.

Article 9

1. Processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.

2. Paragraph 1 shall not apply if one of the following applies:

- (a) the data subject has given explicit consent to the processing of those personal data for one or more specified purposes, except where Union or Member State law provide that the prohibition referred to in paragraph 1 may not be lifted by the data subject;
- (b) processing is necessary for the purposes of carrying out the obligations and exercising specific rights of the controller or of the data subject in the field of employment and social security and social protection law in so far as it is authorised by Union or Member State law or a collective agreement pursuant to Member State law providing for appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject;
- (c) processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person where the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent;
- (d) processing is carried out in the course of its legitimate activities with appropriate safeguards by a foundation, association or any other not-for-profit body with a political, philosophical, religious or trade union aim and on condition that the processing relates solely to the members or to former members of the body or to persons who have regular contact with it in connection with its purposes and that the personal data are not disclosed outside that body without the consent of the data subjects;
- (e) processing relates to personal data which are manifestly made public by the data subject;
- (f) processing is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims or whenever courts are acting in their judicial capacity;
- (g) processing is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest, on the basis of Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject;
- (h) processing is necessary for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine, for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, medical diagnosis, the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and services on the basis of Union or Member State law or pursuant to contract with a health professional and subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 3;
- (i) processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, such as protecting against serious cross-border threats to health or ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices, on the basis of Union or Member State law which provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject, in particular professional secrecy;

- (j) processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) based on Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.
3. Personal data referred to in paragraph 1 may be processed for the purposes referred to in point (h) of paragraph 2 when those data are processed by or under the responsibility of a professional subject to the obligation of professional secrecy under Union or Member State law or rules established by national competent bodies or by another person also subject to an obligation of secrecy under Union or Member State law or rules established by national competent bodies.
4. Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health.

In general, as follows from desk research and the country expert reports, the landscape regarding use of the above listed legal basis for the reuse of health data collected for other purposes (in particular in clinical or clinical trial context) is very fragmented. More specifically, the permissible legal basis largely depends on national laws and practice. This conclusion is concurrent with the finding of the EC Health Data Study²⁵ that *“It is clear from the views shared in the workshops and by country correspondents to the legal and technical survey that while the GDPR is a much appreciated piece of legislation, **variation in interpretation of the law and national level legislation linked to its implementation have led to a fragmented approach which makes cross-border cooperation for care provision, healthcare system administration or research difficult.**”* Furthermore: *“Given that the GDPR foresees the possibility of special legislation for processing of genetic information, it is not surprising that **significant variation** may exist between some Member States in this area”²⁶.* Moreover, the national laws may provide specific rules regarding use of health data (Article 9.4 GDPR).

However, while potentially different legal bases may be considered, in practice what transpires from the reports is that the “choice” of the legal basis of use for the Data Submitter would be narrowed to the following options:

- obtaining consent from the patients as data subjects (Article 6(1)a and Article 9(2)(a) GDPR) or
- “scientific privilege” i.e. re-use of existing data collected for other purpose under certain conditions and safeguards (Article 5(1)(b) and 89(2) GDPR).

The latter possibility may be also conflated with a separate legal basis for re-use of data and considered provided for under Article 6(1)(e) or (f) in conjunction with Article 9(2)(j) GDPR and, if applicable, national provisions. Such approach seems to be presented by Article 29 Working Party Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679 which explicitly point out that *“The GDPR does not restrict the application of Article 6 to consent alone, with regard to processing data for research purposes. As long as appropriate safeguards are in place, such as the requirements under Article 89(1), and the processing is fair, lawful, transparent and accords with data minimisation standards and individual rights, other lawful bases such as Article 6(1)(e) or (f) may be available. This also applies to special categories of data pursuant to the derogation of Article 9(2)(j)”²⁷.* This is further discussed in “Purpose limitation” section, while below we will focus on consent as one of the possible options for submitters.

In the context of BIGPICTURE, consent was indicated as the dominant basis for the submitting and use of WSI and Metadata for research purposes, with limited exceptions to this rule.

In particular, in **Italy** *“Prior informed consent of the patient is the general legal basis for research on*

²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/default/files/ehealth/docs/ms_rules_health_data_en.pdf, further as “EC Health Data Study”, pg. 9, Executive summary.

²⁶ EC Health Data Study, pg. 26

²⁷ Guidelines on Consent under Regulation 2016/679 (wp259rev.01) <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/623051/en>, pg. 28.

health data and samples. The art. 110 of the D.Lgs 196/2003 (Personal data protection code) provides exceptions to the consent rule” (response to Q3). Consequently, “if consent cannot be obtained (art. 110 D.Lgs. 196/2003), or it requires a disproportionate effort, the research project must be approved by the local ethical committee and the research project must be submitted to prior consultation with the Italian Privacy Authority “(response to Q32).

In **Germany** “In most cases patient’s consent is required (...) Using patient’s data without consent requires a dataset-based examination (...) In this examination, the data protection concept, major interest of research and the patient’s protection-worthy interest in the data are being are balanced against each other. The researcher’s academic freedom must outweigh patient’s fundamental right of informational self-determination. If this is the case, the data / material might be used. Specifically for WSIs, if those conditions are fulfilled, the data provider could provide the slides to the project, even if they were collected initially for another purpose” (response to Q4).

In **Finland**, the situation is different: “Consent is required for physically or psychologically invasive research (...) but for processing personal data consent is just one of the options for legal bases. The questions and this response largely relate to use of data not initially collected for research. Secondary use of samples/data is possible subject to the rules described (...)” (response to Q4). Specifically, the **Finnish** law provides specific rules on the use of health data for scientific research purposes, if suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights of the data subject are in place.

Also in **Belgium** the law “does not impose the use of consent as a legal ground for (primary) data processing, hence the data processing may be based on any of the six legal bases described in Article 6(1) of the GDPR. Regarding further processing of data, the rules established in the GDPR and the rules of the Belgian Data Protection Law, as cited above, apply. However, informed consent as an ethical requirement for procurement of HBM for scientific research is needed, with some exceptions” (response to Q4). Nevertheless, the consent rules still apply (with some exceptions) with respect to obtaining and using human biological material.

Given the above, it would not be possible to indicate to the Data Submitters which legal basis is appropriate for their submission of their Data, much less impose a particular basis (e.g., consent) for everyone. The expert reports indicate that ensuring a legal basis should be a responsibility of the Data Submitter and the conditions and the applicable basis vary, depending on the national law and also on the context in which the data were collected. Moreover, contingent on the set up of the roles of the partners in the consortium (see section 1.2.8.2 Roles of the involved parties below), other partners which will process the data as controllers, may need to validate whether they would be permitted to do so. The project will further investigate those rules during the definition of the honest broker mechanism (WP3) and more detailed work on the set-up of the repository.

Last, but not least, in the event that the Data Submitter decides to collect consents from the data subjects it would need to ensure that such consent meets the requirements of the GDPR.²⁸ Fulfilment of those conditions is not easy, in particular it may require re-consenting for use of data which were collected from patients in another context. This may lead to decrease in the availability and diversity of the data.

Conclusion: Each Data Submitter must check whether they can assure that they have the appropriate legal basis to contribute Data to BIGPICTURE. In many cases consent of the data subject may be the appropriate legal basis, however ensuring that this consent fulfils the requirements of the GDPR is not easy.

1.2.2. Fairness and transparency

The rule of transparency states that data must be processed in a transparent matter in relation to the data subject. This rule is closely linked to information rights (Art. 13-14 GDPR) and data subject rights

²⁸ Article 4 (11) provides for definition for consent under which it is freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject’s wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her. Article 7 GDPR provides for further conditions of consent.

(“DSR”, Art. 15-21 GDPR). Under those provisions, in general, data subjects must be properly informed about the details of processing of their data for a specific purpose (also in case the data are not collected directly from the data subject).²⁹ There are very limited exceptions from this requirement. For example, under Article 14(5)(b) GDPR, if the data are collected **not directly** from the data subject, the requirement to provide him/her with information does not apply if the provision of such information proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort, in particular for processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in Article 89(1) or in so far as the obligation to provide information is likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the objectives of that processing.³⁰ If the data are collected **directly** from the data subject, this exception does not apply.

In the context of BIGPICTURE, the transparency of the processing vis-à-vis the data subjects should be ensured through appropriate notices and policies, such as properly drafted information language made available to patients (unless exception applies), privacy notice on the repository website and clear description in any agreements to be entered into by the Data Submitters, such as BIGPICTURE License.

Data subject rights give the data subject possibilities to obtain information about processing and - in cases specified by the law - influence such processing.

These rights are set out in Chapter III of the GDPR, and include the rights of the data subject to :

- obtain information about the processing of their personal data (Article 15(1) GDPR)
- obtain access to the personal data held about them and copy of the data (Article 15(1) and 15(3) GDPR)
- ask for incorrect, inaccurate or incomplete personal data to be corrected (Article 16 GDPR);
- request that personal data be erased when it’s no longer needed or if processing it is unlawful (right to be forgotten, Article 17 GDPR);
- request the restriction of the processing of their personal data in specific cases (Article 18 GDPR);
- receive personal data in a machine-readable format and send it to another controller (‘data portability’, Article 20 GDPR);
- object to the processing of their personal data for marketing purposes or on grounds relating to their particular situation (Article 21 GDPR);
- request that decisions based on automated processing concerning them or significantly affecting them and based on their personal data are made by natural persons, not only by computers. They also have the right in this case to express their point of view and to contest the decision (Article 22 GDPR).

However, according to Article 89(2) GDPR there are possible exceptions to the rules of transparency. In particular, where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 GDPR subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.

According to the country reports, the following countries made use of this possibility: **Belgium, Finland, Germany, the Netherlands.**

In **Belgium**, while exceptions are provided, the regime of making use of them is quite complex: “A

²⁹ Detailed list of information to be provided is included in Articles 13 and 14 GDPR.

³⁰ While whether the exception applies needs to be decided on a case by case basis, some arguments which may be invoked relate to consequences of providing information to the data subjects to the research objectives. In other cases, it may not be possible to contact the patients which have been treated long time ago or re-contacting them may be unethical.

controller for scientific or historical research or for statistical purposes may consider that he can comply with all the provisions of the GDPR and therefore not rely, or only partly rely, on the derogations provided for according to Art. 89(2) of the GDPR” (response to Q3). Thus, there are various scenarios which may be followed by the controller. If however the controller wishes to take benefit of the derogations, “Title 4 provides for appropriate safeguards which the controller wishing to derogate from the rights of data subjects must implement.”

Also in other jurisdictions there are certain conditions which apply if controller wishes to makes use of the exceptions from data subjects’ rights. In particular in **Finland**, while there are statutory deviations from the rights provided in Articles 15, 16, 18 or 21, it is also required that: “1) the processing is based on an appropriate research plan; 2) a person or group responsible for the research has been designated; and 3) the personal data are used and disclosed only for scientific or historical research purposes or for other compatible purposes, and the procedure followed is also otherwise such that data concerning a given individual are not revealed to outsiders” (response to Q3).

In **Germany** “the rights of the data subject provided for in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 GDPR are limited to the extent that these rights are likely to make the realization of the research or statistical purposes impossible or seriously impair the restriction is necessary for the fulfilment of research or statistical purposes. In addition, the right to information according to Art. 15 GDPR does not exist if the data are necessary for purposes of scientific research and the provision of information would require a disproportionate effort” (response to Q5).

In other countries, such as **UK, Italy and Sweden** there are no national law exceptions to the rules of Article 15-21 GDPR.³¹

Conclusion: Where possible and legally required, privacy notices should be drafted and made available to the data subjects, unless specific exemption applies. This includes preparing privacy information about processing of data in the context of BIGPICTURE which would be available on the platform.

Conclusion (2): Each Data Submitter must check whether they must enable data subjects to exercise their DSR rights. The consortium must agree on how the process of handling DSR will be carried out. In particular, to what extent the BIGPICTURE infrastructure can technically and legally enable the exercise of the DSR rights (e.g., deletion of the data).

1.2.3. Purpose limitation

The GDPR allows special considerations for situations when personal data to be used in a research project were originally collected for a purpose other than scientific research. This is the situation applicable to WSIs and Metadata in BIGPICTURE project. The Slides from which the WSIs are generated were collected for other purposes i.e. for most part are derived from clinical studies conducted by the Data Submitters or from provision of health services by them.

The basis for these considerations is related to the fundamental data protection principle of “purpose limitation” enshrined in Article 5(1)(b) GDPR. According to this principle personal data must be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and may not be further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes. There is an important caveat to this rule: further processing for, inter alia, scientific research purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1) GDPR, not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purpose. Further explanation of purpose limitation principle is provided in recital 50 of the GDPR. The full wording of those provisions is cited below.

This is often referred to as “presumption of compatibility” under which “*in principle personal data collected in the commercial or healthcare context, for example, may be further used for scientific research purposes, by the original or a new controller, if appropriate safeguards are in place*”.³²

³¹ Exceptions from Article 14.5 may still apply.

³² European Data Protection Supervisor Preliminary opinion of 6 January 2020 on data protection and scientific research, https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/20-01-06_opinion_research_en.pdf

Article 5.1. (a) (b)
<p>1. Personal data shall be:</p> <p>(a) processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject ('lawfulness, fairness and transparency');</p> <p>(b) collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes ('purpose limitation')</p>
Article 89
<p>Safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes</p> <p>1. Processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this Regulation, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.</p> <p>2. Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.</p> <p>3. Where personal data are processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18, 19, 20 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.</p> <p>4. Where processing referred to in paragraphs 2 and 3 serves at the same time another purpose, the derogations shall apply only to processing for the purposes referred to in those paragraphs.</p>
Recital 50
<p>(50) The processing of personal data for purposes other than those for which the personal data were initially collected should be allowed only where the processing is compatible with the purposes for which the personal data were initially collected. In such a case, no legal basis separate from that which allowed the collection of the personal data is required. If the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller, Union or Member State law may determine and specify the tasks and purposes for which the further processing should be regarded as compatible and lawful. Further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes should be considered to be compatible lawful processing operations. The legal basis provided by Union or Member State law for the processing of personal data may also provide a legal basis for further processing. In order to ascertain whether a purpose of further processing is compatible with the purpose for which the personal data are initially collected, the controller, after having met all the</p>

requirements for the lawfulness of the original processing, should take into account, inter alia: any link between those purposes and the purposes of the intended further processing; the context in which the personal data have been collected, in particular the reasonable expectations of data subjects based on their relationship with the controller as to their further use; the nature of the personal data; the consequences of the intended further processing for data subjects; and the existence of appropriate safeguards in both the original and intended further processing operations.

On the basis of these provisions, and supported by the local law, some countries allow that - under defined conditions - the medical data collected for other purpose may be re-used for research without the explicit consent of the patients.

According to the country reports, this may be possible in **Belgium, Germany, Italy, UK, Sweden** and **Finland**. In **Netherlands** however patient “opt-in” (affirmative consent) is usually required. Only in limited cases the consent provided earlier may be sufficient to justify a new research project requiring additional data use. However, *“this needs to be reviewed on a case-by-case basis. Usually, some level of review of the anticipated research proposal will be needed (e.g., by a data access committee). This review will also verify whether the intended reuse of data matches the original purpose of the data collection (including wording of the consent which was provided earlier)”* (response to Q3).

The conditions that allow data re-use vary greatly between the Data Submitter’s jurisdictions. Usually, they are connected with obtaining the approval of an ethics committee (as further explained in section 3 Ethical requirements below) and providing a guarantee of appropriate safeguards. Examples are provided below, however country reports should be consulted for further information.

In particular in the **UK** *“Data can be reused for scientific research provided consent or exemption (based on the Control of Patient Information Regulation and Section 251 of the NHS Act 2006, for e.g., in case of pandemic, for public concern, in regard to specific cancer types, for secret research) is in place and a Research Ethics Committee review is favourable”* (response to Q4).

Safeguards may be specified in detail or be left to the discretion of the researcher. In particular for **Finland** the law provides for a non-exclusive list of examples of the safeguards, such as:

- *“measures that enable subsequent checking and verification of the identity of the person who has recorded, altered or transferred personal data;*
- *measures to improve the competence of the personnel processing personal data;*
- *designation of a data protection officer;*
- *internal measures by the controller and the processor for preventing access to personal data;*
- *pseudonymisation of personal data;*
- *encryption of personal data;*
- *measures that ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services related to the processing of personal data, including the ability to restore the availability of and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;*
- *a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing;*
- *specific rules of procedure for ensuring compliance with the Data Protection Regulation and this Act when personal data are transferred or processed for another purpose;*
- *a data protection impact assessment in accordance with Article 35 of the Data Protection Regulation;*
- *other technical, procedural and organisational measures.”* (response to Q5).

Also in **Belgium**, the list of general safeguards is provided in Title 4 Belgian Data Protection Law, in particular in Articles 190 to 204 thereof. They would only apply to a controller which “*may achieve his purposes only by derogating from the principles and obligations and rights of the data subjects*” and if no code of conduct, approved in accordance with Article 40 of the GDPR is respected.

Conclusion: Selection of an appropriate legal basis for the submission of the Data must be tackled on a case-by-case basis for each Data Submitter separately, taking into account compliance with the national law and practice on re-use of health data for research purposes and that these WSIs may be made available to other researchers in line with the project’s objectives.

1.2.4. Data minimisation

Under the rule of data minimalization data collected and used in the BIGPICTURE project must be as minimal as possible, taking into account the intended purposes. This implies that:

- Data should not be held for further use, unless this is essential for reasons that were stated in advance.
- Data should only include as much data as required to successfully answer the research question(s).
- Data collected for one purpose cannot be repurposed without further consent. However, certain exceptions to this rule apply, as discussed under section 1.2.3 Purpose limitation above.

It has been observed that there is certain tension between complying with the principle of data minimalization and “reaping the benefits of <<big data>>.”³³

In the context of BIGPICTURE, the discussions about scope of the data needed evolve around Metadata which is to be accompanying the images. The current outcome of those discussions is provided in *D3.2 Minimal dataset deliverable*. Notwithstanding the requirements of the minimal Metadata, Data Submitters can at their own discretion provide additional Metadata, on top of what is defined as “minimum required” by BIGPICTURE. In such cases, they would need to similarly motivate the necessity for the increased scope, outside of the needs given by BIGPICTURE.

Conclusion: Discussions and agreement regarding the minimal dataset accompanying the WSI must take into account the rule of data minimization, in particular be aligned with research objectives for the creation of the repository. Reasons for the scope of the data should be documented.

1.2.5. Accuracy

According to the accuracy principle, personal data must be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay.

The principle of accuracy is closely linked to the quality of data. It is argued that it applies to data itself, and not to further decisions made using the data (inferences drawn from that data).³⁴ This implies that BIGPICTURE must take and document steps to ensure that WSIs are of representative quality (as agreed by the relevant partners) and contain accurate Metadata. There should also be a process of removing and correcting incorrect or misleading data. This will also play a role when a data subject would exercise their DSR to rectify personal data. In order to keep the data accurate and up-to-date, data subjects should have the opportunity to update their personal data when it is inaccurate. However, some jurisdictions may allow exceptions for DSR - see section 1.2.2 above.

³³ Finck, Michèle & Biega, Asia. (2021). Reviving Purpose Limitation and Data Minimisation in Personalisation, Profiling and Decision-Making Systems, <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/2101/2101.06203.pdf>

³⁴ Study: How the GDPR changes the rules of scientific research, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634447/EPRS_STU\(2019\)634447_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634447/EPRS_STU(2019)634447_EN.pdf)

BIGPICTURE is taking significant effort in ensuring quality of its data. In particular the work will include developing standards and guidelines for generating WSI data and establishing a European Digital Pathology Quality Control Centre (T5.7).

Conclusion: BIGPICTURE must take and document steps to ensure that WSIs are accurate, of appropriate quality and contain accurate Metadata. There should also be a process of removing and correcting incorrect or misleading data, in particular at the legitimate request of a data subject (unless an exception applies).

1.2.6. Storage limitation

Under the storage limitation principle, personal data must be kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. However, personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) GDPR subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by the GDPR in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject. This does not however imply that data stored for scientific research may be kept forever. Data Submitters (and accordingly data subjects) must be informed about the retention period, or at least its basis and rationale. After this period lapses, the data must be removed or anonymized.

Conclusion: Data Submitters and other controllers within the BIGPICTURE project must define a retention period for the pseudonymized WSIs and their associated Metadata that are collected for the participation in BIGPICTURE and/or available in the repository.

1.2.7. Integrity and confidentiality

The obligation described in this point means that personal data must be protected by appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure its confidentiality, integrity and availability, as provided in Article 32 GDPR. This is closely related to requirements to provide appropriate safeguards under Article 89(2) GDPR. Moreover, the country experts were asked to identify data localization and infrastructure requirements (Q18-20).

1.2.7.1. Security requirements

Article 32 GDPR concerns the security of the processing. The controller must implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure an appropriate level of security according to the risks posed by the processing. For this, the state of the art must be considered, as well as the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing, including the risk of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons. Measures that can be taken include:

- the pseudonymization and encryption of personal data;
- the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services;
- the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;
- a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organizational measures for ensuring the security of the processing.

If the controller hires a processor, such processor must provide guarantees to implement security measures (Article 28(2) GDPR). The processor is responsible to take all measures pursuant to Article 32 and may be held liable for infringement of this obligation. Whether a security level is appropriate depends on the precise risks presented by a given processing operation. These can range from

accidental or unlawful destruction, loss and alteration, to unauthorized disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.

Controllers and processors must ensure their employees handling personal data do not process them except as instructed.

This general obligation for ensuring the security of personal data will apply to processing of WSIs and associated Metadata in the context of BIGPICTURE, including to storing them and making them available through the dedicated infrastructure. Most country experts (the **Netherlands, Sweden**) have indicated that there are no other specific rules applicable to security features of infrastructure for storing WSIs, other than the GDPR rules described above. However, based on local practice for the **Netherlands**, *“Usually, an encrypted connection is used for data transfers to meet to these requirements (...) For personal data these are usually interpreted in such a manner that some form of well accepted audit certificate (ISO 27001 or similar national certifications NE7510, NEN7512, NEN7513) is needed to prove that the security requirements are in place. This requirement for certification is usually also included in data processing agreements related to health data”* (responses to Q18 and 20).

In **Finland** *“From 1.5.2022 onwards, unless permanently anonymised, data can be made available only to processing environments verified and approved in accordance with the Secondary Use Act. Permissions granted now will only apply until 30.4.2022. Human biological samples in registered biobanks, technical records of the samples (like WSI) and associated data (sample related metadata, but also related diagnoses etc.) are available on application for research projects from the biobanks. The Biobank Act is expected to be renewed, and it is possible that the renewal will include similar restrictions on processing environments as the Secondary Use Act (see above)”* (response to Q2).

Conclusion: BIGPICTURE must be mindful of the security requirements which are provided in the GDPR and local legislation, to ensure that Data Submitters from those countries can participate. The description of those safeguards should be made available to Data Submitters. In turn, each Data Submitter must check whether the safeguards offered by BIGPICTURE fulfil their requirements.

1.2.7.2. Appointment of a DPO

According to Article 37 GDPR, a data protection officer (“**DPO**”) must be designated if - among other circumstances - if the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on a large scale of special categories of data and personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences. Within a group of entities, a single DPO can be assigned. Even when not required to do so, a DPO may be designated.

Some country experts have indicated national provisions requiring appointment of a DPO. For example, in **Belgium** *“There is also an obligation in the Belgian Data Protection Act to designate a DPO, specifically in cases where personal data are processed for scientific research purposes and the processing may result in a high risk. When personal data is processed for scientific purposes, the controller must anonymize or pseudonymize the personal data after it is collected. In cases of further processing, it is possible to de-pseudonymize the personal data only when necessary for the research purposes and, where applicable, after consulting the DPO. The DPO also must issue opinions on the use of the various pseudonymization and anonymization methods employed. The DPO thus provides an additional layer of security for the storage and processing of health data”* (response to Q20).

The DPO must demonstrate certain professional qualities and expert knowledge of data protection law. It may be a staff member or someone working through an external service contract. The contact details of the DPO must be communicated to the supervisory authority.

According to Article 38 GDPR, the DPO must be involved, properly and in a timely manner, in all issues which relate to the protection of personal data. The DPO is supported in its tasks by the controller and processor and must be able to work without instructions. Data subjects may contact the DPO with issues, as well as for the exercise of their rights.

The DPO must, according to Article 39 GDPR, inform and advise the controller or the processor; monitor compliance; provide advice where requested; cooperate with the supervisory authority; and act as the contact point for the supervisory authority. The DPO must have due regard to the risk associated with processing operations, considering the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing.

In the context of BIGPICTURE, the role of data protection officer is taken by BIGPICTURE GDPR taskforce. However, all organizations hosting the repository must confirm that they have appointed a DPO and contract details of these DPOs are made available to all controllers and processors involved in the project.

Conclusion: The Data Submitters should be required to confirm that they appointed a DPO and if not - that they are exempted from this requirement. All other partners hosting the repository should be required to do the same. Details of DPOs should be exchanged and available for the controllers and processors of BIGPICTURE data.

1.2.8. Accountability

Data controllers within BIGPICTURE must be able to demonstrate compliance with the GDPR principles. While it is not possible to prepare an exhaustive list of documents which are required from BIGPICTURE to achieve this goal, for instance, the following steps should be taken.

1.2.8.1. Record of processing activities

This will entail keeping a record of processing activities, which should include:

- the categories of data subjects from which the data are collected;
- types of data which are collected; what other parties the data is shared with, and, if applicable, details of any transfers of personal data to a third country (i.e., outside the EU);
- the time limits for erasure;
- and a general description of security measures.

1.2.8.2. Roles of the involved parties

Moreover, under the general umbrella of accountability responsibility for addressing obligations under the GDPR with respect to handling WSI should be assigned to involved parties.

The personal data processing operation must be conducted under the responsibility of a **controller**. A controller is, according to Article 4(7) GDPR “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data.” If two or more entities participate in the determination of the purposes and means of a processing operation, they would qualify as **joint controllers**.

A controller may use a **processor**, defined by Article 4(8) GDPR as “a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller.” Given the importance of these two actors, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) provided further guidance on this matter in Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR (“**Guidelines 07/2020**”).³⁵

First, a data controller is usually the organisation as such, and not an individual within the organisation (such as the CEO, an employee or a member of the board), that acts as a controller.

Second, the controller decides on the key elements i.e. determines the purposes (why?) and means (how?) of the processing operation. The controller must decide on both purposes and means. However, some more practical aspects of implementation (“non-essential means”) can be left to the

³⁵ Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR, https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-072020-concepts-controller-and-processor-gdpr_en

processor. Importantly, the controller does not necessarily need to access the data to be qualified as a controller.

Third, as processing operations are becoming exceedingly complex, it is possible that multiple entities can be designated as joint controllers. As noted by the EDPB guidelines, joint participation can take the form of a *common decision* taken by two or more entities or result from *converging decisions* by two or more entities, where the decisions complement each other and are necessary for the processing to take place in such a manner that they have a tangible impact on the determination of the purposes and means of the processing. An important criterion is that the processing would not be possible without both parties' participation in the sense that the processing by each party is inseparable, i.e. inextricably linked.³⁶ Joint controllers should determine and agree on their respective responsibilities for compliance with the obligations under the GDPR in a binding document.³⁷

It is, however, important to distinguish the case where controllers act jointly for the same purpose from the situation where multiple entities each pursue their own means and purposes. As noted by the EDPB, the fact that several actors are involved in the same processing does not mean that they are necessarily acting as joint controllers of such processing.³⁸ For example, exchange of a set of data without jointly determined purposes or means of processing should be considered a transmission of data between two independent controllers. Using a shared infrastructure by different controllers does not necessarily entail joint controllership. On the other hand, existence of joint responsibility does not necessarily imply equal responsibility of the various operators involved in the processing of personal data. The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) in recent rulings³⁹ clarified that those operators may be involved at different stages of that processing and to different degrees so that the level of responsibility of each of them must be assessed with regard to all the relevant circumstances of the particular case.

Forth, regarding the **processor**, the GDPR assumes this entity to act under delegation by the controller and cannot process the data otherwise than according to the controller's instructions. Such delegation should be governed by a controller-processor agreement (data processing agreement, DPA), construed in compliance with Article 28 GDPR. As noted, while the processor may have some leeway to determine the non-essential aspects of the means of the processing, they should have no say over the purposes of the processing.

In the context of research projects, the Guidelines 07/2020 state that *“Several research institutes decide to participate in a specific joint research project and to use to that end the existing platform of one of the institutes involved in the project. Each institute feeds personal data it already holds into the platform for the purpose of the joint research and uses the data provided by others through the platform for carrying out the research. In this case, all institutes qualify as joint controllers for the personal data processing that is done by storing and disclosing information from this platform since they have decided together the purpose of the processing and the means to be used (the existing platform). Each of the institutes however is a separate controller for any other processing that may be carried out outside the platform for their respective purposes.”*

Given the above, in order to impose the proper structure of data protection framework in the BIGPICTURE project is it crucial to carry out an assessment of roles of all consortium partners. This assessment must be made on a factual, rather than a formal, analysis of their actual influence with respect to determining the purposes and means of the collecting the WSIs, their storage and use for the purposes of the project. This does not however imply that all the partners of the BIGPICTURE consortium must assume such a role. Certain partners may not make any decisions regarding WSIs nor process such data and thus would not have a role defined under the GDPR.

Conclusion: It is crucial for BIGPICTURE to map the responsibilities of all involved parties and allocate controller, joint controller and processor roles based on those responsibilities.

³⁶ Guidelines 07/2020, pg. 3.

³⁷ Article 26 GDPR.

³⁸ Guidelines 07/2020, pg. 24.

³⁹ Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz Schleswig-Holstein v Wirtschaftsakademie, (C- 210/16), Tietosuojavaltuutettu v Jehovan todistajat — uskonnollinen yhdyskunta (C-25/17), Fashion ID GmbH & Co. KG v Verbraucherzentrale NRW eV (C-40/17).

Once this is determined, the policy framework and data sharing agreements should follow to ensure clear allocation of the obligations and rights with respect to the collection, storage and sharing of WSIs.

1.2.8.3. DPIA requirements

Article 35 GDPR requires a prior assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data, particularly when using new technologies and when the processing – taking into account its nature, scope, context and purposes – is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. The data protection officer may be requested advice.

According to the GDPR, a data protection impact assessment (“**DPIA**”) is required when the processing concerns an automated processing providing systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person; when processing on a large scale special categories of data; or when systematically monitoring a publicly accessible area on a large scale. A public list of these operations is maintained by the supervisory authority.

A DPIA must contain:

- a systematic description of the envisaged processing operations and the purposes of the processing;
- an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes;
- an assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects; and
- the measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance, taking into account the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and other persons concerned.

A DPIA is not required if the processing is prescribed by law and if a general impact assessment was already conducted in adopting that legal basis.

If the processing can result in a high risk, the controller should contact the supervisory authority. If the authority finds that the processing would infringe upon the GDPR, or that the risks are insufficiently mitigated, it may provide a negative advice to the processing. Member States may allow authorities to require controllers to obtain prior authorization.

In the context of BIGPICTURE, the project combines health data from many sources and thus processing on a large scale special categories of data is likely to take place. Moreover several country experts have underlined the importance of conducting a DPIA. In particular in **Finland** “*If the data are considered personal data, then under the Data Protection Act (DPA), if GDPR’s data subject rights (Art 15, 16, 18 or 21) are deviated from, a GDPR data protection impact assessment (DPIA) must be performed by the data controller of the research data and provided to data protection authorities in advance or relevant GDPR-approved code of conduct followed (see also answer 5 below). In addition, in the general BigPicture context, biobanks who are expected to provide the WSI should have performed DPIAs for their operations, but if they would start using BigPicture entities as processors to hold data for onwards disclosures they should perform a specific DPIA regarding this process (in accordance with the EDPB guidance and the conditions of Art. 35 GDPR)*” (response to Q3).

Also in **Italy**, conducting and making a DPIA publicly available is one of the conditions for taking advantage of an exception from seeking the consent of the data subject for processing of health data for scientific research purposes (see response to Q3). In **Belgium**, if the DPIA was appropriate and “*the controller processes sensitive data, within the meaning of article 9.1 of the Regulation, for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes*”, this assessment should be added to the record of processing activities as one of the general safeguards (response to Q6).

BIGPICTURE will be conducting several (4) iterations of a Data Privacy Impact Assessment (D5.13-16).

Conclusion: BIGPICTURE should conduct a DPIA exercise to evaluate all relevant aspects of sharing of WSIs within the project, in line with the GDPR requirements. This DPIA should become a reference source that will feed into and contribute to own assessments conducted by the Data Submitters (acting as controllers).

1.3. Specific categories of health data

The legal experts have been asked to provide specific comments regarding the following specific types of WSIs:

- Containing genetics data
- Relating to rare diseases and Covid19
- WSI which were obtained in the context of clinical trials.

The responses which were obtained can be summarized as follows:

1.3.1. Data containing genetics data

Most of the experts did not indicate any particular restrictions relating to genetics data i.e. indicated that processing of genetic data in the same way as other health data. This is the case in **Belgium, Finland** (where however Genome Act is under preparation), **the Netherlands** (although unsolicited findings resulting from genetics research would need to be addressed under the planned Medical Tissue Act, WzI).

In **Germany**, the specific law *Gendiagnostikgesetz* includes several restrictions, *“but it explicitly states that these restrictions are not applicable to research use of genetic data. If this use is included in the informed consent, there are no restrictions for research use. If there is no informed consent, it is expected that genetic information, in particular germline information, will be restricted by the ethical committee”* (response to Q11).

Moreover, in **Italy**, there are specific rules which regarding processing and *“custody and safety”* of genetic data and biological samples. Special laws or provisions on genetic data also apply in **Sweden** and the **UK** (Human Tissue Act).

1.3.2. Data relating to rare diseases and COVID-19

Most of the experts (**Belgium, Finland, Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden, UK**) did not indicate any particular legal restrictions. However, it was emphasized that rare diseases data can be more identifiable despite protections (making it difficult or impossible to de-identify the WSIs) and this may affect decisions to grant access to them. For **Italy**, the expert identified certain guidelines regarding use of data on COVID-19, which should be consulted.

1.3.3. Data which were obtained in the context of clinical trials

For clinical trials, the response which was most common (e.g., **Finland, the Netherlands, UK**), was that participating in a clinical trial requires a study-specific informed consent. Thus, it would need to be checked whether the original consent encompasses use of data for other research studies, such as BIGPICTURE.

Moreover, for **Belgium**, it was noted that *“if the human body material is used for purposes other than those described in the clinical trial dossier, then the material must be transferred to a biobank”*, where it falls within the scope of the Human Material Body Law (response Q15).

Some countries (e.g., **Italy**) did not indicate any additional considerations.

1.3.4. Data categories under special considerations

In the **UK** there are specific data categories which may need to be excluded from the Data. This is

likely to apply in very narrow circumstances, given the objectives of the project. In particular: “*Data about abortions, certain sexual health conditions (including but not limited to HIV and Female Genital Mutilation) are held separately from the record by statute and would require special review from RECs and approvals from specialist centres (specialist treatment centres for conditions like HIV or interventions relating to FGM) to be shared*” (response to Q25).

Moreover, in the **Netherlands** “*usage of the national social security number (BSN) is strictly regulated. Health providers are required by law to use it in clinical care records, while its usage in health research is strictly forbidden*” (response to Q22).

Conclusion: BIGPICTURE should carefully consider whether to mandate the Data Submitters to provide WSIs with accompanying Metadata on specific categories of health data (genetic data, rare diseases, COVID-19). Provision of this Metadata should be marked as optional, which may be provided that the Data Submitter may share this information in line with the national law. WSIs containing such data in their Metadata may need an additional layer of ethical approval or special consideration. For WSIs derived from clinical trials, the Data Submitters must assure that the submission of the WSI is in line with any consent obtained from the individual and/or information provided to them during clinical trial.

Conclusion (2): Data Submitters should confirm that the Data that they make available to BIGPICTURE do not contravene any of their national laws restricting the disclosure of specific types of personal or health information, such as national ID number or information about certain diseases.

2. Non-clinical WSIs

The inquiry sent out to the legal experts included questions regarding rules which regulate use of WSI of animal samples (non-clinical WSI). In their responses, most of the experts indicated legislation on the use of laboratory animals and ethical requirements for animal testing/experiments. However, **no specific rules** were identified that regulate the creation of digital representations of animal Slides and use of WSIs of animal samples in such context as BIGPICTURE. For the **UK** the respondent advised that “*Should be checked with the specific site. There may be restrictions based on use of specified purpose, including standard research ethics guidelines*” (response to Q10).

3. Ethical requirements

The rules regarding ethical approvals vary greatly between the Data Submitters’ jurisdictions. In many countries those rules are not codified but rather depend on local practice and the type of Data Submitter. For instance, for the **UK**: “*There is divergence in the rules for obtaining the approval depending on the authority. There are more than 80 different RECs, which vary in their expertise*” (response to Q2). Also in the **Netherlands**, “*As for WSIs, there is not a specific regime. In practice, biobanks and cohorts typically need to seek approval from an ethical board before initiating such a collection to meet the requirements in the Medical Treatment Contact Act (WGBO). For other data collections several institutions have so-called Institutional Review Boards (IRB), which is not a legal obligation but an institutional safeguard that all procedures are followed. There is clearly a lack of consensus in this area*” (response to Q9).

If applicable, typically ethical requirements entail a specific regime of obtaining an authorization from the ethics committees to access health data and use it for research purposes.

It is important to note that **all of the countries in question** indicated that the Data Submitter would be required to obtain an ethical approval to contribute Data to the project. In particular, in **Germany** “*For BIGPICTURE, these existing approvals would need an amendment to include WSIs as well as transfer to the repository. For retrospective projects of one single department and use of already existing data (including slides and WSIs) with anonymisation, a simplified ethical board approval is required*” (response to Q9). Similarly, this is the case in **Finland** “*For access to biobank collections, an ethical review is also required, but this is sometimes performed by the biobanks’ own scientific*

boards as part of processing the access application. However, in practice in many (if not most) cases a statement from a statutory committee established in accordance with the Medical Research Act is required (requires a separate prior application)” (response to Q9).

Furthermore, in the context of BIGPICTURE, while the organization of the honest broker mechanism is still being discussed in the framework of WP3, the ethical requirements for obtaining the ethical approval should be further investigated and aligned with the planned establishment of data access committees (“**DAC**”). In particular, it must be discussed with the participating Data Submitters if under their authorizations they could agree to delegate to outside DACs the right to make decision on accessibility of contributed WSIs to other researchers. As the **Finnish** respondent noted *“Access to samples and data in the discussed context is legally controlled and permissions are needed. Providing these permissions cannot be freely delegated, so only the entities (biobanks and Findata) recognised in the law can grant access. BIGPICTURE partners or a legal vehicle created by the project would not be such an entity, unless it establishes itself as a biobank registered in Finland. This would most likely be possible, but there are uncertainties related to the pending changes and the new biobank act may affect the feasibility of this option” (response to Q21).*

Based on the received country responses it is apparent that there is no unified framework within the Data Submitters jurisdictions on contributing data to research repositories and also the rules of ethics; approval conditions are often vague. This is to be further discussed together with the actual initial Data Submitters organizations and the conditions upon they receive their ethical approvals for the participation in the project. From a high-level perspective, given the findings of the expert reports, the following scenarios should be further examined:

- a) Data Submitter’s ethical approval encompasses transfer of data to the repository and making the data further available to other researchers upon fulfilment of certain criteria (presumably to be examined by DAC) would not require a new ethics approval.

For example, as noted by report for the **Netherlands** *“In the context of BigPicture, since the project does not involve new research on human subjects, the external partners applying to the biobanks to access their submitted WSIs via the BigPicture infrastructure would not have to obtain an ethics approval” (response to Q17).*

- b) Separate approval from the Data Submitter’s ethical committee must be obtained by the researcher seeking the access to WSIs, before the access is granted.

This is illustrated by the following comment from the **Finland** expert *“BIGPICTURE doesn’t seem like a medical research project as such, but rather an infrastructure to support many future activities, it doesn’t seem possible to provide independent control to BIGPICTURE, but biobanks will make a decision on this if an application is made and a research plan presented (requires also an ethical review). In such case, generally the researcher’s application made through this infrastructure to a contributing biobank should be treated as any other application to the biobank, so the researcher would need to fulfil the conditions for access to data. There could be however some room for discretion for the biobank for setting up “fast track” for such applications if they for example were able to be standardised to warrant expedited processing. Moreover, processing could be subcontracted to BIGPICTURE partners as long as the biobank controls access. This is under the assumption that data provider retains control over access to the WSI it contributes” (response to Q32).*

In **Belgium** the legal situation depends on various factors, including which law would apply for the researcher which seeks to obtain the WSI. Moreover, there is uncertainty on how the ethics committees would approach possible delegation of competence to allow access to WSIs to DACs. As noted by the expert team: *“The specific legal provisions applicable to the further use of the WSI slides, once made accessible via the BigPicture repository, will depend on 1) the data protection law applicable to the research project for which these slides will be used, and 2) if Belgian data protection law is applicable to this research project, the requirements of this particular research project with regard to the necessity to benefit from the research exemptions mentioned in Art. 89(2) of the GDPR (see the 4 possible scenarios in the answer to Q3). It is not excluded that ethical committees in Belgian academic hospitals will be reluctant to approve “blank” access to their WSI slide collections and to delegate their competence to an entity belonging to a common repository. It is also not excluded that*

ethical committees of academic hospitals in Belgium will be reluctant to approve the use of WSI slides in research projects regulated by data protection laws of other Member States.” (response to Q32).

Conclusion: Each Data Submitter must confirm that they comply with the rules applicable to seeking and adhering to ethical approval in their jurisdiction.

Conclusion (2): BIGPICTURE must engage in discussions with concrete Data Submitters on the approach of their ethical committees to delegating authorization of access to WSIs to a DAC (if appointed outside of their organization).

4. Specific regulations regarding biobanks

As demonstrated by the expert responses, biobank law is not harmonized between the jurisdictions of the Data Submitters, located in the European Union and the UK. Furthermore, not all countries in scope have specific rules relating to biobanks.

In particular, specific biobank law is implemented in **Finland, Belgium and Sweden.**

No such law was identified in the **Netherlands, Germany, Italy** and the **UK**. However, there exist certain national rules on the use of human materials (tissues and blood). For example, in the **Netherlands** rules on use of human material are provided in the Medical Treatment Contract Act (WGBO) and Dutch Code for proper secondary use of human tissue. They contain “*concrete standards for Dutch health research that are accessible to researchers*” (response to Q16). In the **UK**, there is fragmented patchwork of laws that applies to medical research on humans, providing for a distinction between human material (samples) and data. UK’s Human Tissue Act would not apply to WSIs, though (response to Q17).

The further conclusion which can be drawn from the received input is that for most of the jurisdictions, it is questionable whether the WSIs will be under the scope of biobank law. In particular, in **Belgium** “*Images of human body samples are “data” (“personal data” if the person concerned is identifiable). A collection of such images is not a biobank, according to the Q & A in the Compendium*” (response to Q3). Also in **Sweden** it is “*the common interpretation of the Biobank Act has been that storing tissue samples in biobanks does not amount to processing of personal data as such*” (response to Q16). Thus, **Swedish** Biobank Act would not be directly applicable to sharing the digital images of those samples (WSI). This is also the case in the **UK**, in the sense that distinction is made between samples and data.

The situation is different in **Finland**. Here, there is a different regime for accessing data under Secondary Use Act and rules which apply to biobanks, as they are regulated under the Biobank Act (response to Q6). However, in principle, the WSI would be considered as falling under the scope of Biobank Act if obtained from the biobank: “*Biobanks maintain collections of samples and related data (metadata, clinical data etc. linked to the samples) for future research purposes. WSI produced by the biobank would be considered a technical record of the sample*”(response to Q16). Consequence of this is a requirement for the material/data transfer agreement (M/DTA) to be concluded to access a WSI from a biobank in Finland.

The biobank acts can have further consideration on the set up of the roles and responsibilities of BIGPICTURE partners. As noted by **Finnish** expert: “*It would seem that the only way Finnish data can be in BIGPICTURE is under a subcontract for processing, with no independent decision making over disclosures or transfer. Another option could be registering as a biobank in Finland.*” Furthermore: “*If BIGPICTURE however wanted to have independent control of the Finnish WSIs (e.g., by granting access requests to the researchers), this would seem possible only if the controlling entity/entities registers a biobank in accordance with the Finnish Biobank Act and concludes agreements with the original provider biobanks. This should be further considered by the project partners*” (response to Q22).

Moreover, the biobank laws would apply to the transferring of the glass Slides as such. While this issue was outside of the scope of the assessment, nevertheless some reports contain additional information about transferring the original Slides (e.g., **Sweden, UK**) or more detailed analysis of

biobank law was provided (**Belgium**).

Conclusion: Each Data Submitter must indicate which special rules apply to the submitted Data under biobank laws. In particular if there is a requirement for concluding a material transfer agreement (MTA).

5. Intellectual Property (IP) rights to the Data

The possible IP rights to the WSI and accompanying Metadata include:

- database rights
- copyright and photograph protection,
- protection of trade secrets.

Below, we summarize the essence of each type of right and provide a summary of the findings from relevant jurisdictions.

5.1. Database rights

Databases are protected under EU Law. The Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases (“**Database Directive**”) was adopted in 1996 and provides for uniform legal protection regime in the EU.

The Database Directive protects collections, sometimes called 'compilations', of works, data or other materials which are arranged, stored and accessed by means which include electronic, electromagnetic or electro-optical processes or analogous processes.⁴⁰ Protection extends to collections of independent works, data or other materials which are systematically or methodically arranged and can be individually accessed.⁴¹

In accordance with the Database Directive, the Member States were obligated to provide for a right for the maker of a database which made investments in creation of the database. The objective of this *sui generis* right (specific property right for databases) is to ensure protection of any investment in obtaining, verifying or presenting the contents of a database for the limited duration of the right.⁴² This right encompasses the right to prohibit extraction and re-utilization of the database or its substantial part.⁴³ This right may be transferred or licensed and applies irrespective of the eligibility of that database for protection by copyright or by other rights and irrespective of eligibility of the contents of that database for protection by copyright or by other rights. The right of protection of databases is without prejudice to rights existing in respect of their contents. It runs for 15 years from the first of January of the year following the date of completion of the database. Moreover, the Database Directive protects databases by copyright if they are original by reason of the selection or arrangement of their content.

The rules of the Database Directive were transposed by the responding jurisdictions and may apply to the collection of the WSIs provided by the Data Submitters. For instance, in **Belgium** exists a separate regime for database rights in the Belgian Act on Economic Law. In **Germany**, such protection is provided in the *Urheberrechtsgesetz*. Also in **Italy**, the collection of WSI may be a database protected under one of the bases mentioned in the Italian Copyright Law. Detailed responses on the rules are provided in Q24 of the country reports.

However, as pointed out by some of the respondents, the consequences to collection of WSI in the context of BIGPICTURE would be rather limited, assuming that the Data Submitter was the holder of the database rights (e.g., maker of the database). For **Finland** it was noted that “*There are specific legal rules addressing how patient and biobank data can be and, in some cases, must be shared, so*

⁴⁰ Recital 13 Database Directive. Article 1.2 e provides that “database” shall mean a collection of independent works, data or other materials arranged in a systematic or methodical way and individually accessible by electronic or other means.

⁴¹ Recital 17 Database Directive.

⁴² Recital 40 Database Directive.

⁴³ Article 7(1) Database Directive.

the IPR doesn't seem particularly consequential to BIGPICTURE" (response to Q24). Also in **Italy**, "If the hospital was the "maker" of the WSI database, it would be entitled to the "sui generis right" to this database and would be able to grant licenses to use these WSI in the research projects" (response to Q24).

In the **Netherlands** it may be even doubtful if the rights to the database would arise "Database rights could apply to an organized collection of slides, but technically, such database rights would apply to the infrastructure and the entirety of the database, not individual sides or individual contributions from the data providers" (response to Q24).

5.2. Copyright protection and photograph rights

Copyright protection is only partially harmonized within the EU, with the regulatory framework for copyright and neighbouring rights (acquis) consisting of 11 directives and 2 regulations. There is however no universally recognized definition of copyrighted works.⁴⁴ It is generally accepted that it includes every original work of authorship, irrespective of its literary or artistic merit. The ideas in the work do not need to be original, but the form of expression must be an original creation by the author.⁴⁵

In the context of BIGPICTURE, as indicated by some of the country respondents, a collection of WSIs may potentially be recognized as copyrightable work (**Italy**). Moreover, some of the jurisdictions (**Finland, Sweden, Belgium**) recognize *sui generis* right to photographs, even if the threshold of artistic work is not met. However, the latter right may be subject to additional conditions. For instance, in **Belgium** the right to photograph is included in Article XI.174 of the Belgian Act of Economic Law. However, "the legal doctrine and jurisprudence unanimously declare that the person depicted must be recognisable. If the person depicted is not recognisable, this right to photograph is not applicable and the consent of the depicted person is no longer necessary" (response to Q24). For this reason, the **Belgian** right to photograph would not be applicable for WSI, as the person will not be recognisable from the image.

In addition, should the IP rights to WSI and Metadata arise, they would most likely be vested in the Data Submitter (**Finland**), either by law or by employee contracts. For example in **Sweden**: "The neighbouring rights to the photographs would typically be vested in the institution (employer) rather than individual employees, by way of employment contract" (response to Q24).

Both the copyrights and database rights may be transferred or licensed to the project and the user. For the **UK** the respondent noted that "Existing IP (specifically the IP relating to records) remains with the Health Care Trust / Health Board that are the Data Controllers of the Records. Arising IP is negotiated in a per case basis" (response to Q23).

Other than this reservation, no further particular limitations in this respect were observed by the respondents. In particular for **Germany** "The pathologist / hospital can provide the rights to use this image to the BIGPICTURE repository" (response to Q24).

5.3. Protection of trade secrets

In the EU, following the Trade Secrets Directive⁴⁶ a trade secret means information which meets all of the following requirements:

- it is secret in the sense that it is not, as a body or in the precise configuration and assembly of its components, generally known among or readily accessible to persons within the circles that normally deal with the kind of information in question;
- it has commercial value because it is secret;

⁴⁴ Article 2 of Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (1886) states that: "The expression 'literary and artistic works' shall include every production in the literary, scientific and artistic domain, whatever may be the mode or form of its expression." The Convention lists examples of such works.

⁴⁵ WIPO Understanding Copyright and Related Rights (https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_909_2016.pdf)

⁴⁶ Directive (EU) 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure (further as "Trade Secrets Directive").

- it has been subject to reasonable steps under the circumstances, by the person lawfully in control of the information, to keep it secret.⁴⁷

The Trade Secrets Directive was transposed into laws of Member States and similar conditions have been provided for in those laws. The Trade Secrets Directive provides harmonization of the rules of civil law through which victims of trade secret misappropriation can seek protection. Trade secrets however are not intellectual property rights thus the holder of the trade secret does not enjoy an exclusive right. The Trade Secrets Directive does not alter the legal obligations requiring to divulge information for such public policy objectives nor regarding open access rights. Importantly, it does not provide any mandatory rules on what information cannot be disclosed by the rightful owner of such information.

As the scope of Trade Secrets Directive is quite broad, trade secrets protection may apply to WSI and Metadata. As the **Belgian** report states “*it can be concluded that the WSI (and the metadata connected to it) can be considered a trade secret. The Data Submitter could therefore decide to keep certain information secret and remove it from the WSI under trade secret protection*” (response to Q26). Also in **Finland** “*collections/compilations of WSI and related data could clearly be subject to database or catalogue protections, like any data/information, also personal*” (response to Q26).

Nonetheless, as noted by some respondents, the important condition of the trade secrets protection to apply is that the holder of the information must take reasonable measures to keep it secret. For instance, in **Belgium** the following measures may be considered “*surveillance in a vault, a password, encryption, etc.*” (response to Q26).

On the reverse side, this does not mean that the Data Submitter *must* keep any of its business information in confidence and thus must remove any of its commercially valuable information from the WSI or its Metadata. However, if this information is no longer kept secret then it would lose its protection. As put by the **Netherlands** expert “*There is no requirement to remove trade secrets in the Wbb [Dutch Trade secret act], this depends on the decision of the holder of the trade secret if they want to make it public*” (response to Q26).

Conclusion: The Data Submitters must check if IP rights to Data arise in their jurisdiction. If this is the case, Data Submitter must confirm that he obtained such rights, either by virtue of law or by contract (e.g., by an agreement with the researcher), and can submit Data in the scope required to participate in BIGPICTURE.

Conclusion (2): BIGPICTURE license/licenses should be drafted to contain license (or transfer of rights) for the use of the submitted Data for the purpose of the BIGPICTURE project. License requirements should also be included in the contract (or terms and conditions) of the use of Data by researchers accessing the repository.

6. Contractual limitations and open data (public data) restrictions

6.1. Contractual limitations

The majority of the respondents did not indicate any contractual limitations (other than requirements of the personal data protection, which were discussed above). For instance, the **Belgium** report states that there is no specific law in **Belgium** that regulates the use of WSI. However, the rules of use of health data, including requirement for pseudonymisation or anonymisation, apply (response to Q23).

Certain provisions however exist in **Finland**. In particular “*research results must be made public.*” This is in addition to other requirements described in other parts of this report, such as keeping the data confidential and used only as necessary under the approved research plan (response to Q23).

In **Netherlands** the laws provide for narrower legal basis for use of data if it is used for research for commercial purposes. Namely “*Dutch implementing legislation for GDPR allows exceptions to research use without consent only for research performed in the public interest (art 24 and 28 UAVG).*”

⁴⁷ Article 2(1) Trade Secrets Directive.

Consequently, research use for commercial purposes is only allowed based on consent” (response to Q23).

6.2. Open data rules

All of the questioned countries have identified rules on access to public sector information. For EU Member States they have been implemented by requirements of the directives on open data and the re-use of public sector information.⁴⁸

None of the respondents have however indicated that those laws would limit the use of WSI in the context of BIGPICTURE. On the contrary, it was noted that the open data laws would not apply to WSIs. For example, based on responses to Q29-30 to the questionnaires:

- **Finland:** “The *lex generalis* Act on the Openness of Government Activities applies to public sector operators including the biobank operators contemplated in BIGPICTURE, and to some extent also private biobanks. I do not foresee any relevant impact as access to the relevant data is specifically stipulated.”
- **Germany:** “The rules of Access to Information (HDSIG) apply to universities and university hospitals insofar as they do not operate in the field of research and teaching.”
- **Italy:** “The access to public information is regulated by the D.Lgs. n. 33, 14 March 2013, as modified by the D.Lgs. n. 97, 25 May 2016, (which implemented the Freedom of Information Act – FOIA -). However, this legislation does not add any restrictions or conditions apply to making the WSI available to the BigPicture.”
- **Netherlands:** “As mentioned above, WOB rules are not applicable to BigPicture partners or slide contributors, as only public bodies are subject to them.”
- **Sweden:** “The provisions on public access to information would however not apply to data submitter’s own participation in a research project and its submission of data to such project. They would only be applicable if a third party researcher requested data from an institution, which was subject to public access of information laws.”

Conclusion: Based on the responses from the country experts, the existing public data laws should not be an obstacle in providing the Data to the project nor imposing conditions for their use in the context of BIGPICTURE. However, given the different types of Data Submitters which may enrol in the project, this should also be verified by the Data Submitter prior to WSI submission.

7. Other issues

Below we shortly summarize responses to remaining questions from the legal assessment questionnaire.

7.1. Digitalization of WSI

No specific rules regarding digitalization (beyond data protection laws) were identified and described. For instance in **Belgium** there is “no specific law or specific provisions in the law of 19 December 2008 regarding digitalization of images of human tissue and samples in Belgium. Generating images from human tissue and digitalization of those images will be qualified as a processing of personal data if the patient is identifiable from whom the tissue or samples have been collected. Digital pathology slides will be considered as <<representations>> of HBM and, therefore, as <<data>> (<<personal data>> if the patient is identifiable)” (response to Q8).

Some respondents also pointed to general rules on handling of human biological material (**Finland**). Those rules are for example in **Sweden** (response to Q8). In the **UK** rules of Human Tissue Act and

⁴⁸ The most recent Open Data Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information), entered into force on 16 July 2019, replacing the Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive.

UK GDPR provisions around Genetic Data must be followed.

7.2. Requirements for development of AI/ML

No requirements relating to artificial intelligence/machine learning in the context of WSIs were identified by the country respondents. Some respondents (for e.g., **Finland**) noted that EU's artificial intelligence regulation might be enacted in time to affect BIGPICTURE.

7.3. Honest broker mechanism

In some jurisdictions honest brokers services exist either provided for by the law, or in practice. In **Belgium** it is a legal requirement to use honest broker services in certain situations i.e. *“pseudonymisation by a trusted third party or by one of the data providers is mandatory before transmitting health data to researchers who wish to benefit from one or more of the exemptions mentioned in Art. 89(2) GDPR, if they collect health data from multiple sources”* (response to Q21).

In the **Netherlands** while there is no “official” honest broker service, *“there is a fairly commonly used commercial service for secure data linkage which has some features of an honest broker. This service is called ZorgTTP”* (response to Q21).

Moreover, in **Finnish** permissions authority under the Secondary Use Act, *Findata*, can be seen as type of honest broker, as it provides permissions and access to health and social care data from many data controllers and may “pre-process” data for the researcher, for example pseudonymize or anonymize it (response to Q21).

None of the other respondents identified any requirements of the honest broker mechanism that would impact the BIGPICTURE project.

7.4. General information about databases and registers containing patient’s health data and biological samples

Each of the country experts provided overview of the registers which may contain data relevant for the project (responses to Q1). This information may be further analysed to obtain additional Data Submitters at later stages of the project.

7.5. Potential consequences of non-compliance

BIGPICTURE as a whole is not a legal entity, thus responsibility for any non-compliance with the above mentioned rules (e.g., infringement of the GDPR rules) would need to be evaluated towards particular partners or even - in some cases - to individuals within those organization (e.g., for criminal liability). The types of the potential sanctions vary between the involved countries (responses to Q7 to the questionnaires). Moreover, the GDPR contains very complex rules regarding the authority which could be authorized to investigate a privacy infringement. In practice, given different scenarios which may occur and also the transnational character of the consortium, the responsibility of BIGPICTURE members in case of any breach of the above mentioned rules would need to be ascertained on a case by case basis. It is not possible to draw an overarching principle at this stage, especially given that the roles of the partners are not defined. In particular, for data protection infringements, the scope of responsibility of each entity is related to the position it has regarding the data (controller, processor, joint controller). This is explained above in section 1.2.8.2.

Appendix 2 - Belgium Country Report

Responses for Belgium

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Topic	Questions
National provisions on personal data processing in the context of scientific research	<p>1. Which national laws regulate use and sharing of health (“health data”), including WSIs, for research purposes? Please provide the name of the law, online reference, and relevance for the BigPicture (if not explained in other sections below)</p> <p>Response: List below provides an overview of the main national laws which are relevant for the BigPicture, including the name of the national law or soft law, link (in French) and comments.</p> <p>a. 7 MAI 2004. - <i>Loi relative aux expérimentations sur la personne humaine</i> (Law of 7 May 2004 on experiments on the human person)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&cn=2004050732&table_name=loi • A full list of the laws, royal decrees and circulars that modify or complement the law is available here: https://www.famhp.be/en/human_use/medicines/medicines/research_development/ethic_committee • The law implements European Directive 2001/20 (the Clinical Trials Directive, CTD). However, the Belgian Law of 7 May 2004 has a broader scope than the CTD. An experiment is defined as: “<i>Expérimentation : essai, étude ou investigation menée sur la personne humaine qui a pour objectif le développement des connaissances propres à l'exercice des professions de soins de santé tel que visé à l'arrêté royal n° 78 du 10 novembre 1967 relatif à l'exercice des professions de soins de santé</i>” <p>b. 7 MAI 2017. - <i>Loi relative aux essais cliniques de médicaments à usage humain</i> (Law of 7 May 2017 on clinical trials involving medicinal products for human use)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/eli/loi/2017/05/07/2017012146/justel • The law will enter into force on the same date as the entry into force of the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR), set for January 1, 2022. It only addresses matters that the Regulation has left up to the national governments to legislate. <p>c. 30 JUILLET 2018. - <i>Loi relative à la protection des personnes physiques à l'égard des traitements de données à caractère personnel</i> (Law of 30 July 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&cn=2018073046&table_name=loi • An unofficial translation into English is available here: https://www.dataprotectionauthority.be/publications/act-of-30-july-2018.pdf • The law implements the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). <p>d. 19 DECEMBRE 2008. - <i>Loi relative à l'obtention et à l'utilisation de matériel corporel humain destiné à des applications médicales humaines ou à des fins de recherche scientifique</i> (Law of 19 December 2008 on obtaining and using human body material (HBM) for human medical applications or scientific research purposes)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&cn=2008121944&table_name=loi • The initial text of the Law contained legal rules on the procurement and use of HBM by biobanks for research purposes that did not enter into force for 10 years, and in the meantime were amended several times. Changes were introduced, first, by the Law of 19 March 2013 containing diverse provisions concerning health. Second, the Law of 10 April 2014 containing diverse provisions concerning health established specific rules for biobanks created in the framework of a clinical trial. Finally, the law of 22 June 2016

introduced further modifications to the legal framework. All three laws were scheduled to enter into force only after the publication of one or more executive Royal Decrees. With the adoption of the Royal Decree of 9 January 2018, the legal framework described above finally entered into force¹.

- e. 9 JANVIER 2018. - *Arrêté royal relatif aux biobanques* (Royal Decree on biobanks of 9 January 2018)
 - http://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&table_name=loi&cn=2018010914
 - See above for the importance of the Royal Decree. In addition, specific custodian responsibilities are further elaborated in the decree.
 - f. 30 OCTOBRE 2018. - *Loi modifiant la loi du 19 décembre 2008 relative à l'obtention et à l'utilisation de matériel corporel humain destiné à des applications médicales humaines ou à des fins de recherche scientifique* (Law of 30 October 2018 modifying the Law of 19 December 2008 on obtaining and using human body material (HBM) for human medical applications or scientific research purposes)
 - http://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&table_name=loi&cn=2018103013
 - With this law, the scope of Belgian biobank rules was extended to the donation, procurement, control and import of HBM intended for use exclusively in manufactured products, in particular medicinal products, advanced therapy medicinal products (ATMPs) or medical devices.
 - g. *Compendium biobanques* (20.07.2018), published by the Federal Agency for Medicines and Health Products (FAMHP)
 - Available in French, Dutch and English here: https://www.fagg-fmmps.be/sites/default/files/content/compendium_20072018.pdf
 - The Compendium is an unofficial commentary drafted by the Federal Agency and strives to shed clarity as to how to interpret and implement the biobank legislation. During the preparation of the Compendium, the input of relevant stakeholders was sought, namely representatives of academic and industrial biobanks, ethical committees and juridical experts. The document covers a broad range of topics such as, inter alia, the scope of the biobank legislation, consent, notification procedure, transformation of HBM, traceability and anonymization, ethics committees.
 - h. 22 AVRIL 2019. - *Loi relative à la qualité de la pratique des soins de santé* (Law of 21 April 2019 on the Quality of Health Care Practice)
 - https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&cn=2019042220&table_name=loi
 - This law entered into force very recently (01.07.2021). It foresees a general obligation for healthcare practitioners to share patient data with other healthcare practitioners only if the patients have given their previous consent (Article 36). In Belgium, patients can give their informed consent on the “eSanté portal” <https://ehealth.fgov.be/fr/esante/professionnels-de-la-sante/ehealthconsent/presentation-generale> (physicians are stimulated to assist patients to collect this informed consent)
2. Please describe how the databases and registers containing patient’s health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are organized in your jurisdiction and which type of data they contain. If possible, please indicate which databases or registers may be relevant for BigPicture.

¹ For more information, see Lalova T. et al. (2021) An Overview of Belgian Legislation Applicable to Biobank Research and Its Interplay with Data Protection Rules. In: Slokenberga S., Tzortzatou O., Reichel J. (eds) GDPR and Biobanking. Law, Governance and Technology Series, vol 43. Springer, Cham. Link: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49388-2_10, available here: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-49388-2_10#Fn58_source

Response: Databases and registers containing patients' health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes in Belgium are held by individual – mostly academic – hospitals. Biobanks (collections of human body material for research purposes) exist, for example, at the [University Hospital in Leuven](#), the [University Hospital in Ghent](#), the [University Hospital in Antwerp](#), the [Bordet Institute in Brussels](#) ("the Tumour Bank"), etc. The [Belgian BBMRI network](#) connects 17 biobanks that are linked to public institutions such as hospitals, universities and research centers. All these biobanks and networks are also included in the [Directory of BBMRI-ERIC](#).

In Belgium the human body material (further referenced as HBM) banks must have obtained a recognition from the [Federal Agency for Medicines and Health Products \(FAMHP\)](#). The recognition is granted under the Law of 19 December 2008 on the acquisition and use of human body material for the purpose of medical application to humans or scientific research. The accredited institutions can be found in the EU directory of Tissue institutions (see the following link: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/eucoding/reports/te/index.xhtml>). Also important in this regard is the Royal Decree on Biobanks² which lays down the procedure on how a biobank must register with the Belgian Federal Agency for Medicines and Health Products (FAMHP). The Royal Decree determines the requirements for the extraction of HBM intended for the biobank, the modification and discontinuation of the biobank's operations, the rules on reporting to the ethics committee, the data that the register to be maintained by the biobank should contain, the rules on coding, tracing and identification of the donor, etc.

In 2015 a pilot project has been set up in Brussels to create a "Digital Pathology Platform". This platform, called SecundOS (Second Opinion Simplified) is operational since 2018.³ In the Walloon Region, a "[Center for Microscopy and Molecular Imaging](#)" (CMMI) has been set up by Belgian French-speaking universities and industrial partners with EU funding. This institute manages the [DIAPath platform](#). The DIAPath (Digital Image Analysis in Pathology) is a platform oriented towards the validation of tissue-based biomarkers using standardized immunohistochemistry (IHC) and slide digitalization processes. It proposes services that range from sample preparation to image and data analysis. The largest Belgian university hospitals, for example the university hospital in Leuven have integrated digital pathology in the healthcare processes, making use of industrial solutions such as the [Philips IntelliSite Pathology Solution](#).

Belgium does not yet have a coordinated index or some other form of overview of health data (such as digital pathology slides) available for secondary use (e.g. scientific research). Attempts have been undertaken to publish (incomplete) lists of health data bases since 2005. A list of about 50 of such databases has been published by the [Belgian Health Care Knowledge Centre \(KCE\)](#). Today a list of 150 health databases is available on the [Healthstat.be website](#) of Healthdata.be (accessible only with the Belgian eID).

[Healthdata.be](#) is a platform which is an initiative by [Sciensano](#) (the Belgian Scientific Institute of Public Health). One the other initiatives, the healthdata.be [FAIR platform](#), was launched in 2017. The first release (0.1) contained 27,241 records from 2 catalogs: the inventory "AP18" of the Action Plan eHealth 2013-2018 (252 records), and an extract of the [European Union Clinical Trials Register](#) (26989 records). It is the ambition to continuously add catalogs, projects and resources, related to Belgian health and health care, to this platform, and to develop taxonomies connecting all these projects and resources.

3. Please describe general conditions on using patient's health data and WSIs of human biological samples for scientific research purposes.

² Royal Decree of 9 January 2016 on biobanks

(https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=nl&la=N&cn=2018010914&table_name=wet)

³ See e.g. <https://healthcare-in-europe.com/en/news/belgium-sets-up-a-dx-pathology-platform.html>; for more details: http://www.fondsyvonneboel.be/uploads/2/2/2/0/22206040/bilan_scientifique.pdf

Response: Associated data, more specifically personal data related to health, are collected alongside samples, hence, in the context of HBM procurement, the data protection rules apply too. Images of human body samples are “data” (“personal data” if the person concerned is identifiable). A collection of such images is not a biobank, according to the Q & A in the Compendium.

The relevant rules according the Belgian Data Protection Law are to be found in Title 4, and are copied below.

It is important to emphasize that, according to Art. 186, these rules have to be interpreted as conditions to benefit from the research exemptions applicable in Belgium pursuant to Art. 89(2) of the GDPR. Consequently, a controller for scientific or historical research or for statistical purposes may consider that he can comply with all the provisions of the GDPR and therefore not rely, or only partly rely, on the derogations provided for according to Art. 89(2) of the GDPR.

Four scenarios are possible:

(1) Either a controller can achieve its purposes by complying with all the obligations of the GDPR and respecting all the rights of data subjects, in which case the controller does not invoke any derogation;

(2) A controller may achieve his purposes by complying with all the obligations of the GDPR, but without being able to ensure that all the rights of the data subjects are respected, in which case he may not rely on any of the exemptions provided for in Article 5(1) GDPR. In other words, he may not invoke the flexibility provided for in Articles 5(1)(b), 5(1)(e), 9(2)(j), 14(5) and 17(3)(d) of the GDPR, but - provided that he respects the appropriate safeguards provided for in Title 4 of the Belgian law - he may invoke the exemptions provided for in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 20 (and 19 and 21, if the processing is for archiving purposes in the public interest);

(3) A controller cannot achieve his purposes if he has to comply with all the obligations of the GDPR, but can ensure compliance with the rights of the data subjects; he must therefore provide appropriate safeguards which constitute technical and organisational measures to derogate from Articles 5.1(b), 5.1(e), 9.2(j), 14.5 and 17.3(d) of the GDPR, but will not be subject to the appropriate safeguards provided for in Title 4 of the Belgian law;

(4) The controller may achieve his purposes only by derogating from the principles and obligations and rights of the data subjects; he must therefore provide for technical and organisational measures and submit to the appropriate safeguards in Title 4 of the Belgian law.

It is clear that Title 4 of the Belgian Data Protection Law does not in any way impose an additional obligation on data controllers for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes. On the contrary, Title 4 provides for appropriate safeguards which the controller wishing to derogate from the rights of data subjects must implement.

TITLE 4. - Processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes referred to in article 89, §§ 2 and 3, of the Regulation

CHAPTER I. – General provisions

Art. 186. This Title sets out the exemption regime with respect to the rights of data subjects referred to in article 89, §§ 2 and 3 of the Regulation.

In so far as the exercise of the rights referred to in article 89, §§ 2 and 3 of the Regulation is likely to make the achievement of the processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes impossible or to seriously hinder this achievement, and as derogations are required to achieve those purposes, the derogations in question shall apply in the conditions set out in this Title.

Art. 187. Articles 190 to 204 do not apply, provided that a code of conduct, approved in accordance with article 40 of the Regulation, is respected.

Art. 188. For the purposes of this Title:

1° "trusted third party" means the natural or legal person, the de facto association or the public administration other than the controller of the processing for archiving purposes or research or statistical purposes, that pseudonymises the data;

2° "communication of data" means communication of data to identified third parties;

3° "dissemination of data" means the disclosure of data without identifying the third parties.

Art. 189. This Title does not apply to processing operations carried out by the authorities referred to in Title 3.⁴

CHAPTER II. - General safeguards

Art. 190. The controller shall designate a data protection officer if the processing of the personal data is likely to result in a high risk as referred to in article 35 of the Regulation.

Art. 191. When processing data for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes, the controller shall, prior to collection, and without prejudice to articles 24 and 30 of the Regulation, add the following elements to the record of processing activities:

1° the justification for the use of the data, whether pseudonymised or not;

2° the reasons why the exercise of the rights by the data subject is likely to make the achievement of the purposes impossible or to seriously hinder it;

3° where appropriate, the data protection impact assessment if the controller processes sensitive data, within the meaning of article 9.1 of the Regulation, for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes.

Art. 192. When processing data for archiving purposes in the public interest, the controller shall, prior to collection, and without prejudice to articles 24 and 30 of the Regulation, add the following elements to the record of processing activities:

1° the justification for the public interest of the stored archives;

2° the reasons why the exercise of the rights by the data subject is likely to make the achievement of the purposes impossible or to seriously hinder it.

CHAPTER III. - Data collection

Section 1 - Data collected from the data subject

Art. 193. Without prejudice to article 13 of the Regulation, any controller collecting personal data from the data subject shall inform the data subject:

1° whether or not the data will be rendered anonymous;

2° the reasons why the exercise of the rights by the data subject is likely to make the achievement of the purposes impossible or to seriously hinder it.

Section 2. - Further processing of data

Art. 194. Where personal data are not collected from the data subject, the controller shall conclude an agreement with the original controller.

The first subparagraph does not apply in cases where:

1° the processing relates to personal data that were made public;

2° European Union law, a law, a decree or an ordinance:

a) gives the controller as a mandate to process personal data for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research or statistical purposes; and

b) prohibits the reuse of the data collected for other purposes.

⁴ Title 3 regulates the processing of personal data by intelligence and security services, armed forces, etc.

Where exempted from concluding an agreement, the controller shall notify the original controller of the data collection.

Art. 195. *The agreement or notification referred to in article 194 shall contain the following elements:*

1° in the event of an agreement, the contact details of the original controller and of the controller of the further processing;

2° the reasons why the exercise of the rights by the data subject is likely to make the achievement of the purpose of the further processing impossible or to seriously hinder it.

Art. 196. *The agreement or notification concerning the data collection shall be appended to the record of processing activities.*

Art. 197. *The controller processing data for research or statistical purposes shall use anonymous data.*

If it is not possible to achieve the research or statistical purpose by processing anonymous data, the controller shall use pseudonymised data.

If it is not possible to achieve the research or statistical purpose by processing pseudonymised data, the controller shall use non-pseudonymised data.

Section 3. - Anonymisation or pseudonymisation of data processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes

Art. 198. *When processing data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, based on data collected from the data subject, the controller shall anonymise or pseudonymise the data once they have been collected.*

Art. 199. *When the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes is carried out by a controller of the further processing which is the same as the controller of the original processing, the controller shall anonymise or pseudonymise the data before the further processing.*

Art. 200. *The controller is only entitled to de-pseudonymise the data if it is necessary for the research or the statistical purposes, and, where applicable, after consulting the data protection officer.*

Art. 201. *Without prejudice to special provisions, when the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes is carried out by a controller other than the original controller, the original controller shall anonymise or pseudonymise the data before communicating them to the controller tasked with the further processing. The controller of the further processing shall not have any access to the pseudonymisation keys.*

Art. 202. § 1. *Without prejudice to special provisions, when the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes combines several original processing activities, the controllers of the original processing activities shall have the data anonymised or pseudonymised by one of the controllers of the original processing or by a trusted third party before communicating them to the controller tasked with the further processing.*

§ 2. *Without prejudice to special provisions, when the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes combines several original processing activities, of which at least one concerns sensitive data, the controllers of the original processing activities shall have the data anonymised or pseudonymised by the controller of the original processing of sensitive data or by a trusted third party before communicating them to the controller tasked with the further processing.*

Only the controller of the original processing who pseudonymised the data or the trusted third party shall have access to the pseudonymisation keys.

Art. 203. *The trusted third party shall:*

1° be bound by professional secrecy within the meaning of article 458 of the Penal Code, subject to other provisions of this Act and of the Regulation;

2° act independently from the controller of the original processing and of the further processing.

Art. 204. Where a data protection officer was designated in accordance with article 190, the latter shall issue opinions on the use of the various pseudonymisation and anonymisation methods, in particular on their effectiveness in terms of data protection.

Section 4. - Dissemination of data processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes

Art. 205. Without prejudice to European Union law, special acts, ordinances or decrees imposing more stringent conditions on the dissemination of data processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes, the controller shall not disseminate any non-pseudonymised data, unless:

1° the data subject has given his consent; or

2° the data were made public by the data subject in person; or

3° the data are closely linked to the public or historical nature of the data subject; or

4° the data are closely linked to the public or historical nature of facts in which the data subject was involved.

Art. 206. Without prejudice to European Union law, special acts, ordinances or decrees imposing more stringent conditions on the dissemination of data processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes, the controller can disseminate pseudonymised data, with the exception of the personal data referred to in article 9.1 of the Regulation.

Section 5. - Communication of data processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes

Art. 207. Without prejudice to European Union law, special acts, ordinances or decrees imposing more stringent conditions on communication, the controller, who communicates non-pseudonymised data to an identified third party for the purposes referred to in article 89 of the Regulation, shall ensure that the identified third party is unable to reproduce the data communicated, except in a handwritten form, in cases where:

1° it concerns personal data as referred to in articles 9.1 and 10 of the Regulation; or

2° the agreement between the controller of the original processing and the controller of the further processing forbids it; or

3° any such reproduction may compromise the safety of the data subject.

Art. 208. The obligation as referred to in article 207 does not apply when:

1° the data subject has given his consent; or

2° the data were made public by the data subject in person; or

3° the data are closely linked to the public or historical nature of the data subject; or

4° the data are closely linked to the public or historical nature of facts in which the data subject was involved.

The procedure for HBM samples collection and use is described in the Law of 19 December 2008 (the Law/Act on HBM). Below, the relevant information (with reference to the applicable

provisions) is copied from the chapter by Lalova et al, An overview of Belgian legislation applicable to biobank research and its interplay with data protection rules:⁵

“The procedure for samples collection is established in the Act on HBM. Removal of HBM for scientific research is permitted on the condition that it is performed for a specific purpose (Article 8(1)(1)(1) of the Act on HBM). The aim should be specified, precise and relevant for the scientific research.

Again, attention should be paid again to the fact that associated data, and more specifically personal data, are collected alongside samples. Hence, in the context of HBM procurement, data protection rules apply as well.

A central place in the samples collection procedure holds the requirement for informed consent - Article 10(1) of the Act on HBM. According to the biobank legislation, informed consent for biobank research shall be given without prejudice to the applicable data protection rules. Pursuant to the Act on HBM, the donor’s consent for biobank research must be given in an informed, conscious and free manner, and it must be written, dated and signed.

The Act on HBM provides for a right to withdraw one’s consent that can be exercised at any time before the HBM has been subjected to any action after having been obtained. It is not necessary to motivate the withdrawal. In literature, this right to withdrawal is perceived as rather symbolic, since the donor loses such it as soon as the custodian stores or processes the HBM. The GDPR also establishes a right to withdraw consent, which holds relatively more weight than the same right under the Act of HBM. Hence, consent for the processing of associated data can be withdrawn at any time, and if done, this would mean that the custodian must delete all processed data, unless the data can be processed on another legal ground. However, the right of withdrawal under GDPR does not affect the lawfulness of the processing conducted before withdrawal.

Another important consideration related to the Belgian biobank legal framework pertains to the distinction between primary and secondary use of HBM. Primary use is defined as ‘any use of human body material to which the donor has explicitly and specifically given consent in the context of the collection’, whereas secondary use is ‘any use of human body material other than that to which the donor has given his consent in the context of the collection’. In Article 20(1) an informed and explicit consent is required for the secondary use of HBM. However, pursuant to the same provision, in cases where it is impossible to seek consent, or where such a request would be exceptionally inappropriate, the positive opinion of an ethics committee would be sufficient to allow the collection of samples.

Use of residual HBM: A further essential point relates to the use of residual HBM. Residual HBM is defined as the material collected for ‘the diagnosis or treatment of the donor which, after a sufficient and relevant part has been stored for the establishing, refining or completing the diagnosis or treatment of the donor on the basis of new scientific data, is redundant in relation to this purpose and could therefore be destroyed’. In the case of residual HBM, consent is presumed, unless, prior to any operation with the material, the donor announced his/her refusal. The refusal must be addressed to the medical specialist referred to in Article 4(1)(1) of the Act on HBM, or to the chief medical officer of the hospital where the sample was taken.

Who obtains consent: The person responsible for obtaining the consent must be a medical specialist.

Sample collection from minors and incapacitated persons: The Act on HBM provides for the possibility to obtain HBM from minors and incapacitated persons (as defined in Article 492 of the Belgian Civil Code) only in cases whereby the collection of samples cannot have serious consequences for the donor and the removal involves cells and tissues that regenerate, or in

⁵ Available here: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-49388-2_10#Fn58_source . Note that in the chapter, we refer to the law of 19 December 2008 as the Act on HBM, however this is just a difference in translation.

cases where the removal is carried out with an autologous purpose. Informed consent is required, and it should be given by the donor's representative in accordance with the Belgian Act of 22 August 2002 on Patients' Rights.

Sample collection from diseased persons: The Act on HBM provides that a presumption, established in Article 10–14 of the Act of 13 June 1986 regarding the removal and transplantation of organs, applies for research biobanking as well. According to the relevant provisions, anyone who has been domiciled in Belgium for 6 months, is presumed to consent to a sample collection after his death, unless he has expressed his opposition (orally or in writing, with the municipal administration, their general practitioner, or online via MaSante.Belgique.be). This is known as the 'opt-out' system. A new Royal Decree, issued on 9 February 2020, further details the rules on the registration of declarations of will concerning post mortem removal of HBM and organs. The decree enters into force on 1 July, 2020. Of interest is Article 11, which introduces a sensibilization step. Namely, a month before reaching the age of maturity, all persons will receive a letter which would inform them about the opt-out system, and their right to opt-out or explicitly opt-in. The future consequences of this law cannot be predicted. It may be assumed that the new generation will be more aware of the system of opting-out, in comparison to many people today who do not know about it. However, it can also be argued that as long as the general public is not structurally informed about these provisions, this could induce yet another obstacle in accessing HBM for research purposes. The key lies in setting up information campaigns, which are not yet foreseen by the government.

The no (commercial) advantage rule: The Act on HBM prohibits that any financial or material advantage is offered or received in exchange for the donation of HBM. The donor can only receive a compensation for the cost or loss of income that is direct results of the donation.

Who removes the sample: The categories of health professionals that have the right to physically obtain HBM are listed in Article 2 of the Royal Decree. These are medical doctors, dentists, nurses, midwives, pharmacists and licensees or masters in chemical sciences authorized to perform clinical biology analysis, and finally, holders of the professional title 'medical laboratory technologist'. It is possible that the collection of HBM from a living donor takes place outside of a hospital, as long as this occurs in an environment where health, safety and discretion are guaranteed."

4. Is research subject's consent required for scientific research? Would using health data for scientific research purposes be possible, if the data was initially collected for other purpose? If yes, describe any conditions of such use.

Response: Our answer to Q3 partially provides information about this topic and reference to the relevant legal provisions.

In addition, it is important to underline the difference between consent as one of the possible legal grounds for valid data processing, as established in the GDPR, and informed consent as an ethical requirement for participation in scientific research. The Belgian law does not impose the use of consent as a legal ground for (primary) data processing, hence the data processing may be based on any of the six legal bases described in Article 6(1) of the GDPR. Regarding further processing of data, the rules established in the GDPR and the rules of the Belgian Data Protection Law, as cited above, apply.

However, informed consent as an ethical requirement for procurement of HBM for scientific research is needed, with some exceptions (as described in Q3 above).

The Belgian Law of 7 May 2004 on experiments on the human person also requires written informed consent for participation (Article 5(7)). Special provisions exist as regards minors, people who are unable to provide consent, and urgent cases (Articles 7-9).

5. From which generally applicable data protection provisions of GDPR (in particular requirements under Articles 13-21) are scientific researchers exempted and under what conditions?

Response: Below the relevant provisions from the Belgian Data Protection Law is cited in full (unofficial translation). With respect to Article 187 below, note that at the current moment, in Belgium there is no code of conduct, approved in accordance with Article 40 of the GDPR.

Art. 186. *This Title sets out the exemption regime with respect to the rights of data subjects referred to in article 89, §§ 2 and 3 of the Regulation.*

In so far as the exercise of the rights referred to in article 89, §§ 2 and 3 of the Regulation is likely to make the achievement of the processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes impossible or to seriously hinder this achievement, and as derogations are required to achieve those purposes, the derogations in question shall apply in the conditions set out in this Title.

Art. 187. *Articles 190 to 204 do not apply, provided that a code of conduct, approved in accordance with article 40 of the Regulation, is respected.*

6. Are there specific provisions which relate to appropriate safeguards, including using or making available anonymous or pseudonymized health data in the context of scientific research?

Response: The relevant provisions of the Belgian Data Protection Law are cited below:

Art. 188. *For the purposes of this Title:*

1° "trusted third party" means the natural or legal person, the de facto association or the public administration other than the controller of the processing for archiving purposes or research or statistical purposes, that pseudonymises the data;

2° "communication of data" means communication of data to identified third parties;

3° "dissemination of data" means the disclosure of data without identifying the third parties.

Art. 189. *This Title does not apply to processing operations carried out by the authorities referred to in Title 3.*

CHAPTER II. - General safeguards

Art. 190. *The controller shall designate a data protection officer if the processing of the personal data is likely to result in a high risk as referred to in article 35 of the Regulation.*

Art. 191. *When processing data for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes, the controller shall, prior to collection, and without prejudice to articles 24 and 30 of the Regulation, add the following elements to the record of processing activities:*

1° the justification for the use of the data, whether pseudonymised or not;

2° the reasons why the exercise of the rights by the data subject is likely to make the achievement of the purposes impossible or to seriously hinder it;

3° where appropriate, the data protection impact assessment if the controller processes sensitive data, within the meaning of article 9.1 of the Regulation, for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes.

Art. 192. *When processing data for archiving purposes in the public interest, the controller shall, prior to collection, and without prejudice to articles 24 and 30 of the Regulation, add the following elements to the record of processing activities:*

1° the justification for the public interest of the stored archives;

2° the reasons why the exercise of the rights by the data subject is likely to make the achievement of the purposes impossible or to seriously hinder it.

Section 3. - Anonymisation or pseudonymisation of data processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes

Art. 198. When processing data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, based on data collected from the data subject, the controller shall anonymise or pseudonymise the data once they have been collected.

Art. 199. When the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes is carried out by a controller of the further processing which is the same as the controller of the original processing, the controller shall anonymise or pseudonymise the data before the further processing.

Art. 200. The controller is only entitled to de-pseudonymise the data if it is necessary for the research or the statistical purposes, and, where applicable, after consulting the data protection officer.

Art. 201. Without prejudice to special provisions, when the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes is carried out by a controller other than the original controller, the original controller shall anonymise or pseudonymise the data before communicating them to the controller tasked with the further processing.

The controller of the further processing shall not have any access to the pseudonymisation keys.

Art. 202. § 1. Without prejudice to special provisions, when the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes combines several original processing activities, the controllers of the original processing activities shall have the data anonymised or pseudonymised by one of the controllers of the original processing or by a trusted third party before communicating them to the controller tasked with the further processing.

§ 2. Without prejudice to special provisions, when the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes combines several original processing activities, of which at least one concerns sensitive data, the controllers of the original processing activities shall have the data anonymised or pseudonymised by the controller of the original processing of sensitive data or by a trusted third party before communicating them to the controller tasked with the further processing.

Only the controller of the original processing who pseudonymised the data or the trusted third party shall have access to the pseudonymisation keys.

Art. 203. The trusted third party shall:

1° be bound by professional secrecy within the meaning of article 458 of the Penal Code, subject to other provisions of this Act and of the Regulation;

2° act independently from the controller of the original processing and of the further processing.

Art. 204. Where a data protection officer was designated in accordance with article 190, the latter shall issue opinions on the use of the various pseudonymisation and anonymisation methods, in particular on their effectiveness in terms of data protection.

7. What are the potential consequences of non-compliance with the rules outlined in the questions above?

Response: The Belgian Data Protection Law foresees administrative (Art. 221) and criminal penalties (Art. 222-30).

TITLE 6. - Penalties

CHAPTER I. - Administrative penalties

Art. 221. § 1. The corrective powers of the supervisory authority by virtue of article 58.2 of the Regulation also apply to articles 7 to 10, 20 to 24, 28 to 70 of Title 2 and to Title 4 of this Act.

Without prejudice to specific provisions, the first paragraph does not apply to processing activities by the competent authorities referred to in article 26, 7°, b) carried out in the performance of their judicial capacity.

§ 2. Article 83 of the Regulation does not apply to the public authorities or their attendants or authorised representatives, unless it concerns legal persons governed by public law who offer products and services on a market.

CHAPTER II. - Criminal penalties

Art. 222. The controller or the processor, its attendant or authorised representative, the competent authority, as referred to in Titles 1 and 2, shall be punishable by means of a fine of two hundred and fifty to fifteen thousand euro in cases where:

1° the personal data are processed without legal basis in accordance with article 6 of the Regulation and articles 29, § 1, and 33, § 1, of this Act, including the conditions for consent and further processing;

2° the personal data are processed in contravention of the conditions imposed by article 5 of the Regulation and article 28 of this Act, whether through gross negligence or maliciously;

3° the processing objected to pursuant to article 21.1 of the Regulation continues without compelling legal reasons;

4° the transfer of personal data to a recipient in a third country or to an international organisation is made in contravention of the safeguards, conditions or exceptions provided for in articles 44 to 49 of the Regulation or articles 66 to 70 of this Act, whether through gross negligence or maliciously;

5° the corrective measure to temporarily or definitively restrict flows in accordance with article 58.2.f) of the Regulation imposed by the supervisory authority is disregarded;

6° the corrective measure within the meaning of article 58.2.d) of the Regulation imposed by the supervisory authority is disregarded;

7° the legal mandate of verification and control of the competent supervisory authority, its members or experts were hampered;

8° rebellious acts, within the meaning of article 269 of the Criminal Code, were committed against the members of the supervisory authority;

9° certification, as referred to in article 42 of the Regulation, is claimed or data protection seals are used publicly, even though the certifications, seals or marks were not issued by an accredited body or are used after the validity of the certification, seal or mark has expired;

10° the certification referred to in article 42 of the Regulation was obtained on the basis of forged documents or incorrect documents;

11° tasks are carried out in the capacity of a certification body, even though that body was not accredited by the competent national accreditation body;

12° the certification body does not conform to the principles and tasks it is subject to, as referred to in articles 42 and 43 of the Regulation;

13° the tasks of the body referred to in article 41 of the Regulation are carried out without accreditation from the competent supervisory authority;

14° the accredited body referred to in article 41 of the Regulation did not take the appropriate measures in cases where the code of conduct, as referred to in article 41.4 of the Regulation, was infringed.

Art. 223. Shall be penalised by means of a fine of five hundred euro to thirty thousand euro, the controller referred to in Title 1, the processor or the person acting under their authority, who:

1° whether through personal negligence, provided it can be qualified as serious, or maliciously, failed to inform the data subject of the existence of personal data relating to him or her that originated from an authority referred to in Title 3 in contravention of article 11, while he was

aware of the origin of the information and did not find himself in one of the situations referred to in article 11, § 2, first paragraph, 1° or 2°;

2° whether through personal negligence, provided it can be qualified as serious, or maliciously, informed the data subject that an authority referred to in Title 3 is the recipient of one of his personal data in contravention of article 12.

Art. 224. Shall be penalised by means of a fine of two hundred euro to ten thousand euro any member or member of staff of the competent supervisory authority or any expert who breached the confidentiality obligation incumbent on him.

Art. 225. When the court sentences on the grounds of an offence described in articles 222 or 223, it may order that the judgment is published, in full or by extract, in one or several newspapers as specified by the court, at the expense of the convicted party.

Art. 226. Any controller or person acting under the authority of the authority referred to in Title 3 or his processor, who, through personal negligence, provided it can be qualified as serious, or maliciously, failed to abide by one of the obligations concerning confidentiality and security referred to in articles 83 to 86, 116 to 119, 149 to 152, 177 and 178 shall be penalised by means of a fine of one hundred euro to ten thousand euro.

Art. 227. Shall be penalised by means of a fine of one hundred euro to twenty thousand euro:

1° any controller, processor, person acting under the authority of the authority referred to in Title 3 or of the processor or the attendant who, through personal own negligence, provided it can be qualified as serious, or maliciously, processes personal data in circumstances other than those referred to in articles 74, 108, 140 and 170;

2° any controller, processor or attendant processing personal data in contravention of the conditions for processing imposed by articles 75, 109, 141 and 170 and any person acting under the authority of the authority referred to in Title 3 or its processor, who through personal negligence, provided it can be qualified as serious, or maliciously, processes data in contravention of the conditions imposed by articles 75, 109, 141 and 170;

3° anyone who, with a view to extracting the data subject's consent to the processing of personal data relating to him or her, uses matters of fact, violence, threats, gifts or promises;

4° anyone who, through personal negligence, provided it can be qualified as serious, or maliciously, transfers, forces or facilitates the transfer of personal data to a country that is not a member of the European Union or to an international organisation without the requirements imposed by articles 93, 94, 126, 127, 159, 160, 182 and 183 having been met;

5° any person who, through personal negligence, provided it can be qualified as serious, or maliciously, gives access to the personal data referred to in articles 99, 132 and 162 for historical, scientific or statistical purposes and processes those data in contravention of articles 102, 104, 135, 137, 165 or 167.

Art. 228. Without prejudice to specific provisions, the controller, the processor, or its representative in Belgium shall be liable for the payment of the fines his attendant or authorised representative are ordered to pay.

Art. 229. § 1. With regard to the infringements referred to in articles 222 and 223, the competent supervisory authority and the Attorney-General's Office can sign a protocol setting out the working arrangements between the supervisory authority and the Public Prosecutor's Office with regard to files relating to facts where the law provides for both an administrative fine and a criminal penalty.

The King, by decree deliberated on in the Council of Ministers, establishes the further rules and the template for this protocol agreement.

This protocol shall be fully consistent with all the legal provisions and shall in particular deal with the procedures applicable to offenders without disregarding the rights of the offenders.

	<p><i>The protocol shall be published in the Belgian Official Journal and on the website of the competent supervisory authority.</i></p> <p><i>§ 2. In the absence of a protocol and in respect of the infringements referred to in articles 222 and 223, the public prosecutor has a period of two months, as of the date the original report is received, to notify the competent supervisory authority that a preliminary investigation or judicial investigation has been launched or prosecutions were initiated. This notification removes the possibility for the supervisory authority to exercise its corrective powers.</i></p> <p><i>The competent supervisory authority cannot impose any penalties until that term has passed. Failing notification by the public prosecutor within two months, the facts shall be subject to administrative penalties only.</i></p> <p><i>Art. 230. All the provisions of Book I of the Criminal Code, including Chapter VII and article 85, are applicable to the infringements described in this Act or its implementing decrees.</i></p> <p><i>The sanctions foreseen by the Law on HBM are described in Art. 23-24.</i></p> <p><i>The sanctions foreseen by the Law on experiments are described in Art. 33.</i></p>
Digitalization of original slides	<p>8. Are there any specific rules regarding digitalization of images of human tissues and biological samples? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: There is a specific law of 19 December 2008 on the acquisition and use of HBM for the purpose of medical application to humans or scientific research. This law lays down a regime for the donation, extraction, procurement, testing, processing, preservation, storage, distribution, and delivery of HBM. There are also specific provisions on the allocation of HBM. It also contains a specific provision on biobanks (see article 22 of the law). The Royal Decree on Biobanks contains specific rules that are of importance for biobanks.</p> <p>The law is applicable to any human biological material, which makes the scope <i>ratione materiae</i> very broad. The law is in principle even applicable to DNA, proteins, gametes, embryos, and fetuses (see article 2 (1) of the Act on human biological material). The scope <i>ratione loci</i> is also broad as the law applies to HBM removed on Belgian territory, but also to samples imported from abroad and used in Belgium.</p> <p>There is however no specific law or specific provisions in the law of 19 December 2008 regarding digitalization of images of human tissue and samples in Belgium. Generating images from human tissue and digitalization of those images will be qualified as a processing of personal data if the patient is identifiable from whom the tissue or samples have been collected. Digital pathology slides will be considered as “representations” of HBM and, therefore, as “data” (“personal data “ if the patient is identifiable).</p>
Ethical board approvals requirements / biomedical research projects	<p>9. Is there a regime requiring an approval of ethical board or any similar or related conditions prior to making WSIs and sharing them for research purposes? If yes, what does that regime entail? Please refer to any rules of obtaining ethical board approvals for biomedical research projects, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: A favourable opinion by an ethics committee is required for all experiments, pursuant to Article 11 of the Law on experiments on the human person.</p> <p>Regarding biobanking, the following information is relevant: (</p> <p><i>“The positive opinion of an ethics committee is required for the establishment of a notified biobank. Pursuant to Article 22(1)(3) of the Act on HBM, such opinions can only be given by ethics committees with full competence.</i></p> <p><i>Once a positive ethics opinion has been obtained in view of a biobank’s general aims and activities, the biobank can also rely upon it as an approval covering particular projects. (See Article 22(1)(3), (4), and (5) of the Law on HBM). Thus the biobank is alleviated from the burden to seek ethical advice for each new procurement of HBM.</i></p>

	<p><i>In addition, prior to any secondary use of HBM, an ethics committee must provide a favourable opinion (Article 21(1) of the Law on HBM). The ethics committee decides on the relevance of the secondary use and its purpose, the adequacy of the information provided to the donor, and the sufficient specificity and the scope of the donor’s consent (Article 21(3) of the Law on HBM).</i></p> <p><i>Finally, in cases where it is impossible to seek the donor’s consent, or where such a request would be exceptionally inappropriate, the positive opinion of an ethics committee is sufficient to allow the collection of HBM. Whereby such a situation arises, it is also the ethics committee’s responsibility to evaluate whether it appears impossible or exceptionally inappropriate to request the donor’s consent (Article 21(3)(3) of the Law on HBM).”⁶</i></p> <p>Academic hospitals in Belgium have their own internal procedures to be applied by researchers who wish to undertake clinical studies. These procedures include an application for approval by the local ethics committee. For example, the university hospital in Leuven requires first to register a new research project on the website of the Clinical Trial Center and to fill in a GDPR Questionnaire, before submitting the application to the Ethics Committee of the hospital. It is noteworthy that academic hospitals in Belgium use “exercise of a task of public interest” as the legal basis for the processing of their patient data for scientific purposes. They refer to their legal task, which is not only to provide healthcare to patients, but also to support scientific research and academic education. Of course, this legal basis is only valid for research and education within the university to which the hospital belongs or eventually within other Belgian universities. In all other cases, the patient is invited to give an explicit consent for further processing of his/her health data.</p> <p>Reuse of patient data for scientific research purposes is generally limited to academic hospitals in Belgium. Other hospitals are reluctant to give access to patient data for research purposes, unless they are anonymised or if patients have given their consent. Private research institutes, such as the Pfizer Clinical Research Unit in Brussels, only use health data collected via informed consent.</p>
Animal tissues and biological samples (non-clinical WSI)	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI of animal samples may be collected in some jurisdictions.</p> <p>10. Are there any rules that regulate use of WSI of animal samples that have already been produced in another study for scientific research purposes? If yes, please describe.</p> <p>Response: In Belgium the legislation on animal testing/experiments is matter for which the Regions are competent. This means that legislation on the use of laboratory animals, the granting of approvals, the carrying out of inspections, etc. falls under the competence of the regional governments and public services in Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels.</p> <p>The legal provisions regulating this topic, are identical for the three Belgian Regions because they are literal transpositions of the European Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. The Royal decree of 29 May 2013 on the protection of laboratory animals, lays down the provisions for testing on animals.</p> <p>The Royal Decree on animal by-products intended for research, education, the feeding of non-food-producing animals and for the manufacture and placing on the market of certain derived products deserves also a mention here. This Royal Decree lays down some rules on the use and importing of animal by-products for research purposes. Important to note is that exploiters who use animal by-products for diagnosis, education and research or in the context of exhibitions and artistic activities must be registered with DG animal, plant and food. There are however no specific rules that regulate the WSI of animal samples.</p>

⁶ See Lalova T. et al. (2021) An Overview of Belgian Legislation Applicable to Biobank Research and Its Interplay with Data Protection Rules. In: Slokenberga S., Tzortzatou O., Reichel J. (eds) GDPR and Biobanking. Law, Governance and Technology Series, vol 43. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49388-2_10

Processing of genetic data	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI metadata may contain genetic information related to the data subject. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>11. How is processing of genetic data regulated? Please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: Belgian legislation does not contain a general framework regulating the use and protection of genetic information. Even the use of genetic testing is not legally regulated. An examination of the current regulations on genetic data reveals that Belgian legislation on this subject is very scattered. A number of specific branches of law regulate the use of genetic testing and genetic data, such as insurance law, labour law, criminal law and family law. One example is Art. 158 of the Belgian Insurance Law of 2014. This article stipulates which information needs to be transmitted to the insurer and prohibits the transmission of information regarding genetic characteristics. Another example is the law of 2003 regarding medical examination in the context of employment relations. Art. 11 of this law prohibits medical examinations with the purpose of collecting genetic information regarding the employee. Finally, as in many other countries, the collection and storing of DNA-profiles in the context of criminal procedures, is subject to specific restrictions.</p> <p>12. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained human genetic data? Are there any additional restrictions on making the human genetic data available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: As stated above the Belgian Data Protection Act of 30 July 2018 regulates the processing of genetic data in the same way as other health data.</p> <p>On the question whether there are any additional restrictions on making human genetic data available to other researchers, there is a specific regime for when personal data is not collected from the data subject, which states that the controller in that case must conclude an agreement with the original controller. Article 195 of the Data Protection Act lists the essential elements which must be included in the agreement: the contact details of the original controller and of the controller of further processing; or, in cases here derogations from certain data subject's right (i.e. right to access, right to rectification, right to restriction of processing, and right to object) have been adopted, the reason why the exercise of these rights is likely to make the achievement of the purpose of further processing impossible or seriously hindering it.</p> <p>In this regard there are also important rules in Article 21 (1), Article 22 (2) (3) of the Act on HBM, and Article 10 of the Royal Decree of 9 January 2018, which state that each provision of HBM by a biobank, whether the HBM is transferred to another biobank or a third party, should be subject to a written agreement with the person or institution receiving the material. This agreement should govern the possible processing of the donor's personal data by the entity to which the material is made available. The rules in the law on HBM requires more elements to be included in the agreement than what is prescribed by Data Protection Rules, such as the subject of the scientific research for which the HBM is made available, the responsibilities for ensuring traceability, a description of the appropriate technical and organization measures to be taken in the case personal data is also communicated, a coded copy of the consent of the donor. There is also in Article 11 of the Royal Decree on Biobanks a specific prohibition of transfer of personal data to third parties, but it is however permissible when it occurs between biobanks.</p>
Data on rare diseases / Covid 19	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI may relate rare disease or Covid19 research. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>13. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on rare diseases? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p>

	<p>Response: There are some specific laws on rare diseases in Belgium, such as the Royal Decree of 25 April 2014 laying down the standards that a function “rare diseases” must meet in order to be recognised and remain recognized. There are also laws on networks for rare diseases (already 11 of these networks exist in Belgium), which exists out of representatives of university hospitals, normal hospitals, general practitioners, and patient associations.⁷ The networks are a partnership that provides care circuits for patients with a rare disease.</p> <p>There is however no specific regulation on WSI that contains data on rare diseases.</p> <p>14. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on Covid19? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: N/A</p>
Clinical trials	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that the original slides may have been collected during clinical trials in the meaning of Directive 2001/20/EC⁸.</p> <p>15. Are there any additional restrictions on making the health data collected during clinical trials available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: Regarding HBM, the answer to this question can be found in the Q&A of the Biobank compendium (see Table 1 for the link), on p. 12:</p> <p><u>Q: Does human body material collected within clinical trials fall within the scope of the Human Body Material Law?</u></p> <p><i>No. Human material collected within clinical trials with medicines or trials in which medicines are compared to medical devices, is excluded from the scope. This means that there are no additional requirements when the material is collected and used as described in a clinical trial application approved by the FAMHP and an ethics committee.</i></p> <p><i>However, if the human samples collected within clinical trials are used for a purpose other than what was provided in the approved dossier, they fall again within the scope of the Human Material Body Law and must be transferred to a biobank.</i></p> <p><i>Samples taken from other types of studies or experiments must always be managed by a biobank.</i></p> <p><u>Q: Can material collected for a clinical trial be used for other purposes?</u></p> <p><i>Yes, if the human body material is used for purposes other than those described in the clinical trial dossier, then the material must be transferred to a biobank.</i></p>
Biobanks	<p>When answering the following questions, please consider applicable requirements if the WSI were submitted by a biobank or from a biobank in your jurisdiction.</p> <p>16. How are biobanks regulated in your jurisdiction? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information</p> <p>Response: Information about the applicable laws is provided in Q1. For more details, please see Section 1 in Lalova T. et al. (2021) An Overview of Belgian Legislation Applicable to Biobank Research and Its Interplay with Data Protection Rules. In: Slokenberga S., Tzortzotou O., Reichel J. (eds) GDPR and Biobanking. Law, Governance and Technology Series, vol 43. Springer.⁹</p>

⁷ See Royal Decree of 25 April 2014 establishing the accreditation standards for the “rare diseases” network; and Royal Decree of 25 April 2014 establishing the characteristics for the designation of reference centres “rare diseases”, called “expertise centres”, within the recognized function ‘rare diseases’.

⁸ DIRECTIVE 2001/20/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

⁹ Available on: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-49388-2_10#Fn58_source

17. Can health data (including WSI) stored in the biobanks be shared with other parties to be used for scientific research purposes? If yes, what are the conditions of such sharing and use?

Response: Article 2 (27) of the Law on HBM establishes that within the scope of the law is “associated data relating to the human body material and the donor”. Such associated data (i.e., biological and medical characteristics of the donor) is regarded as personal data. The procedure for use of samples and health data stored in biobanks is described in our answer to Q3 above. The consent of the donor is required (Article 10 of the Law on HBM), with exceptions (as described above). In addition, the biobank custodian/manager (the term used in the French version of the law is “gestionnaire”) is entrusted by the law with the responsibilities of a data controller (Article 11(3) of the Royal Decree of 9 January 2018). Pursuant to Art. 15, it is the biobank custodian who shall ensure that the HBM (and thus the associated data as well) is made available for use in accordance with the objectives of the biobank and for which authorisations has been given, in accordance with Art. 10 or Art. 20.

In addition to the general rules, described above, more relevant information as to the sharing of health data to other parties, is provided, in the Q&A of the Biobank compendium (see Table 1), on p. 24:

“Q: Can I outsource human body material to a fellow researcher (in Belgium or abroad) to perform a specific analysis, or does this researcher also need to have an agreement with the biobank?”

The transmission of certain tasks to a third party is possible. To do this, it is not necessary to have an agreement with the biobank, provided that:

- *the work done by this fellow researcher is an integral part of the research project, for which you obtained the material from the biobank;*
- *if any material remains, that material is returned or destroyed after use;*
- *the agreement with the biobank does not prohibit this subcontracting.”*

In addition, we refer to the provisions on further processing of data in the Belgian Data Protection Law (see the answer to Q3 above). Their interplay with the biobank rules is discussed below (quote from the chapter from Lalova et al.):

“Further processing of personal data: Pursuant to Article 194 of the Act of 30 July 2018, where personal data are not collected from the data subject, the controller should conclude an agreement with the original controller. The Article 195 lists the essential elements of the agreement: the contact details of the original controller and of the controller of the further processing; or, in cases where derogations from certain data subject’s rights (i.e., right to access, right to rectification, right to restriction of processing, and right to object) have been adopted, the reasons why the exercise of these rights is likely to make the achievement of the purpose of further processing impossible or seriously hinder it.

These rules are directly related to Article 21(1), Article 22(2)(3) of the Act on HBM, and Article 10 of the Royal Decree of 9 January 2018, pursuant to which each provision of HBM by a biobank, whether the HBM is transferred to another biobank or a third party, should be subject to a written agreement with the person or institution receiving the material. The agreement should govern the possible processing of the donor’s personal data by the entity to which the material is made available.⁵⁶ The biobank legislation requires that this type of agreements contain more elements, than what is prescribed in the data protection rules, e.g. the subject of the scientific research for which the HBM is made available; the responsibilities for ensuring traceability; a description of the appropriate technical and organization measures to be taken in the case personal data is also communicated; a coded copy of the consent of the donor.

Finally, Article 11 of the Royal Decree of 9 January 2018, expressly forbids the transfer of personal data to third parties, but permits it if it occurs between biobanks. Questions remain regarding the practical implementation of the provisions discussed above. For instance, a

	<p><i>detailed account of the appropriate technical and organizational measures to be taken in cases of personal data transfers lacks in the current Belgian data protection legislation.”</i></p>
<p>Data localization and infrastructure requirements</p>	<p>18. What are the rules of transferring health data or human tissues for specific research projects to third parties?</p> <p>Response: The answer could be found in the Biobank compendium (cited below), and in addition, the applicable provisions of the Data protection law (see our response to Q17 above).</p> <p>From Biobank compendium (p 21)</p> <p><i>“Question: How can a biobank make samples available to a researcher?</i></p> <p><i>Before making samples available, a written agreement must be concluded between the biobank and another biobank or an end user. This applies both to the transfer of human body material in Belgium and to export.</i></p> <p><i>There are two possibilities: the general rule is that a contract is established. In some cases, a framework agreement can be established.</i></p> <p><i>The actual transfer of samples can take place without the material physically passing through the biobank. However, the biobank must ensure the traceability of the material and must also oversee the donor's consent. Exceptional situations must be part of the contract.”</i></p> <p>From Biobank compendium (p 22)</p> <p><i>“Question: Which conditions should the agreement between the biobank and the researcher fulfil?</i></p> <p>General rule</p> <p><i>The Royal Decree on Biobanks of 9 January 2018 describes the minimum content of the written agreement:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. the object of the scientific research for which the human body material is made available. The description of it must be in accordance with the opinion of the ethics committee as to the objectives and activities of the biobank;</i> <i>2. responsibilities to ensure traceability;</i> <i>3. if personal data (coming from the medical file of the donor) are provided by a biobank when human body material is made available, the description of the appropriate technical and organisational measures;</i> <i>4. in the case where the biobank, following the provision of human body material, communicates personal data to another biobank:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• in the case of living donors, a template of the consent form (with the contents of the consent) is attached to the agreement;</i> <i>• in the case of deceased donors or residual human body material, the declaration that the legal provisions have been complied with is attached to the agreement.</i> <p>Exception: framework agreement</p> <p><i>The Royal Decree on Biobanks of 9 January 2018 also allows that a framework agreement be concluded between a biobank and end users. The conditions for this are as follows:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. the responsibilities in terms of traceability, data of personal nature and consent are elaborated in a written framework agreement. The researcher must be contractually respect the obligations of this framework agreement, for example by including them in an employment contract of or in standard procedures of a quality system (SOPs).</i> <i>2. the framework agreement describes, in general terms, the purpose of the scientific research for which the human body material may be made available.</i>

	<p>3. the manager of the human body material of the biobank records the specific purpose of the scientific research for which each sample of human body material is made available and confirms in writing to the researcher that consent has been obtained for the specific purpose.”</p> <p>19. Are there any provisions restricting transfer of health data outside of your country?</p> <p>Response: <u>The answer to this question can be found in the Q&A of the Biobank compendium (see Table 1), on p. 6:</u></p> <p>“Q: Do samples exported outside Belgium fall within the scope of the law?”</p> <p>Yes. Samples must first be registered in one (or more) Belgian biobank(s) before being sent abroad. There must be a contract or framework agreement (see below) with the end user or biobank abroad. Through this contract or agreement, it is determined how the obligations relating to traceability, the control of the donor's consent, the feedback to the donor of the human body material will be respected.”</p> <p><u>The restrictions of the GDPR on transferring data to third countries outside the EEA apply (GDPR Art. 44-50). Personal data can be transmitted freely within this area without restrictions. The GDPR prohibits the transfer of personal data outside the EEA in general, with several exceptions. These exceptions include, for instance, adequacy decisions on third countries, binding corporate rules and standard contractual clauses.</u></p> <p>20. Are there any specific infrastructure/security requirements for storing health data?</p> <p>Response: Belgian hospitals have to comply with so-called <u>Minimum Rules (MNM)</u>. The content of the minimum norms are inspired by the ISO 27000-norms. The MNM were drafted by the <u>eHealth-platform</u>.</p> <p>The MNM's are divided in 15 chapters. Each chapter addresses a particular aspect of information security with each point specifically focusing on information security in the use and processing of health data. There is for example a chapter on information security governance, secure staffing, management of assets, access-security, cryptography, physical protection and protection of the environment, security of operations, communication security, development and maintenance of information systems, et cetera.</p> <p>There is also an obligation in the Belgian Data Protection Act to designate a DPO, specifically in cases where personal data are processed for scientific research purposes and the processing may result in a high risk.¹⁰ When personal data is processed for scientific purposes, the controller must anonymize or pseudonymize the personal data after it is collected. In cases of further processing, it is possible to de-pseudonymize the personal data only when necessary for the research purposes and, where applicable, after consulting the DPO.¹¹ The DPO also must issue opinions on the use of the various pseudonymization and anonymization methods employed.¹² The DPO thus provides an additional layer of security for the storage and processing of health data.</p>
Honest broker model	<p>21. Is there a trusted third party service (“honest broker”) established in your jurisdiction, where researcher may submit a request for the data to be pseudonymized before access? If yes, please provide the name of the service, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: Yes, please see response to Q22 below. Please note that pseudonymisation by a trusted third party or by one of the data providers is mandatory before transmitting health data</p>

¹⁰ Article 190 Belgian Data Protection Act. Please read the explanation regarding the limited scope of the provisions of Title 4 of the Belgian Data Protection Act in our answer on Q3.

¹¹ Article 198-200 Belgian Data Protection Act.

¹² Article 204 Belgian Data Protection Act.

	<p>to researchers who wish to benefit from one or more of the exemptions mentioned in Art. 89(2) GDPR, if they collect health data from multiple sources (Art. 202 of the Data Protection Law).</p> <p>22. Please describe any restrictions or limitations regarding “honest broker” of health data according to your national law.</p> <p>Response: The Belgian eHealth platform offers various free of charge services that can be used by all actors in the healthcare sector and their ICT-service providers for the development of online services or for the unlocking of validated authentic sources.</p> <p>One of these services includes a trusted third party service (TTP-service). The eHealth-platform acts as a TTP in the context of a request for disclosure of personal data concerning health. This service allows an institution or healthcare provider holding medical data to send its data in an anonymous form to a known recipient. The information that allows the person concerned to be identified is encrypted. Anonymization will also be performed at the level of the sender of the message so that the recipient does not know from whom the medical data he has received originates and it is not possible to deduce in this way to whom the medical data refers.</p> <p>The TTP works as follows, the sending and receiving of health data is done via the eHealthBox, the messages will be processed by the TTP coding system in order to anonymize them. Once the message is processed and delivered, the sender receives a receipt so he is certain that the message was received, or he receives a notification with the reason why it could not be processed. The process takes around 2 hours in total.</p> <p>In order to use this service by the eHealth-platform you must receive an authorization by the sectoral committee and some other minor formalities need to be fulfilled, which can be found on here: Tempalte-report (fgov.be) (this document also provides in general information on the service in English). If you do not fulfil the conditions to use the TTP-service this could be seen as a limitation or restriction.</p>
<p>Contractual limitations / limitation on commercial use of WSIs</p>	<p>23. Are there any mandatory provisions which impose specific terms of use of health data or WSI by researchers? Please include any limitations on commercial use of WSIs. In your response, please provide name of the law and explain the requirements under such provisions.</p> <p>Response: There is a law on the use of human material for research: the Act on HBM (see link to the official publication in the Belgian Official Gazette here: https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=nl&la=N&table_name=wet&cn=2008121944 available in Dutch and French).</p> <p>The use of health data by researchers is regulated by the Belgian Data Protection Act (see for information about the processing of health data the response on question 11). The use of health data for research should be anonymized or pseudonymised.¹³ The Belgian data protection act has a separate chapter about how the data should be anonymised or pseudonymised for research purposes.¹⁴ The responsibility of pseudonymisation or anonymisation lays with the controller after the collection of the data.</p> <p>However there is no specific law in Belgium that regulates the use of WSI.</p>
<p>Copyrights / database rights / data license requirements</p>	<p>24. Under the laws of your jurisdiction, would the WSI be subject to copyright protection, database rights, any other intellectual property rights? Who would be the holder of such rights?</p> <p>Response: There is a separate regime for database rights in Belgium in the Belgian Act on Economic Law (see article XI.186 - XI.188 of the Belgian Economic Law Act). Under this right databases that constitute the author’s own intellectual creation through the choice or arrangement of the material are protected as such by copyright. The holder of this right is thus</p>

¹³ Article 197 Belgian Data Protection Act.

¹⁴ See Article 198-204 Belgian Data Protection Act.

	<p>the author of the database. The conditions to be considered a database under this right are the following: there must be a collection of data, arranged in a systematic or methodical way and, in addition, the individual data must be able to be accessed separately thanks to electronic means. The owner of the database of WSI could be considered holder of this database right. The non-profit retrieval for education or scientific research can however happen without the consent of the author of the database.</p> <p>The right to photograph could also be relevant for WSI. This is a right of consent that is granted to any depicted person for any depiction of the human image, as well as for any use of this image for unauthorized purposes. The right is included in article XI.174 of the Belgian Act of Economic Law. The legal doctrine and jurisprudence unanimously declare that the person depicted must be recognisable. If the person depicted is not recognisable, this right to photograph is not applicable and the consent of the depicted person is no longer necessary. For WSI, the person will not be recognisable which makes this right not applicable.</p> <p>25. Are those IP rights transferrable or could a license to use them be granted? If yes, please describe any statutory conditions, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: The database right is transferrable or could be licenced to a third party. The Belgian law does not provide any special statutory conditions for transfers or licences of database rights.</p>
Removal of commercially sensitive information (trade secrets)	<p>26. Are there any laws (other than GDPR/data protection laws) which would make it mandatory that certain information (e.g. commercial information) is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information must be removed.</p> <p>Response: No, however if certain information contained in the WSI or its metadata would constitute a trade secret of the data submitter, he/she may decide to remove it.</p> <p>In Belgium, the trade secret law is a transposition of the EU Directive 2016/943 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure.</p> <p>To be considered a trade secret it is not obligated to register it or to submit a request. The information must fulfil the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the information is a secret in the sense that, as a whole or in the proper composition and arrangement of its components, it is not generally known to, or readily accessible to, persons within the circles ordinarily concerned with the type of information in question; • it possess commercial value because it is secret; • it has been subjected by the person lawfully in possession of the information to reasonable measures, given the circumstances, to keep it secret. <p>The protection of trade secrets occurs automatically, there is no specific intellectual property right that protects it. But it is important in order to enjoy the protection that the holder of the information took reasonable measures to keep it secret. These can include: surveillance in a vault, a password, encryption, etc.</p> <p>Because of the broad definition of trade secret in Belgian law (and the EU directive) it can be concluded that the WSI (and the metadata connected to it) can be considered a trade secret. The data submitter could therefore decide to keep certain information secret and remove it from the WSI under trade secret protection.</p> <p>27. Are there any laws which would prohibit that certain information is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information cannot be removed.</p> <p>Response: No.</p>

	<p>28. Are there any other limitations on the submitter of the WSIs with respect to making them available without information constituting a trade secret of the owner?</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Access to public information	<p>29. Which public information laws apply? Please explain how they may impact disclosing of WSI by the foreseen data provider.</p> <p>Response: The Act of 4 May 2016 on the re-use of public sector information.¹⁵ The re-use of public information means the use of government documents for commercial or non-commercial purposes other than the original purpose within the public mission of an agency for which the documents were produced. This law is however only applicable to government bodies (such as the Flemish and local governments, institutions with a public mission and environment entities). The definition of a “government document” is very broad, it includes any information, regardless of the medium, that is in the possession of a government agency. Due to this broad definition WSI could fall under the scope of the Act on the re-use of public sector information. However the law excludes “government documents” that are available to research institutions.¹⁶</p> <p>The data provider in a research project that submits data to the project will not fall under the application of the Act on the re-use of public sector information (as it is not a government body). Therefore the impact of this law on the disclosure of WSI by data providers for research purposes will be limited.</p> <p>30. Please briefly describe the rules of public information access and possible restrictions and specify to which type of providers they would apply.</p> <p>Response: See answer to question 29.</p>
Requirements for development of AI/ML	<p>31. Are there any restrictions or rules regarding use of health data or WSI in the context of development of artificial intelligence and machine learning systems (AI / ML)?</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Requirement for contributing slides to BigPicture	<p>32. Assuming that the source of the WSI slides (see Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus) for your jurisdiction will be as provided above, please summarize the requirements, in particular (a) which of the laws are applicable to contributing the WSI, (b) what steps are required to provide them and (c) from a point of view of data protection laws, in which form (“raw”, anonymized, pseudonymized) may the WSI be submitted?</p> <p>Response: Belgium does not have legislation regarding the use of HBM for the production of WSI slides. In our opinion, such slides have to be qualified as images and consequently, insofar as information relating to an identifiable natural person can be deduced from these images or from the information accompanying these images, as personal data of which the processing is regulated by the European and Belgian data protection legislation. The production and the use of the WSI slides, including the information accompanying the slides, are not regulated by the legal provisions relating to biobanks but only by the provisions of the data protection legislation. The WSI slides are not “data associated with the HBM” and consequently they are not part of the biobank of HBM from which the slides have been generated.</p> <p>The production of WSI slides in Belgium currently takes place in academic hospitals or, by specialised partners (processors) on behalf of academic hospitals. Such hospitals systematically collect HBM from their patients and store the HBM in biobanks administered by the hospital (see, for example, for CHU Liège: the Biothèque Hospitalo-Universitaire de Liège (BHUL)).</p>

¹⁵ Act of 4 May 2016 on the re-use of public sector information, <http://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/eli/wet/2016/05/04/2016009236/justel> (published in Dutch and French).

¹⁶ Article 3 § 2 7° Act on the re-use of public sector information.

	<p>Patients in some academic hospitals have a possibility to opt-out (see, for example, the patient opt-out form of CHU Liège)</p> <p>The legal basis on which the hospitals rely to produce WSI slides, is “processing necessary to perform a task of public interest”. Academic hospitals have not only a task to provide healthcare to patients but also a task to contribute to scientific medical research and education. (see, for example, the privacy policy addressed to patients of CHU Liège)</p> <p>WSI slides held by Belgian academic hospitals can be used for their own internal research projects and also for other research projects in which they participate as a partner. Contributing WSI slides to a common repository such as BigPicture is, therefore, possible from a legal point of view. The internal procedures for the recognition of the research project, including the approval of the hospital ethical committee, must of course be respected. (see, for CHU Liège: https://www.chuliege.be/jcms/c2_16986309/nl/comite-d-ethique-hospitalo-facultaire-universitaire-de-liege/accueil)</p> <p>The specific legal provisions applicable to the further use of the WSI slides, once made accessible via the BigPicture repository, will depend on 1) the data protection law applicable to the research project for which these slides will be used, and 2) if Belgian data protection law is applicable to this research project, the requirements of this particular research project with regard to the necessity to benefit from the research exemptions mentioned in Art. 89(2) of the GDPR (see the 4 possible scenarios in the answer to Q3).</p> <p>It is not excluded that ethical committees in Belgian academic hospitals will be reluctant to approve “blank” access to their WSI slide collections and to delegate their competence to an entity belonging to a common repository. It is also not excluded that ethical committees of academic hospitals in Belgium will be reluctant to approve the use of WSI slides in research projects regulated by data protection laws of other Member States.</p>
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Notes to the respondents

Background:

- The clinical part of the BIGPICTURE data repository will consist of digital scans of slides of human tissues or biological samples (WSI, whole slide imaging). The original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies. Those studies may have been conducted in the past or are ongoing trials. However, the primary purpose of collection of the slides will be the clinical studies or treatment of patients. Thus, the original slides will not be collected directly and primarily for the purpose of digitization for the BIGPICTURE data repository. We assume that the collection of the original slides was done in line with the requirements applicable to the such purpose.
- BIGPICTURE data repository will also reuse WSI from animal tissues that are also going to be digitized slides from existing collections. The BIGPICTURE repository will only store digital slides (WSI), not the glass originals or biological samples.
- The WSI will be accompanied by metadata (i.e. not only image will be stored). Scope of the metadata may vary, depending on the type of WSI.
- The purpose of storing the WSI is to make them available for scientific and research purposes.
- WSI will not be submitted from public health registries or electronic patient record systems.
- The data submitters will have digital pathology slides or will digitize slides generated as part of clinical diagnostic work that, in some instances, will have also been used in clinical studies. For some submitters, in case duplicate samples to the clinical samples are collected in the biobank of human tissues, DNA/RNA and body fluids, data that have been generated as part of research projects that have used these samples may be used. There may be additionally data from archives. No animal experimentation will be performed for the purpose of data collection in the project.
- Additional patient information may accompany WSI. The list will be provided at a later stage, however before month 6 of the project. Results from genomic investigation may be used as associated data in some WSI collections.

Source of WSI

At the current stage of the project, the following have been confirmed as initial data submitters:

UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT	UMC UTRECHT	Netherlands	Cancer node
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT	RUMC	Netherlands	Cancer node
Azienda Ospedaliera Per L'Emergenza Cannizzaro	AOEC	Italy	Cancer node
Technical University of Munich	TUM	Germany	Cancer node
PHILIPPS UNIVERSITAET MARBURG	UMR	Germany	Clinical trial node
THE LEEDS TEACHING HOSPITALS NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE TRUST	LTHNHS	UK	Liver node
HELSINGIN JA UUDENMAAN SAIRAANHOITOPPIIRIN KUNTAYHTYMÄ	HUS	Finland	Lung node
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT GRAZ	MUG	Austria	Lung node
DECIPHEX	DECIPHEX	Ireland	Non-clinical node
Medical University Vienna	MUW	Austria	Renal node
OSTERGOTLANDS LANS LANDSTING	RO	Sweden	Skin node
Linköping University	LiU	Sweden	Skin node
UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE	Belgium	Skin node

Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus

Instructions:

Please provide responses to the below questions based on the laws of your jurisdiction. Please use the below example as guidance as to the level of required detail. **Please note that the provided responses are for**

exemplary purposes only. The circumstances in your jurisdiction may be different, as well as legal basis and legal steps for contributing WSIs to the BigPicture project.

We are looking for a practical description of issues which may impede or influence the planned collection of WSIs and their sharing with other researchers. If certain matter is regulated by GDPR, please do not explain in detail. Mere reference to GDPR rules is sufficient. If the response to certain questions is not clear under the current legal framework or the approach taken depends on the organization, please indicate this and, if possible, describe the most common approach.

Appendix 3 - Finland Country Report

Responses for Finland

Contributor: Tom Southerington (University of Turku)

Topic	Questions
National provisions on personal data processing in the context of scientific research	<p>1. Which national laws regulate use and sharing of health (“health data”), including WSIs, for research purposes? Please provide the name of the law, online reference, and relevance for the BigPicture (if not explained in other sections below)</p> <p>Response: In particular these acts regulate use and sharing of health data in Finland taking into account the context described in Background above (so not necessarily covering all possible instances of using health data, etc.):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Protection Act (“DPA”, 1050/2015 www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2018/en20181050) containing provisions supplementing the GDPR. DPA provides for specific provisions of its applicability and relation to the foreign law (Section 3 of the DPA)¹. • Act on the Status and Rights of Patients (785/1992, finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/1992/19920785, no up-to-date translation) which among other things governs the storage of patient samples and data and for example stipulates that patient data is confidential and can only be disclosed to persons not involved in the particular patient’s care with the patient’s consent or if specifically authorised by law. • Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Care Data (“Secondary Use Act”, 552/2019, www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2019/20190552, no translation yet), which among other things stipulates requirements for secondary use of patient data and also reusing the research data of public health care providers. This Act does not apply to accessing the samples and data held by the biobanks, which are regulated by the Biobank Act. • Biobank Act (688/2012, www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2012/en20120688.pdf) governs setting up biobanks for patient and donor samples and related data for future research use. Other types of sample collections are typically not referred to as biobanks in Finland. Both research and patient samples can be transferred to registered biobanks, after which their use is regulated by the Biobank Act. The Act is under review and might change significantly potentially already in 2022. • Act on the Medical Use of Human Organs, Tissues and Cells (1001/2001, www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2001/en20010101.pdf) governs the use of tissue samples etc. material for other than their intended diagnostic or health care purposes, if they have not been transferred to a registered

¹ Data Protection Act, Section 3 Applicable law: “Finnish law applies to the processing of personal data in the context of activities of an establishment of a controller or a processor located in the territory of the European Union, if the controller is established in Finland. If the law of a foreign state applies to the processing of personal data and derogations are made by virtue of it in accordance with Article 89(2) of the Data Protection Regulation from the rights provided for the protection of the data subject, the safeguards laid down for the protection of the data subject in section 31 below shall, however, be complied with irrespective of the choice of applicable law.”

biobank under the Biobank Act. The act does not address data, only human biological material.

There is a “Genome Act” in preparation, and it might affect access to genetic data, but the exact content of the act is not known yet.

Further information for:

- Biobanks - see e.g. www.biopankki.fi/en/
 - Secondary use of electronic health records etc. data - see e.g.: www.findata.fi/en/
2. Please describe how the databases and registers containing patient’s health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are organized in your jurisdiction and which type of data they contain. If possible, please indicate which databases or registers may be relevant for BigPicture.

Response: Health care data and the data in national health registers are available on application for permitted purposes like scientific research from the public health care provider (when only their data required) or Findata (application for private medical records’ or several care providers’ data). From 1.5.2022 onwards, unless permanently anonymised, data can be made available only to processing environments verified and approved in accordance with the Secondary Use Act. Permissions granted now will only apply until 30.4.2022.

Human biological samples in registered biobanks, technical records of the samples (like WSI) and associated data (sample related metadata, but also related diagnoses etc.) are available on application for research projects from the biobanks. The Biobank Act is expected to be renewed, and it is possible that the renewal will include similar restrictions on processing environments as the Secondary Use Act (see above). It is also possible that the application process will change.

3. Please describe general conditions on using patient’s health data and WSIs of human biological samples for scientific research purposes.

Response: This is a very broad question, but here is an outline taking into account the context described in Background:

- approved application to access the material for a research project (either from biobanks or authorities under the Secondary Use Act),
- data at least pseudonymised as a main rule,
- ethical review (in most biobank cases, not if applying for data under the Secondary Use Act),
- no onward transfers or disclosures to third parties,
- general data protection requirements.

Further comments:

- Directly identifiable data can be provided exceptionally if necessary for the research. The authority who grants access decides whether the data can be provided in a pseudonymized or anonymized manner. Biobank data is almost always coded in order to be able to respond to donor questions regarding use of their data. Biobanks can provide data exceptionally with identifiers as well, mainly to enable connecting with already collected research data. The level of de-identification of data that would fulfil the criteria of anonymous data further to understanding adopted by the Finnish data protection authorities

(in line with the WP29 opinion on data anonymization) may be difficult to achieve in relation to health data, in particular WSI.

- Data under the Secondary Use Act will be available only to checked and approved processing environments starting 1.5.2022 and similar requirements may in the future apply to biobank data as well. Under the Secondary Use Act, only aggregated statistical data (irrevocably anonymised) is available for non-scientific research and development activities.
 - If the data are considered personal data, then under the Data Protection Act (DPA), if GDPR's data subject rights (Art 15, 16, 18 or 21) are deviated from, a GDPR data protection impact assessment (DPIA) must be performed by the data controller of the research data and provided to data protection authorities in advance or relevant GDPR-approved code of conduct followed (see also answer 5 below).
 - In addition, in the general BigPicture context, biobanks who are expected to provide the WSI should have performed DPIAs for their operations, but if they would start using BigPicture entities as processors to hold data for onwards disclosures they should perform a specific DPIA regarding this process (in accordance with the EDPB guidance and the conditions of Art. 35 GDPR).
 - Based on the Section 31 DPA (as further explained in question 5), if GDPR's data subject rights (Art. 15, 16, 18 or 21) are deviated from, it is also required that: 1) the processing is based on an appropriate research plan; 2) a person or group responsible for the research has been designated; and 3) the personal data are used and disclosed only for scientific or historical research purposes or for other compatible purposes, and the procedure followed is also otherwise such that data concerning a given individual are not revealed to outsiders².
4. Is research subject's consent required for scientific research? Would using health data for scientific research purposes be possible, if the data was initially collected for other purpose? If yes, describe any conditions of such use.

Response: Consent is required for physically or psychologically invasive research (Medical Research Act 488/1999, some changes pending www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/1999/en19990488.pdf), but for processing personal data consent is just one of the options for legal bases. The questions and this response largely relates to use of data not initially collected for research. Secondary use of samples/data is possible subject to the rules described in other answers.

5. From which generally applicable data protection provisions of GDPR (in particular requirements under Articles 13-21) are scientific researchers exempted and under what conditions?

Response: There are exceptions provided in the Finnish Data Protection Act.

Section 6 Processing of special categories of personal data

Article 9(1) of the General Data Protection Regulation does not apply:

... 7) to the processing of data for scientific or historical research purposes or for statistical purposes; ...

² Section 31 <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2018/en20181050.pdf>

Where personal data are processed in a context referred to in subsection 1, the controller and the processor shall take suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights of the data subject.

Such measures include [list of examples]:

- 1) measures that enable subsequent checking and verification of the identity of the person who has recorded, altered or transferred personal data;
- 2) measures to improve the competence of the personnel processing personal data;
- 3) designation of a data protection officer;
- 4) internal measures by the controller and the processor for preventing access to personal data;
- 5) pseudonymisation of personal data;
- 6) encryption of personal data;
- 7) measures that ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services related to the processing of personal data, including the ability to restore the availability of and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;
- 8) a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing;
- 9) specific rules of procedure for ensuring compliance with the Data Protection Regulation and this Act when personal data are transferred or processed for another purpose;
- 10) a data protection impact assessment in accordance with Article 35 of the Data Protection Regulation;
- 11) other technical, procedural and organisational measures.

Section 31 Derogations and safeguards relating to processing of personal data for scientific and historical research purposes and statistical purposes

Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes, the rights of the data subject laid down in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 of the Data Protection Regulation may be derogated from, where necessary, provided that:

- 1) the processing is based on an appropriate research plan;
- 2) a person or group responsible for the research has been designated; and
- 3) the personal data are used and disclosed only for scientific or historical research purposes or for other compatible purposes, and the procedure followed is also otherwise such that data concerning a given individual are not revealed to outsiders.

...

Where personal data referred to in Article 9(1) and Article 10 of the Data Protection Regulation are processed for the purposes referred to in subsection 1 or 2, a derogation from the rights of the data subject provided in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 of the Data Protection Regulation requires, in addition to what is provided in subsections 1 and 2, that a data protection impact assessment referred to in Article 35 of the Data Protection Regulation be carried out or that codes of conduct in accordance with Article 40 of the Data Protection Regulation, in which the

derogation from the rights of the data subject referred to above is appropriately taken into account, be complied with.

The written data protection impact assessment shall be submitted by the research party (data controller) to the Data Protection Ombudsman for information before the processing is started.

Section 33 Restrictions concerning the controller's obligation to provide information to data subjects

The obligation to provide information to data subjects referred to in Articles 13 and 14 of the Data Protection Regulation may be derogated from, if this is necessary for national security, defence or public order and security, for preventing or investigating offences, or for a supervisory task relating to taxation or public finances.

The provisions of paragraphs 1–4 of Article 14 of the Data Protection Regulation may also be derogated from if the provision of information causes substantial damage or detriment to the data subject and the data to be recorded are not used for decision-making concerning the data subject.

If a data subject is not provided with information under subsection 1 or 2, the controller shall take appropriate measures to protect the rights of the data subject. These measures include keeping the information referred to in Article 14(1) and (2) of the Data Protection Regulation available to the public, unless this undermines the purpose of the restriction concerning the provision of information.

Section 34 Restrictions concerning the right of access by data subject

The data subject does not have the right of access to data which have been collected concerning him or her, referred to in Article 15 of the Data Protection Regulation, if:

- 1) providing access to the data could compromise national security, defence, or public order and security, or hamper the prevention or investigation of offences;
- 2) providing access to the data could seriously endanger the health or treatment of the data subject or the rights of some other person; or
- 3) the personal data are used in the performance of supervisory and inspection tasks and the refusal to provide access to the data is necessary to safeguard an important economic or financial interest of Finland or the European Union.

If only a part of the data concerning a data subject is such that it under subsection 1 falls outside the scope of the right of access referred to in Article 15 of the Data Protection Regulation, the data subject has the right of access to the remainder of the data concerning him or her.

The data subject shall be informed of the reasons for the restriction, unless this undermines the purpose of the restriction.

Where the data subject does not have the right of access to data which have been collected concerning him or her, the information referred to in Article 15(1) of the Data Protection Regulation shall be provided to the Data Protection Ombudsman on the request of the data subject.

6. Are there specific provisions which relate to appropriate safeguards, including using or making available anonymous or pseudonymized health data in the context of scientific research?

Response: See 5 above. In accordance with the Biobank Act, samples and data must normally be pseudonymised. Under Secondary Use Act data is also normally at least

	<p>pseudonymised and specific processing environment rules³ will apply from 1.5.2022. Those rules do not however apply to biobanks, as they are regulated under the Biobank Act. The permissions processes can also be seen as safeguards as can material/data transfer agreements and the administrative decisions required to get access to the data.</p> <p>7. What are the potential consequences of non-compliance with the rules outlined in the questions above?</p> <p>Response: GDPR fines, penal code fines, breach of confidentiality up to 1 year imprisonment, damages to data subjects. Loss of licence to use. Loss of trust on which especially the biobanks rely.</p>
Digitalization of original slides	<p>8. Are there any specific rules regarding digitalization of images of human tissues and biological samples? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: Not for research purposes. Handling human biological material for health care purposes is subject to traceability, quality etc. requirements in particular in the Act on the Medical Use of Human Organs, Tissues and Cells (1001/2001, www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2001/en20010101.pdf).</p>
Ethical board approvals requirements / biomedical research projects	<p>9. Is there a regime requiring an approval of ethical board or any similar or related conditions prior to making WSIs and sharing them for research purposes? If yes, what does that regime entail? Please refer to any rules of obtaining ethical board approvals for biomedical research projects, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: An ethical review is an absolute statutory requirement for (medical) research involving physically or psychologically invasive activities (Medical Research Act 488/1999, some changes pending www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/1999/en19990488.pdf). For access to biobank collections, an ethical review is also required, but this is sometimes performed by the biobanks' own scientific boards as part of processing the access application. However, in practice in many (if not most) cases a statement from a statutory committee established in accordance with the Medical Research Act is required (requires a separate prior application).</p>
Animal tissues and biological samples (non-clinical WSI)	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI of animal samples may be collected in some jurisdictions.</p> <p>10. Are there any rules that regulate use of WSI of animal samples that have already been produced in another study for scientific research purposes? If yes, please describe.</p> <p>Response: No specific rules.</p>
Processing of genetic data	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI metadata may contain genetic information related to the data subject. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>11. How is processing of genetic data regulated? Please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p>

³ Included in the Secondary Use Act (<https://findata.fi/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2020/10/20ddc0dd-findata-maarays-1-2020-muiden-palveluntarjoajien-tietoturvalisille-kayttoymparistoille-asetettavat-vaatimukset.pdf>)

	<p>Response: No specific rules on genetic data. A Genome Act is in preparation and might affect the use of genetic data.</p> <p>12. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained human genetic data? Are there any additional restrictions on making the human genetic data available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: Not currently. A “Genome Act” is in preparation and might affect access to genetic data, but this is not known yet.</p>
Data on rare diseases / Covid 19	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI may relate rare disease or Covid19 research. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>13. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on rare diseases? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: Not specifically, but rare data can be more identifiable despite protections and this may affect decisions to grant access to them.</p> <p>14. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on Covid19? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: No specific rules.</p>
Clinical trials	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that the original slides may have been collected during clinical trials in the meaning of Directive 2001/20/EC⁴.</p> <p>15. Are there any additional restrictions on making the health data collected during clinical trials available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: Clinical trial (samples and) data are typically subject to study-specific informed consents, sometimes specific ethical committee requirements, and of course the general data protection rules. If performed by public health care organisations, trial data can be subject to the Secondary Use Act and obtainable for further research in accordance with that act. Trial samples and related data can sometimes be stored in a registered biobank, in which case they are available for research from there. The EU Clinical Trials Regulation will start to apply 31.1.2022. Some national complementing legislation is pending.</p> <p>The majority of clinical (pharmaceutical) trials are performed by/on behalf of the industry, who typically control the collected data, sometimes also samples. Even if the case report forms were not available, often some of the data will be marked in medical records and thus available under the Secondary Use Act.</p>
Biobanks	<p>When answering the following questions, please consider applicable requirements if the WSI were submitted by a biobank or from a biobank in your jurisdiction.</p> <p>16. How are biobanks regulated in your jurisdiction? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information</p> <p>Response: The Biobank Act (changes planned, potentially in 2022, exact content not known yet, www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2012/en20120688.pdf). Biobanks maintain collections of samples and related data (metadata, clinical data etc. linked to the samples) for future research purposes. WSI produced by the</p>

⁴ DIRECTIVE 2001/20/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

	<p>biobank would be considered a technical record of the sample. Researchers can apply for them to be used in their specific research projects (research plan required). A Material/data transfer agreement (M/DTA) is also required. Agreement terms include e.g. obligations to make research results public and to provide data analysed from biobank samples back to the biobank.</p> <p>17. Can health data (including WSI) stored in the biobanks be shared with other partners to be used for scientific research purposes? If yes, what are the conditions of such sharing and use?</p> <p>Response: See above. Sharing samples and related data is the purpose of the Finnish biobanks. Other types of sample collections are not normally referred to as biobanks in Finland. Please note that only the registered biobanks are considered biobanks and their purpose is to support research by making samples and data available on application. Research and hospital collections outside of these biobanks are not referred to as biobanks, but just sample collections, pathology archives etc. The requirement is an application approved by the biobank in question. Biobanks can only withhold their samples/data on justified bases.</p> <p>Under the current law, applicants must provide a research plan, a statement by a competent ethics committee under the Medical Research Act or another statement enabling assessment and an account of the processing of the samples and information. The biobank can refuse a request based on the biobank's research area and operating policies, to secure intellectual property rights related to (earlier) research, to secure the realisation of research projects where the samples/data were originally collected, to preserve samples, to ensure data protection (e.g. if it is concerned on the applicant's capacity to protect personal data), or for research ethical reasons. An M/DTA is also required.</p>
Data localization and infrastructure requirements	<p>18. What are the rules of transferring health data or human tissues for specific research projects to third parties?</p> <p>Response: From 1.5.2022 data obtained under the Secondary Use Act will be available only to processing environments meeting the requirements in the act and audited by auditors approved by Finnish authorities. Similar requirements may be introduced to the new Biobank Act, this remains to be seen.</p> <p>19. Are there any provisions restricting transfer of health data outside of your country?</p> <p>Response: GDPR applies. Also, from 1.5.2022 onwards the Secondary Use Act will in practice effect international transfers concerning data obtained under it, because the processing environments must be audited against Finnish requirements (the Act + Findata's instructions) by entities approved for that task by Finnish authorities (www.kyberturvallisuuskeskus.fi/en/our-services/assessment-accreditation-and-guidance/accredited-information-security-inspection). This does not necessarily mean that the data must remain in Finland, however the Finnish national requirements must be complied with and systems outside of Finland must be possible to be audited by Finnish companies approved by Finnish authorities.</p> <p>In case of BigPicture project the Finnish government and academia owned company CSC is working on the systems, and they also provide systems to the Secondary Use Act permissions authority Findata, so they are aware of these requirements.</p> <p>Similar requirements may be introduced to the biobanks by the new biobank act, which is in preparation, but the exact content is not known yet.</p>

	<p>20. Are there any specific infrastructure/security requirements for storing health data?</p> <p>Response: See above on the Secondary Use Act requirements. It contains generic requirements, which are not specific to health data in research. Systems used in health care must meet medical device regulations. For public sector (including universities) the requirements in the Act on Information Management in Public Administration apply (www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2019/en20190906.pdf).</p>
<p>Honest broker model</p>	<p>21. Is there a trusted third party service (“honest broker”) established in your jurisdiction, where researcher may submit a request for the data to be pseudonymized before access? If yes, please provide the name of the service, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: Not in general. Registered biobanks are honest brokers of a kind, tasked to maintain sample and data collections to be used in future research. Findata, the permissions authority under the Secondary Use Act can be seen as one as well, providing permissions and access to health and social care data from many data controllers. Findata also may “pre-process” data for the researcher (e.g. pseudonymize or anonymize it).</p> <p>Access to samples and data in the discussed context is legally controlled and permissions are needed. Providing these permissions cannot be freely delegated, so only the entities (biobanks and Findata) recognised in the law can grant access. BIGPICTURE partners or a legal vehicle created by the project would not be such an entity, unless it establishes itself as a biobank registered in Finland. This would most likely be possible, but there are uncertainties related to the pending changes and the new biobank act may affect the feasibility of this option.</p> <p>22. Please describe any restrictions or limitations regarding “honest broker” of health data according to your national law.</p> <p>Response: The general rules apply and don’t really recognise an honest broker (apart from biobanks under the Biobank Act and Findata under the Secondary Use Act). It would seem that the only way Finnish data can be in BIGPICTURE is under a subcontract for processing, with no independent decision making over disclosures or transfer. Another option could be registering as a biobank in Finland (see above).</p>
<p>Contractual limitations / limitation on commercial use of WSIs</p>	<p>23. Are there any mandatory provisions which impose specific terms of use of health data or WSI by researchers? Please include any limitations on commercial use of WSIs. In your response, please provide name of the law and explain the requirements under such provisions.</p> <p>Response: See other answers. Data can be provided for research, but there is no requirement for the researchers to work for academia. Data must be kept confidential and used only as necessary under the approved research plan. Research results must be made public.</p>
<p>Copyrights / database rights / data license requirements</p>	<p>24. Under the laws of your jurisdiction, would the WSI be subject to copyright protection, database rights, any other intellectual property rights? Who would be the holder of such rights?</p> <p>Response: This is debatable, but WSI could be deemed to be protected as photographs under the Finnish Copyright Act (www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/1961/en19610404.pdf). In accordance with Section 49a, the photographer has an exclusive right to control a photographic</p>

	<p>picture whether in the original or an altered form by making copies and by making it available to the public.</p> <p>Further, collections/compilations of WSI and related data could clearly be subject to database or catalogue protections, like any data/information, also personal. In accordance with the Finnish Copyright Act Section 49 “a person who has made</p> <p>1) a catalogue, a table, a programme, or any other work in which a large number of information items are compiled, or</p> <p>2) a database the obtaining, verification, or presentation of which has required substantial investment,</p> <p>shall have the exclusive right to control the whole or, in qualitative or quantitative terms, a substantial part thereof, by making copies of it and by making it available to the public.”</p> <p>The database and catalogue rights do not extend to individual pieces of information separately.</p> <p>There are specific legal rules addressing how patient and biobank data can be and, in some cases, must be shared, so the IPR doesn't seem particularly consequential to BIGPICTURE.</p> <p>25. Are those IP rights transferrable or could a license to use them be granted? If yes, please describe any statutory conditions, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: Yes. Transfer/licensing possibilities are limited by other legislation governing confidential and personal data, i.e. not IP-rules but rules on patient and biobank data, which govern acceptable secondary use purposes, and access requirements and processes.</p>
<p>Removal of commercially sensitive information (trade secrets)</p>	<p>26. Are there any laws (other than GDPR/data protection laws) which would make it mandatory that certain information (e.g. commercial information) is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information must be removed.</p> <p>Response: It is hard to imagine what this could be, but if WSI would hold information that is stipulated to be confidential, like trade secrets, it would be necessary to redact that information.</p> <p>27. Are there any laws which would prohibit that certain information is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information cannot be removed.</p> <p>Response: No.</p> <p>28. Are there any other limitations on the submitter of the WSIs with respect to making them available without information constituting a trade secret of the owner?</p> <p>Response: They can be made available in accordance with the rules explained in the other answers.</p>
<p>Access to public information</p>	<p>29. Which public information laws apply? Please explain how they may impact disclosing of WSI by the foreseen data provider.</p> <p>Response: The <i>lex generalis</i> Act on the Openness of Government Activities applies to public sector operators including the biobank operators contemplated in</p>

	<p>BIGPICTURE, and to some extent also private biobanks. I do not foresee any relevant impact as access to the relevant data is specifically stipulated. (621/1999, www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/1999/en19990621_20150907.pdf; https://oikeusministerio.fi/en/brochure-about-the-act-on-the-openness-of-government-activities).</p> <p>30. Please briefly describe the rules of public information access and possible restrictions and specify to which type of providers they would apply.</p> <p>Response: See above, government and other public entities, including universities, also biobanks, are subject to the general rules on information openness. Health related data is an exception from general freedom of information as it is stipulated to be confidential, but even confidential data can be provided to scientific research projects. There are specific rules on health and social care data, which apply to biobank data and health care providers' data: the Biobank Act will apply to data in biobanks' registers, the Secondary Use Act will apply to data in medical and social care registers.</p>
Requirements for development of AI/ML	<p>31. Are there any restrictions or rules regarding use of health data or WSI in the context of development of artificial intelligence and machine learning systems (AI / ML)?</p> <p>Response: The generic rules, no rules specifically addressing AI/ML. EU's artificial intelligence regulation might be enacted in time to affect BIGPICTURE.</p>
Requirement for contributing slides to BigPicture	<p>32. Assuming that the source of the WSI slides (see Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus) for your jurisdiction will be as provided above, please summarize the requirements, in particular (a) which of the laws are applicable to contributing the WSI, (b) what steps are required to provide them and (c) from a point of view of data protection laws, in which form ("raw", anonymized, pseudonymized) may the WSI be submitted?</p> <p>Response: See all the above answers. The Finnish data is expected to be provided from Helsinki Biobank (part of HUS listed in table 1) and potentially also Auria Biobank, so subject to the Biobank Act. As BIGPICTURE doesn't seem like a medical research project as such, but rather an infrastructure to support many future activities, it doesn't seem possible to provide independent control to BIGPICTURE, but biobanks will make a decision on this if an application is made and a research plan presented (requires also an ethical review). In such case, generally the researcher's application made through this infrastructure to a contributing biobank should be treated as any other application to the biobank, so the researcher would need to fulfil the conditions for access to data. There could be however some room for discretion for the biobank for setting up "fast track" for such applications if they for example were able to be standardised to warrant expedited processing. Moreover, processing could be subcontracted to BIGPICTURE partners as long as the biobank controls access. This is under the assumption that data provider retains control over access to the WSI it contributes.</p> <p>If BIGPICTURE however wanted to have independent control of the Finnish WSIs (e.g. by granting access requests to the researchers), this would seem possible only if the controlling entity/entities registers a biobank in accordance with the Finnish Biobank Act and concludes agreements with the original provider biobanks. This should be further considered by the project partners.</p> <p>If additional data (data not in the biobank register) is required, this can be applied for under the Secondary Use Act. Here the situation is similar, access can be granted for use within a research project, not for onward disclosures. Specific processing environment requirements will start to apply from 1.5.2022.</p>

Notes to the respondents

Background:

- The clinical part of the BIGPICTURE data repository will consist of digital scans of slides of human tissues or biological samples (WSI, whole slide imaging). The original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies. Those studies may have been conducted in the past or are ongoing trials. However, the primary purpose of collection of the slides will be the clinical studies or treatment of patients. Thus, the original slides will not be collected directly and primarily for the purpose of digitization for the BIGPICTURE data repository. We assume that the collection of the original slides was done in line with the requirements applicable to the such purpose.
- BIGPICTURE data repository will also reuse WSI from animal tissues that are also going to be digitized slides from existing collections. The BIGPICTURE repository will only store digital slides (WSI), not the glass originals or biological samples.
- The WSI will be accompanied by metadata (i.e. not only image will be stored). Scope of the metadata may vary, depending on the type of WSI.
- The purpose of storing the WSI is to make them available for scientific and research purposes.
- WSI will not be submitted from public health registries or electronic patient record systems.
- The data submitters will have digital pathology slides or will digitize slides generated as part of clinical diagnostic work that, in some instances, will have also been used in clinical studies. For some submitters, in case duplicate samples to the clinical samples are collected in the biobank of human tissues, DNA/RNA and body fluids, data that have been generated as part of research projects that have used these samples may be used. There may be additionally data from archives. No animal experimentation will be performed for the purpose of data collection in the project.
- Additional patient information may accompany WSI. The list will be provided at a later stage, however before month 6 of the project. Results from genomic investigation may be used as associated data in some WSI collections.

Source of WSI

At the current stage of the project, the following have been confirmed as initial data submitters:

UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT	UMC UTRECHT	Netherlands	Cancer node
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT	RUMC	Netherlands	Cancer node
Azienda Ospedaliera Per L'Emergenza Cannizzaro	AOEC	Italy	Cancer node
Technical University of Munich	TUM	Germany	Cancer node
PHILIPPS UNIVERSITAET MARBURG	UMR	Germany	Clinical trial node
THE LEEDS TEACHING HOSPITALS NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE TRUST	LTHNHS	UK	Liver node
HELSINGIN JA UUDENMAAN SAIRAANHOITOPPIIRIN KUNTAYHTYMÄ	HUS	Finland	Lung node
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT GRAZ	MUG	Austria	Lung node
DECIPHEX	DECIPHEX	Ireland	Non-clinical node
Medical University Vienna	MUW	Austria	Renal node
OSTERGOTLANDS LANS LANDSTING	RO	Sweden	Skin node
Linköping University	LiU	Sweden	Skin node
UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE	Belgium	Skin node

Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus

Instructions:

Please provide responses to the below questions based on the laws of your jurisdiction. Please use the below example as guidance as to the level of required detail. **Please note that the provided responses are for**

exemplary purposes only. The circumstances in your jurisdiction may be different, as well as legal basis and legal steps for contributing WSIs to the BigPicture project.

We are looking for a practical description of issues which may impede or influence the planned collection of WSIs and their sharing with other researchers. If certain matter is regulated by GDPR, please do not explain in detail. Mere reference to GDPR rules is sufficient. If the response to certain questions is not clear under the current legal framework or the approach taken depends on the organization, please indicate this and, if possible, describe the most common approach.

Appendix 4 - Germany Country Report

Responses for Germany

Contributors: Nina Raschke, Carsten Denkert (UMR)

Topic	Questions
National provisions on personal data processing in the context of scientific research	<p>1. Which national laws regulate use and sharing of health (“health data”), including WSIs, for research purposes? Please provide the name of the law, online reference, and relevance for the BigPicture (if not explained in other sections below)</p> <p>Response:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679) - Hessisches Datenschutz- und Informationsfreiheitsgesetz (HDSIG, https://www.rv.hessenrecht.hessen.de/bshe/document/jlr-DSIFGHEV1IVZ)¹ - Hessisches Krankenhausgesetz (https://www.rv.hessenrecht.hessen.de/bshe/document/jlr-KHGHE2011V11P30) - Bundesdatenschutzgesetz (if applicable) (https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bdsg_2018/). <p>There is no law regulating biobanks in Germany.</p> <p>2. Please describe how the databases and registers containing patient’s health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are organized in your jurisdiction and which type of data they contain. If possible, please indicate which databases or registers may be relevant for BigPicture.</p> <p>Response: For BigPicture, there are two types of databases. For samples from clinical trials, the main database is the clinical trial database hosted by the trial sponsor. In addition there is the database of the biosamples and digital images, which is hosted by the academic partner (Institute of Pathology, Philipps University Marburg).</p> <p>For other samples, the main database is the laboratory information system of the Institute of Pathology (Nexus system), that is also used for the diagnostic work of the institute.</p> <p>3. Please describe general conditions on using patient’s health data and WSIs of human biological samples for scientific research purposes.</p> <p>Response: The rules of using patient’s health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are regulated by GDPR, BDSG and HDSIG.</p> <p>There is no specific regulation for WSI. However, it should be noted that WSI represent high-resolution images of a tumor. The use of tumor images for research and education has not been restricted by data protection regulations, images of tumor are widely used in the scientific literature and in teaching activities regardless of informed consent. The reason for this is that it is not possible to</p>

¹ Every federal state in Germany has its own data protection law. But every law is based on the GDPR, so the differences are marginal.

identify the patient from an image of his/her tumor, therefore images represent anonymous information.

If the tumor image is linked to other biological datasets of an individual (e.g. via metadata which are part of additional datasets), more complex regulation are relevant. It is possible to use patients health data and biological samples for research if there is an informed consent of the individual available. This is the case in all samples from clinical trials that will be the main activity of the partner UMR in BIGPICTURE.

Some activities of UMR will use images of diagnostic material outside of clinical trials. If there is no informed consent, the use is possible if the data and samples are anonymous. Otherwise, if there is no informed consent, the use of pseudonymous data is possible if there is a decision from an ethical board that the research interest in the use of the data is more relevant than the interest of the individual patient in data protection. This will be – for example – the case if there is an aggressive tumor type that urgently needs additional research, if it is not possible to contact the patient or if it is likely that the patients did already die from the disease at the time of diagnosis.

4. Is research subject's consent required for scientific research? Would using health data for scientific research purposes be possible, if the data was initially collected for other purpose? If yes, describe any conditions of such use.

Response: In most cases patient's consent is required, see above (3.) for details.

Using patient's data without consent requires a dataset-based examination (see examples above "3."). In this examination, the data protection concept, major interest of research and the patient's protection-worthy interest in the data are being balanced against each other. The researcher's academic freedom must outweigh patient's fundamental right of informational self-determination. If this is the case, the data / material might be used. Specifically for WSIs, if those conditions are fulfilled, the data provider could provide the slides to the project, even if they were collected initially for another purpose.

5. From which generally applicable data protection provisions of GDPR (in particular requirements under Articles 13-21) are scientific researchers exempted and under what conditions?

Response: The rights of the data subject provided for in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 GDPR are limited to the extent that these rights are likely to make the realization of the research or statistical purposes impossible or seriously impair the restriction is necessary for the fulfillment of research or statistical purposes. In addition, the right to information according to Art. 15 GDPR does not exist if the data are necessary for purposes of scientific research and the provision of information would require a disproportionate effort (§ 23 HDSIG).

6. Are there specific provisions which relate to appropriate safeguards, including using or making available anonymous or pseudonymized health data in the context of scientific research?

Response: According to § 24 HDSIG contrary to Art. 9 Paragraph 1 of GDPR, the processing of special categories of personal data is possible for scientific, or historical research purposes or for statistical purposes even without consent, if the processing is necessary for these purposes and the interests of the person responsible in the processing outweigh the interests of the person concerned in an exclusion of the processing. The person responsible provides appropriate and specific measures to safeguard the interests of the data subject in accordance with

	<p>§ 20 (2) HDSIG. Before the start of the research project, a data protection concept must be drawn up, which is to be submitted to the responsible supervisory authority upon request.</p> <p>§ 20 (2) HDSIG states specific measures to safeguard the interests of the data subjects. Such as technical and organizational (t&o) measures to ensure that processing is carried out in accordance to the GDPR; measures to ensure that it can be checked and determined whether and by whom personal data has been entered, changed or removed; raising awareness; encryption; pseudonymization; measures to maintain confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of the systems and services, including the ability to quickly restore availability and access in the event of a physical or technical incident; establishment of a procedure for regular review, assessment and evaluation of the effectiveness of the t&o measures; specific procedures that ensure compliance with the GDPR.</p> <p>In addition to the measures mentioned in § 20 (2), special categories of personal data processed for scientific or historical research purposes or for statistical purposes within the meaning of Art. 9 (1) GDPR must be anonymized as soon as this according to the research or statistical purpose is possible, unless the legitimate interests of the data subject conflict with this. As soon as the research or statistical purpose allows this, the features that can be used to establish a personal reference are to be saved separately; the characteristics are to be deleted as soon as the research or statistical purpose allows this.</p> <p>7. What are the potential consequences of non-compliance with the rules outlined in the questions above?</p> <p>Response: Intentional or negligent violations of the GDPR can result in fines. Compensation can also be paid to the individual for injury and violations of personal integrity caused by any processing contrary to the provisions of the GDPR.</p>
Digitalization of original slides	<p>8. Are there any specific rules regarding digitalization of images of human tissues and biological samples? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Ethical board approvals requirements / biomedical research projects	<p>9. Is there a regime requiring an approval of ethical board or any similar or related conditions prior to making WSIs and sharing them for research purposes? If yes, what does that regime entail? Please refer to any rules of obtaining ethical board approvals for biomedical research projects, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: A full ethical board approval is needed for any prospective clinical trial or research project. This is particularly relevant if there are therapeutic or diagnostic interventions that are not part of the standard patient workup. For WSIs from clinical trials, there are already existing ethical approvals for research projects using data and biomaterials from these trials. For BIGPICTURE, these existing approvals would need an amendment to include WSIs as well as transfer to the repository.</p> <p>For retrospective projects of one single department and use of already existing data (including slides and WSIs) with anonymisation, a simplified ethical board approval is required.</p>

<p>Animal tissues and biological samples (non-clinical WSI)</p>	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI of animal samples may be collected in some jurisdictions.</p> <p>10. Are there any rules that regulate use of WSI of animal samples that have already been produced in another study for scientific research purposes? If yes, please describe.</p> <p>Response: Animal testing must meet requirements of German animal protection laws, e.g. Tierschutzgesetz, Versuchstiermeldeverordnung. Authorization of the supervising authority may be required. (It should be noted that it is not planned to provide animal tissues slides from UMR).</p>
<p>Processing of genetic data</p>	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI metadata may contain genetic information related to the data subject. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>11. How is processing of genetic data regulated? Please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: The processing of genetic data must meet the requirements of GDPR. The German “Gendiagnostikgesetz” (https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/gendg/) includes several restrictions, but it explicitly states that these restrictions are not applicable to research use of genetic data.</p> <p>If this use is included in the informed consent, there are no restrictions for research use. If there is no informed consent, it is expected that genetic information, in particular germline information, will be restricted by the ethical committee. In such case, the genetic information will not be submitted as part of the WSI metadata.</p> <p>12. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained human genetic data? Are there any additional restrictions on making the human genetic data available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: See question 11.</p>
<p>Data on rare diseases / Covid 19</p>	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI may relate rare disease or Covid19 research. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>13. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on rare diseases? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: If the data concerns very rare diseases, this can affect the rules regarding data protection, because in case of such diseases it may be difficult or impossible to de-identify the data to the extent that it is made anonymous. Furthermore the German Infection Protection Act (IfSG, https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/ifsg/) may apply to physical slides of tissues only in very rare situations, e.g. fresh tissue. For FFPE slides used in BigPicture, there are no restrictions. According to the IfSG any person who wishes to import or export pathogens to and from the territory covered by this Act, store, supply or work with them there requires an authorization to do so from the competent authority. These regulations are not relevant for FFPE slides used in BigPicture.</p> <p>This does not apply to WSI, which are just high-resolution images which do not contain infections agents.</p>

	<p>14. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on Covid19? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: See Question 13. There are no special requirements concerning Covid19.</p>
Clinical trials	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that the original slides may have been collected during clinical trials in the meaning of Directive 2001/20/EC².</p> <p>15. Are there any additional restrictions on making the health data collected during clinical trials available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: No, general conditions apply.</p>
Biobanks	<p>When answering the following questions, please consider applicable requirements if the WSI were submitted by a biobank or from a biobank in your jurisdiction.</p> <p>16. How are biobanks regulated in your jurisdiction? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information</p> <p>Response: N/A. There is no law regulating biobanks in Germany. The German standards for biobanking are developed by the German Biobank Node/ the German Biobank Alliance (GBA) (https://www.bbmri.de/about-gbn/who-we-are/?L=1) which provide a central communication platform and is partner in the European Biobanking Network BBMRI-ERIC. The individual universities are not required to follow the recommendations of the GBA, nevertheless these recommendations are regarded as a national standard by most institutions.</p> <p>17. Can health data (including WSI) stored in the biobanks be shared with other parties to be used for scientific research purposes? If yes, what are the conditions of such sharing and use?</p> <p>Response: The transfer of health data to third parties may be lawful, if the requirements of Art. 6 GDPR are met. There is no specific regulation regarding WSI, but considering the fact that WSI are high-resolution images, the transfer should be possible. There might be restrictions regarding associated datasets or metadata.</p>
Data localization and infrastructure requirements	<p>18. What are the rules of transferring health data or human tissues for specific research projects to third parties?</p> <p>Response: See question 1.</p> <p>19. Are there any provisions restricting transfer of health data outside of your country?</p> <p>Response: Transfer of health data outside of Germany is subject to GDPR requirements. Transfer of data outside EU must meet the requirements of Artt. 44-50 GDPR.</p> <p>20. Are there any specific infrastructure/security requirements for storing health data?</p> <p>Response: Not beyond GDPR, which stipulates requirements for storing health data.</p>

² DIRECTIVE 2001/20/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

Honest broker model	<p>21. Is there a trusted third party service (“honest broker”) established in your jurisdiction, where researcher may submit a request for the data to be pseudonymized before access? If yes, please provide the name of the service, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: No.</p> <p>22. Please describe any restrictions or limitations regarding “honest broker” of health data according to your national law.</p> <p>Response: N/A</p>
Contractual limitations / limitation on commercial use of WSIs	<p>23. Are there any mandatory provisions which impose specific terms of use of health data or WSI by researchers? Please include any limitations on commercial use of WSIs. In your response, please provide name of the law and explain the requirements under such provisions.</p> <p>Response: Not specifically applicable to WSI.</p>
Copyrights / database rights / data license requirements	<p>24. Under the laws of your jurisdiction, would the WSI be subject to copyright protection, database rights, any other intellectual property rights? Who would be the holder of such rights?</p> <p>Response: Only the author’s own intellectual creations constitute works within the meaning of Act on Copyright and Related Rights (Urheberrechtsgesetz UrhG; https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_urhg/englisch_urhg.html#p0018).</p> <p>There are no specific regulations for WSIs, but it could be argued that a WSI is a high resolution image/picture. Typically, the ownership of an histological image lies with the person that has created this image, which would be the pathologist / the university. The pathologist is only allowed to publish this image if the patient cannot be identified from the image (which is true for histological tumor images). The pathologist / hospital can provide the rights to use this image to the BIGPICTURE repository.</p> <p>Collections of works, data or other independent elements which by reason of the selection or arrangement of the elements constitute the author’s own intellectual creation (collections) are protected as independent works without prejudice to an existing copyright or related right in one of the individual elements. A database work within the meaning of UrhG is a collection whose elements are arranged systematically or methodically and the individual elements are individually accessible by electronic or other means. A computer program (section 69a UrhG) used in the creation of the database work or to provide access to its elements does not constitute an integral part of the database work.</p> <p>25. Are those IP rights transferrable or could a license to use them be granted? If yes, please describe any statutory conditions, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: The author may grant a right to another to use the work in a particular manner or in any manner (right of use). A right of use may be granted as a non-exclusive right or as an exclusive right, and may be limited in respect of place, time or content. Since the pathologist has created the WSI as part of his/her research work at the university, the institution will be able to provide this authorization.</p>
Removal of commercially sensitive	<p>26. Are there any laws (other than GDPR/data protection laws) which would make it mandatory that certain information (e.g. commercial information)</p>

information (trade secrets)	<p>is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information must be removed.</p> <p>Response: No, however if certain information contained in the WSI or its metadata would constitute a trade secret of the data submitter, this submitter may choose to remove it.</p> <p>27. Are there any laws which would prohibit that certain information is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information cannot be removed.</p> <p>Response: No.</p> <p>28. Are there any other limitations on the submitter of the WSIs with respect to making them available without information constituting a trade secret of the owner?</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Access to public information	<p>29. Which public information laws apply? Please explain how they may impact disclosing of WSI by the foreseen data provider.</p> <p>Response: The principle of public access to information is a fundamental principle in Germany. One of the fundamental laws, the Freedom of the Press Act, contains provisions on the right to access official documents, which is a manifestation of the principle of public access to information. There are, however, provisions on secrecy that restrict the right to access official documents (https://www.rv.hessenrecht.hessen.de/bshe/document/jlr-PressGHEV7P10).</p> <p>Another law is Federal Act Governing Access to Information held by the Federal Government (Freedom of Information Act; https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_ifg/englisch_ifg.html). Everyone is entitled to official information from the authorities of the Federal Government in accordance with the provisions of this Act.</p> <p>Everyone who's data is processed within Hesse is entitled to official information from the authorities of the State Government of Hesse in accordance with the HDSIG (§§ 80 ff.HDSIG) There are situations in which only the data categories are disclosed and situation in which the data itself is disclosed, the current state of jurisdiction is not completely clear in which situations the data itself must be disclosed. Nevertheless, from a practical point of view, it will not be a problem to disclose the WSI (which is just a high resolution image) to the patient upon request.</p> <p>30. Please briefly describe the rules of public information access and possible restrictions and specify to which type of providers they would apply.</p> <p>Response: The rules of Access to Information (HDSIG) apply to universities and university hospitals insofar as they do not operate in the field of research and teaching.</p>
Requirements for development of AI/ML	<p>31. Are there any restrictions or rules regarding use of health data or WSI in the context of development of artificial intelligence and machine learning systems (AI / ML)?</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Requirement for contributing slides to BigPicture	<p>32. Assuming that the source of the WSI slides (see Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus) for your jurisdiction will be as provided above, please summarize the requirements, in particular (a) which of the laws are applicable to contributing the WSI, (b) what steps are required to provide</p>

	<p>them and (c) from a point of view of data protection laws, in which form (“raw”, anonymized, pseudonymized) may the WSI be submitted?</p> <p>Response: This test is identical to the response to question 3.</p> <p>The rules of using patient’s health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are regulated by GDPR, BDSG and HDSIG.</p> <p>There is no specific regulation for WSI. However, it should be noted that WSI represent high-resolution images of a tumor. The use of tumor images for research and education has not been restricted by data protection regulations, images of tumor are widely used in the scientific literature and in teaching activities regardless of informed consent. The reason for this is that it is not possible to identify the patient from an image of his/her tumor, therefore images represent anonymous information.</p> <p>If the tumor image is linked to other biological datasets (e.g. via metadata), more complex regulations are relevant:</p> <p>It is possible to use patients health data and biological samples for research if there is an informed consent available, this is the case in all samples from clinical trials that will be the main activity of the partner UMR in BIGPICTURE.</p> <p>Some activities of UMR will use images of diagnostic material outside of clinical trials. If there is no informed consent, the use is possible if the data and samples are anonymous (for example WSIs linked to very general data categories).</p> <p>Otherwise, if there is no informed consent, the use of pseudonymous data is possible if there is a decision from an ethical board that the research interest in the use of the data is more relevant than the interest of the individual patient in data protection. This will be – for example – the case if there is an aggressive tumor type that urgently needs additional research and for which is not possible to contact the patients (for example if it is likely that the patients did already die from the disease) before the research project is conducted.</p>
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Notes to the respondents

Background:

- The clinical part of the BIGPICTURE data repository will consist of digital scans of slides of human tissues or biological samples (WSI, whole slide imaging). The original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies. Those studies may have been conducted in the past or are ongoing trials. However, the primary purpose of collection of the slides will be the clinical studies or treatment of patients. Thus, the original slides will not be collected directly and primarily for the purpose of digitization for the BIGPICTURE data repository. We assume that the collection of the original slides was done in line with the requirements applicable to the such purpose.
- BIGPICTURE data repository will also reuse WSI from animal tissues that are also going to be digitized slides from existing collections. The BIGPICTURE repository will only store digital slides (WSI), not the glass originals or biological samples.
- The WSI will be accompanied by metadata (i.e. not only image will be stored). Scope of the metadata may vary, depending on the type of WSI.
- The purpose of storing the WSI is to make them available for scientific and research purposes.
- WSI will not be submitted from public health registries or electronic patient record systems.
- The data submitters will have digital pathology slides or will digitize slides generated as part of clinical diagnostic work that, in some instances, will have also been used in clinical studies. For some submitters, in case duplicate samples to the clinical samples are collected in the biobank of human tissues, DNA/RNA and body fluids, data that have been generated as part of research projects that have used these samples may be used. There may be additionally data from archives. No animal experimentation will be performed for the purpose of data collection in the project.
- Additional patient information may accompany WSI. The list will be provided at a later stage, however before month 6 of the project. Results from genomic investigation may be used as associated data in some WSI collections.

Source of WSI

At the current stage of the project, the following have been confirmed as initial data submitters:

UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT	UMC UTRECHT	Netherlands	Cancer node
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT	RUMC	Netherlands	Cancer node
Azienda Ospedaliera Per L'Emergenza Cannizzaro	AOEC	Italy	Cancer node
Technical University of Munich	TUM	Germany	Cancer node
PHILIPPS UNIVERSITAET MARBURG	UMR	Germany	Clinical trial node
THE LEEDS TEACHING HOSPITALS NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE TRUST	LTHTNHS	UK	Liver node
HELSINGIN JA UUDENMAAN SAIRAANHOITOPIIRIN KUNTAYHTYMÄ	HUS	Finland	Lung node
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT GRAZ	MUG	Austria	Lung node
DECIPHEX	DECIPHEX	Ireland	Non-clinical node
Medical University Vienna	MUW	Austria	Renal node
OSTERGOTLANDS LANS LANDSTING	RO	Sweden	Skin node
Linköping University	LiU	Sweden	Skin node
UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE	Belgium	Skin node

Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus

Instructions:

Please provide responses to the below questions based on the laws of your jurisdiction. Please use the below example as guidance as to the level of required detail. **Please note that the provided responses are for exemplary purposes only. The circumstances in your jurisdiction may be different, as well as legal basis and legal steps for contributing WSIs to the BigPicture project.**

We are looking for a practical description of issues which may impede or influence the planned collection of WSIs and their sharing with other researchers. If certain matter is regulated by GDPR, please do not explain in detail. Mere reference to GDPR rules is sufficient. If the response to certain questions is not clear under the current legal framework or the approach taken depends on the organization, please indicate this and, if possible, describe the most common approach.

Appendix 5 - Italy Country Report

Responses for Italy

Contributor: Matteo Macilotti, Marialuisa Lavitrano, University of Milan (UNIMIB)

Topic	Questions
National provisions on personal data processing in the context of scientific research	<p>1. Which national laws regulate use and sharing of health (“health data”), including WSIs, for research purposes? Please provide the name of the law, online reference, and relevance for the BigPicture (if not explained in other sections below)</p> <p>Response: Italian Personal data protection code, D.Lgs. 196/2003 as modified by D.Lgs. 101/2018 (https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2003-06-30;196!vig=). This law adapts the Italian legal system to the GDPR.</p> <p>2. Please describe how the databases and registers containing patient’s health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are organized in your jurisdiction and which type of data they contain. If possible, please indicate which databases or registers may be relevant for BigPicture.</p> <p>Response: Patient data databases and registers are distributed in public hospitals, private hospitals, universities and research centres. There is no central database and there is no national standard format for data collection. Responsibility for registers and databases rests with the manager of each of these entities. In general, the competence on health is regional. Each of the 20 Italian regions organizes its own collection system and its IT system.</p> <p>3. Please describe general conditions on using patient’s health data and WSIs of human biological samples for scientific research purposes.</p> <p>Response: Prior informed consent of the patient is the general legal basis for research on health data and samples.</p> <p>The art. 110 of the D.Lgs 196/2003 (Personal data protection code) provides exceptions to the consent rule.</p> <p>The consent of data subject for the processing of health data for scientific research purposes in the medical, biomedical or epidemiological, it is <u>not</u> necessary when the research is carried out in based on provisions of law or regulation or law of the European Union in accordance with Article 9, paragraph 2, letter j) of the GDPR. This includes the case in which the research is part of a biomedical or health research program envisaged under pursuant to article 12-bis of the legislative decree of 30 December 1992, n. 502 (Italian National Plan of Research), and an impact assessment is conducted and made public pursuant to articles 35 and 36 of the GDPR.</p> <p>Consent is also not necessary when, due to particular reasons, it is impossible to inform the data subjects or informing them would involve a disproportionate effort, or threaten to make the research impossible or seriously affect the achievement of the purposes of the research.</p> <p>In such cases, data controller must take appropriate measures to protect the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of the interested party. Moreover the research program is subject to motivated favourable opinion of the competent Ethics Committee at the territorial level and must be subjected to <u>prior consultation</u> of the Italian Privacy Authority in connection with Article 36 of the GDPR.</p>

The §5 of the Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority (Garante) n. 146, 5 June 2019, governs the case in which it is not possible to obtain consent providing further clarifications to the above mentioned rule of art. 110 of Lgs 196/2003:

“When it is not possible to obtain the consent of the interested parties, the data controllers must document, in the research project, the existence of the reasons, considered entirely particular or exceptional, for which informing the interested parties is impossible or involves a disproportionate effort, or risks to make it impossible or seriously jeopardize the achievement of the purposes of the research, including in particular:

1. the ethical reasons due to the fact that the interested party ignores his condition. This category includes research for which the information on the processing of data to be made to the interested parties would involve the revelation of information concerning the conduct of the study, the knowledge of which could cause material or psychological damage to the interested parties (they can fall under this hypothesis, for example, epidemiological studies on the distribution of a factor that predicts or can predict the development of a disease state for which there is no treatment);

2. the reasons for organizational impossibility due to the circumstance that the failure to consider the data referring to the estimated number of interested parties who cannot be contacted to inform them, compared to the total number of subjects intended to be involved in the research, would produce significant consequences for the study in terms of alteration of the relative results; this having regard, in particular, to the inclusion criteria provided for by the study, the methods of recruitment, the statistical number of the chosen sample, as well as the period of time elapsed from the moment in which the data relating to the interested parties were originally collected (for example, in cases where the study concerns individuals with pathologies with a high incidence of mortality or in the terminal phase of the disease or in old age and in serious health conditions).

With regard to these reasons of organizational impossibility, the following provisions also concern the processing of the data of those who, after making every reasonable effort to contact them (also through the verification of their status in life, the consultation of the data reported in the clinical documentation, the use of any telephone numbers provided, as well as the acquisition of contact data at the registry office of the patients or the resident population) appear to be at the time of enrolment in the study: (a) deceased or (b) not contactable.

The obligation to disclose information to the interested parties included in the research remains unaffected in all cases in which, during the course of the study, this is possible and, in particular, where they contact the treatment center, including for check-ups, also in order to allow them to exercise the rights provided for by the Regulation;

3. health reasons due to the seriousness of the clinical state in which the interested party is, due to which he is unable to understand the information provided in the information and to validly give consent.

In such cases, the study must be aimed at improving the same clinical state in which the person concerned is. Furthermore, it is necessary to prove that the purposes of the study cannot be achieved through the processing of data relating to persons able to understand the information provided in the information and to validly give consent or with other research methods. This, having regard, in particular, to the inclusion criteria provided for by the study, the methods of enrolment, the statistical number of the selected sample, as well as the reliability of the results that can be achieved in relation to the specific purposes of the study. With reference to these reasons, it is necessary to obtain the consent of the persons

indicated in art. 82, paragraph 2, lett. a), of the Code as amended by Legislative Decree no. 101/2018. This, it being understood that the information on the processing of data is provided to the interested party as soon as the health conditions allow it, also for the purpose of exercising the rights provided for by the Regulations.

4. Is research subject's consent required for scientific research? Would using health data for scientific research purposes be possible, if the data was initially collected for other purpose? If yes, describe any conditions of such use.

Response: Yes, the consent is required. It's is possible to use health data initially collected for other purposes with the explicit consent of the person. If it is not possible, authorization for further processing must be obtained from Italian Privacy Authority in accordance with art. 110 bis of D.Lgs 196/2003. This article establishes that the Italian Privacy Authority can authorize the further processing of personal data, including those of special treatments referred to in Article 9 of the GDPR, for scientific research purposes or for statistical purposes of the third parties who mainly carry out these activities when, due to particular reasons, informing the interested subjects is impossible or involves a disproportionate effort, or risks making the research impossible or seriously affects the achievement of the research purposes. This is on the condition that the researchers have taken appropriate measures to protect the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of the data subjects, in accordance with article 89 of the GDPR including preventive forms of minimization and data anonymization¹.

The Italian Privacy Authority (Garante) communicates the decision taken on the request for authorization within forty-five days, after which the failure to pronounce is equivalent to rejection. With the provision of authorization or even subsequently, on the basis of any checks, the Garante may establish the necessary conditions and measures to ensure adequate guarantees to protect the interested individuals as part of the further processing of their personal data by third parties, also in terms of its safety.

5. From which generally applicable data protection provisions of GDPR (in particular requirements under Articles 13-21) are scientific researchers exempted and under what conditions?

Response: There is no exemption.

6. Are there specific provisions which relate to appropriate safeguards, including using or making available anonymous or pseudonymized health data in the context of scientific research?

Response: Yes, they are provided in § 5.4 of the Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority (Garante) n. 146, 5 June, 2019.

According to it, where the research cannot achieve its purposes without the identification, even temporary, of the interested individuals , in the processing following the retrospective collection of data, encryption or pseudonymisation techniques or other solutions must be adopted which, considering the volume of data processed, the nature, the object, the context and the purposes of the processing, will make the individuals not directly identifiable to the researchers. Those solutions should allow individuals to be identified only in case of need.

In these cases, the codes used cannot be inferred from the personal identification data of the concerned individuals, unless this will be impossible due to the

¹ Please note that art. 110bis speaks of „form of anonymization”. Pseudonymisation is also included with this expression, because is a form of anonymization.

	<p>particular characteristics of the processing or a manifestly disproportionate use of means is required and this is also justified in writing, in the research proposal.</p> <p>The combination of the research material with the identification data of the concerned data subject, as long as it is temporary and essential for the result of the research, must also be justified in writing.</p> <p>In application of the principle of minimization (as mentioned in Article 5, paragraph 1, letter c) GDPR),, the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes in the medical, biomedical or epidemiological field may concern data relating to the health of the data subjects and, only where this is indispensable for achieving the purposes of the research. This applies also to the data relating to sexual life or sexual orientation, as well as to racial and ethnic origin.</p> <p>7. What are the potential consequences of non-compliance with the rules outlined in the questions above?</p> <p>Response: Sanction pursuant to art. 83. c. 4 GDPR: will apply to the one who does not carry out the impact assessment referred to in article 110, paragraph 1, first sentence of the Italian personal data protection code, or does not submit the research program to prior consultation with the Privacy Authority in accordance with the third period of the aforementioned article 110, paragraph 1.</p> <p>Sanction pursuant to art. 83. C. 5 GDPR will apply to the violation of the obligations established by art. 110 bis of the Italian personal data protection code.</p>
Digitalization of original slides	<p>8. Are there any specific rules regarding digitalization of images of human tissues and biological samples? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: No, there is not.</p>
Ethical board approvals requirements / biomedical research projects	<p>9. Is there a regime requiring an approval of ethical board or any similar or related conditions prior to making WSIs and sharing them for research purposes? If yes, what does that regime entail? Please refer to any rules of obtaining ethical board approvals for biomedical research projects, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: There is not a specific rule for the WSI. The rules mentioned above are applied: GDPR, – Italian Personal data protection code D.Lgs. 196 del 2003 and Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority, n. 146, June 5, 2019 (see question 6).</p> <p>All medical research projects require ethics committee approval. Specific rules for ethics committees are provided for in Articles 110 / 110bis Legislative Decree 196/2003 when it is not possible to obtain the consent of patients. There are no specific rules on how the approval is obtained.</p> <p>In the context of BigPicture, it would be possible that the ethics approval allows the data provider to provide the WSI to the repository to be shared in the future with other (unspecified) researchers via the BigPicture infrastructure. Clearly, this characteristic must be declared in the research project.</p>
Animal tissues and biological samples (non-clinical WSI)	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI of animal samples may be collected in some jurisdictions.</p> <p>10. Are there any rules that regulate use of WSI of animal samples that have already been produced in another study for scientific research purposes? If yes, please describe.</p> <p>Response: In Italy, the use of animals for scientific purposes is regulated by Legislative Decree no. 26 which implemented Directive no. 2010/63 / EU. There are not specific rules the regulated use of WSI of animal samples.</p>

Processing of genetic data	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI metadata may contain genetic information related to the data subject. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>11. How is processing of genetic data regulated? Please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Art. 2 septies, D.Lgs. 196/2003 (https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2003-06-30;196!vig=) - Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority, n. 146,, 2019 (https://www.garanteprivacy.it/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/9068972). <p>The § 4.2 of the Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority provides that:</p> <p>In any case, the following precautions are adopted for the custody and safety of genetic data and biological samples:</p> <p>a) access to the premises must take place according to a documented procedure established by the data controller, which provides for the identification of persons, previously authorized, who access for any reason after closing time. These checks can also be carried out with electronic tools. The use of biometric data is allowed with regard to the aforementioned physical access procedures, in compliance with the principles on the protection of personal data and the specific processing requirements referred to in art. 9 of the GDPR;</p> <p>b) the conservation, use and transport of biological samples are put in place in ways also aimed at ensuring their quality, integrity, availability and traceability;</p> <p>c) the transfer of genetic data, with electronic messaging systems including mail, is carried out with the following precautions: transmission of the data in the form of an attachment and not as a text included in the body of the message; data encryption taking care to make the cryptographic key known to the recipient through communication channels other than those used for data transmission; use of protected communication channels, taking into account the state of the art of the technology used; protection of the attachment in ways suitable to prevent the unlawful or accidental acquisition of the transmitted data, such as a password for opening the file made known to the recipient through communication channels other than those used for data transmission. The use of "web application" communication channels is allowed which envisage the use of protected transmission channels, taking into account the state of the art of technology, and guarantee, after verification, the digital identity of the server that delivers the service and the client station from which the data is accessed, using digital certificates issued in compliance with the law by a certification authority;</p> <p>d) the consultation of genetic data processed with electronic tools is permitted subject to the adoption of authentication systems based on the combined use of information known to the persons designated for the purpose and devices, including biometric, in their possession;</p> <p>e) the genetic data and biological samples contained in lists, registers or databases are processed with encryption or pseudonymisation techniques or other solutions which, considering the volume of data and samples processed, make them temporarily unintelligible even to those who is authorized to access it and allow the data subjects to be identified only in case of need, in order to minimize the risks of accidental knowledge and unauthorized or unauthorized access. Where the lists, registers or databases are kept with electronic tools and also contain data</p>
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	<p>concerning the genealogy or the state of health of the interested parties, the aforementioned techniques must also allow the separate processing of genetic and health data from other data. personal data that allow the persons concerned to be directly identified.</p> <p>The § 4.11 of the Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority provides that:</p> <p>The processing of genetic data and biological samples for scientific and statistical research purposes is permitted only if aimed at protecting the health of the data subject, third parties or the community in the medical, biomedical and epidemiological fields, including in the context of clinical trials or scientific research aimed at developing genetic analysis techniques.</p> <p>The processing must be carried out on the basis of a project drawn up in accordance with the standards of the relevant disciplinary sector, also in order to document that the processing of data and the use of biological samples is carried out for suitable and effective scientific purposes.</p> <p>The project documentation specifies the measures to be adopted in the processing of personal data to ensure compliance with this provision, as well as with the legislation on the protection of personal data. It also specifies the measures adopted concerning the custody and security of data and biological samples, and identifies any data processors (Article 28 of EU Regulation 2016/679). In particular, where the research involves the collection and / or use of biological samples, the project documentation indicates the origin, nature and methods of taking and storing the samples, as well as the measures adopted to ensure the voluntary nature of the provision of the biological material by the interested party.</p> <p>The project findings must be kept confidential (since it is possible to consult the project for the sole purpose of applying the legislation on the protection of personal data) for five years from the scheduled conclusion of the research.</p> <p>When the purposes of the research can be achieved only through the identification, even temporary, of the data subjects, the data controller adopts specific measures to keep the identification data separate from the biological samples and genetic information already at the time of collection, unless this is impossible due to the particular characteristics of the processing or requires a manifestly disproportionate use of means.</p> <p>12. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained human genetic data? Are there any additional restrictions on making the human genetic data available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: No there are not.</p>
Data on rare diseases / Covid 19	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI may relate rare disease or Covid19 research. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>13. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on rare diseases? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: No there are not.</p> <p>14. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on Covid19? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: Yes, please see:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EDPB Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak - Art. 40 D.L. April 8 2020, n. 23 - FAQ Data processing in clinical trials and medical research in the context of the COVID-19 health emergency (https://www.garanteprivacy.it/temi/coronavirus/faq#clinicaltrials)
Clinical trials	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that the original slides may have been collected during clinical trials in the meaning of Directive 2001/20/EC².</p> <p>15. Are there any additional restrictions on making the health data collected during clinical trials available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: No, there are not.</p>
Biobanks	<p>When answering the following questions, please consider applicable requirements if the WSI were submitted by a biobank or from a biobank in your jurisdiction.</p> <p>16. How are biobanks regulated in your jurisdiction? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information</p> <p>Response: There is not a specific law for biobanks.</p> <p>17. Can health data (including WSI) stored in the biobanks be shared with other parties to be used for scientific research purposes? If yes, what are the conditions of such sharing and use?</p> <p>Response: Yes, it is possible. Health data must be pseudonymized before being shared. The transfer must take place using technological tools that prevent unauthorized persons from reading it. The research project in which the data is to be used must be included in the informed consent given by the patient. If it is not included, a new consent must be obtained.</p>
Data localization and infrastructure requirements	<p>18. What are the rules of transferring health data or human tissues for specific research projects to third parties?</p> <p>Response: The art. 4.11.4 of the Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority, 21 December, 2018 establishes that:</p> <p>Genetic data and biological samples collected for scientific and statistical research purposes can be communicated or transferred to research bodies and institutes, associations and other public and private bodies for research purposes, exclusively in the context of joint projects.</p> <p>Genetic data and biological samples collected for scientific and statistical research purposes may be communicated or transferred to the bodies indicated above, not participating in joint projects, limited to information without identifying data, for scientific purposes directly linked to those for which they were originally collected and clearly determined in writing in the request for data and / or samples. In this case, the requesting bodies undertakes not to process the data and / or use the samples for purposes other than those indicated in the request and not to communicate them or further transfer them to third parties.</p> <p>Given the above rules as well as conditions mentioned above, in the context of BigPicture, the WSIs (digital slides possibly containing genetic metadata) contributed by the data submitters could be made available to other researchers on request submitted via the BigPicture infrastructure only if the data would not be identifiable from the perspective of the researchers.</p>

² DIRECTIVE 2001/20/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

19. Are there any provisions restricting transfer of health data outside of your country?

Response: The transfer of personal data outside of the country is regulated by Articles 45 and 46 of the GDPR. There are no other restrictions.

20. Are there any specific infrastructure/security requirements for storing health data?

Response: Art. 5.6 of the Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority, 21 December, 2018 establishes that:

The data and biological samples used for carrying out the research are stored using encryption techniques or the use of identification codes or other solutions which, given the number of data and samples stored, do not make them directly attributable to the interested individuals, for a period of time not exceeding that necessary for the purposes for which they were collected or subsequently processed.

To this end, the retention period following the conclusion of the study is indicated in the research project, at the end of which the aforementioned data and samples are anonymised.

Art. 5.7 of the Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority, 21 December, 2018 establishes that:

Data controller must adopt specific organizational and technical measures to increase the level of security of the data processed for the execution of the study.

These measures concern both data storage or archiving phase (and, possibly, the collection and storage of biological samples), and the subsequent phase of processing the same information, as well as the subsequent phase of data transmission to the researcher or to external subjects that are parts of the project. In particular, the following measures are adopted:

a. adequate measures to guarantee the quality of the data and the correct attribution to the interested individuals;

b. suitable measures to guarantee the protection of the controller's data from the risks of unauthorized access to data, theft or partial or complete loss of storage media or portable or fixed processing systems (for example, through the partial or full application of cryptographic technologies to file systems or databases, or through the adoption of other measures that make the data unintelligible to unauthorized subjects) in data recording and archiving operations;

c. protected transmission channels, taking into account the state of the art of technology, in cases where it is necessary to communicate the data collected as part of the study to a centralized database where they are stored and archived or to a promoter or external subjects of which the same researcher uses for the conduct of the study. Where said transmission is carried out using optical media (CD-ROM), a specific person in charge of reception at the researcher is designated and a transmission channel different from that used for the transmission of the content is used for the sharing of the data encryption key;

d. labelling techniques, in the conservation and transmission of biological samples, by means of identification codes, or other solutions which, considering the number of samples used, make them not directly attributable to the interested individuals, allowing them to be identified only in case of need.

Honest broker model	<p>21. Is there a trusted third party service (“honest broker”) established in your jurisdiction, where researcher may submit a request for the data to be pseudonymized before access? If yes, please provide the name of the service, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: No, there is not.</p> <p>22. Please describe any restrictions or limitations regarding “honest broker” of health data according to your national law.</p> <p>Response: N/A</p>
Contractual limitations / limitation on commercial use of WSIs	<p>23. Are there any mandatory provisions which impose specific terms of use of health data or WSI by researchers? Please include any limitations on commercial use of WSIs. In your response, please provide name of the law and explain the requirements under such provisions.</p> <p>Response: No, there are not. The relevant provisions are described in the previous questions.</p>
Copyrights / database rights / data license requirements	<p>24. Under the laws of your jurisdiction, would the WSI be subject to copyright protection, database rights, any other intellectual property rights? Who would be the holder of such rights?</p> <p>Response: In the Italian jurisdiction the copyright is regulated by Law 22.04.1941 n. 633.</p> <p>The databases are protected by the Copyright Law - modified by Legislative Decree 6 May 1999, n. 169 implementing Directive 96/9 / EC relating to the legal protection of databases - both as works of creativity of a creative nature resulting from the intellectual work of man, and as an asset (devoid of the character of creativity) produced thanks to significant investments in terms of money, time or work (“sui generis right”).</p> <p>In the first case there will be copyright protection and the creator of the collection is the owner of all the exclusive faculties pursuant to law 633/41 (copyright law); in the second case, however, the creator of the database will be recognized, only in the territory of the European Union, “sui generis right” aimed at protecting the work done and the investments made.</p> <p>The art. 2 n. 9 Copyright Law defines databases as "collections of works, or other independent elements systematically or methodically arranged and individually accessible by electronic or other means".</p> <p>The content of a database, therefore, can consist of a collection of works or a set of data such as, for example, the name and telephone number of all the resident citizens of a certain city - in this case the data inserted must not violate the privacy of the citizens themselves. The article also specifies that the material collected and organized systematically and methodically can be consulted in any way, making both electronic and paper collections fall into the category.</p> <p>Creativity, an indispensable requirement for all the works of art, must characterize the criteria for choosing and arranging the material included in the collection (art.1, paragraph 2, Copyright Law), investing in the form of compilation and not its content, on which other subjects could legitimately claim rights.</p> <p>The author of a database, who has chosen and creatively organized the material within the collection, is the holder of the exclusive rights of a economic and moral nature recognized to all the authors of intellectual works, classified in general in</p>

the Chapter III of Title I, and specific to articles 64-quinquies and sixty Copyright Law (Section VII, Chapter IV, Title I), where particular rules are dictated to the rights of economic use of databases.

In particular, a provision of art. 64-quinquies Copyright Law the author can make or authorize:

- a) permanent or temporary, total or partial reproduction by any means and in any form;
- b) the translation - if the content of the collection is in the public domain - the changes, adaptations and different provisions of the material that affect the choice and arrangement of the material - in this way a new work is created of data;
- c) the distribution, i.e. the placing on the market or available to the public of the original or copies of the database. According to the principle of exhaustion of the right (expressly referred to in the text), the first legitimate sale of a copy on the territory of the European Community exhausts the right to authorize subsequent sales in the same territory;
- d) presentation, demonstration or communication in public, including transmission by any means and in any form;
- e) the economic use of the results of the operations referred to in lett. B).

In the following art. 64-sexies, paragraph 1, Copyright Law are the hypotheses of free use of a database, namely:

- a) access and consultation - not, however, reproduction - carried out for educational or scientific research purposes;
- b) use for public security purposes or in the context of an administrative or judicial procedure.

Furthermore, paragraph 2 - mandatory rule - limits the rights of the author referred to in art. 64-quinquies of the Copyright Law in favour of the legitimate user of a database establishing that the activities referred to in art. 64-quinquies Copyright Law they are free if necessary for access to the contents of the collection and for its normal use.

The rights and relative exceptions set out above are those that the law recognizes to the author of a database that is creative in the choice and arrangement of the material contained therein.

The "sui generis" right

Furthermore, the case in which the final result of this activity is not a creative work, but a legally relevant asset to be protected due to the large financial investments, time or work, is also regulated.

The person who makes these investments aimed at creating a database is defined by the law as the database maker (Article 102-bis, paragraph 1 letter a) Copyright Law), and is the holder of a sui generis right: the database maker of a database citizen or habitual resident on the territory of the European Union, can "prohibit the extraction operations or reuse of all or a substantial part of it", without prejudice, of course, to the rights already existing on the content of the collection or parts of it " (Article 102-bis, paragraph 3, Copyright Law).

Furthermore, the extraction and reuse of insubstantial parts of the database carried out in a systematic and repeated manner "are not allowed if they presuppose operations contrary to the normal management of the database or cause unjustified prejudice to the creator of the database" (art. 102- bis, paragraph 9, Copyright Law).

	<p>The duration of the database maker’s right is 15 years, renewable in the event of substantial changes or additions made to the collection, starting from 1 January of the year following the date of completion or from 1 January of the year following the date of the first making available to the public, if this took place before the expiry of 15 years from completion (art. 102-bis, paragraphs 6 and 7, Copyright Law).</p> <p>Furthermore, according to the EU principle of exhaustion, the first legitimate sale of a copy of a database in the EU territory, exhausts the "right to control the resale of the copy in the territory of the European Union" (art. 102-bis, paragraph 2, Copyright Law) .</p> <p>Art. 102-ter Copyright Law specifies the obligations and rights of the user, licensee and non-assignee of the right to use a database made available to the public. In particular, he must not cause prejudice to the owner of the copyright or related rights on the content and must not perform operations in contrast with the management of the database or that cause unjustified prejudice to the database maker. Instead, the user can carry out the extraction or reuse of non-substantial parts of the content for any purpose.</p> <p>Finally, the violation of the above rules may constitute a crime described in art. 171-bis, paragraph 1-bis, Copyright Law.</p> <p>In summary, in the context of BigPicture project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collection of WSI may be a database protected under one of the basis mentioned above; - If the hospital was the “maker” of the WSI database, it would be entitled to the “sui generis right” to this database and would be able to grant licenses to use these WSI in the research projects. <p>25. Are those IP rights transferrable or could a license to use them be granted? If yes, please describe any statutory conditions, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: Yes, a license can be granted to use them and it is possible to transfer a database. There are not particular statutory conditions. It is a contract that must respect the general rules on contracts.</p> <p>There are particular restrictions if the database contains personal data, namely the GDPR and the Italian law that transposes the GDPR (Legislative Decree 196/2003). The transfer of the database to the purchaser is admissible if the transferor has informed the data subjects and acquired a specific consent to the transfer. This consent must be separated from the others, with a clear indication of the categories (economic or commodity, e.g. finance, publishing) of the party to whom the data is transferred. The purchaser must, therefore, release the privacy policy to the interested individuals before processing the data (e.g. sending commercial communications). The origin of the data must also be specified in this information, so that interested individuals can also contact the transferring company to exercise their rights.</p>
Removal of commercially sensitive information (trade secrets)	<p>26. Are there any laws (other than GDPR/data protection laws) which would make it mandatory that certain information (e.g. commercial information) is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information must be removed.</p> <p>Response: The only hypothesis in which the deletion of data could be requested is in the case of personal data. This is when there is no consent of the person to whom</p>

	<p>the data refers to the use or to the transfer of the data. The privacy law mentioned above regulates these assumptions.</p> <p>27. Are there any laws which would prohibit that certain information is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information cannot be removed.</p> <p>Response: No, there are not. For the avoidance of doubt, if the submitter of the WSI removed some metadata from them to protect its trade secrets (for e.g. on the compound used during the research in which the slide was obtained), this would not be contrary to the Italian law.</p> <p>28. Are there any other limitations on the submitter of the WSIs with respect to making them available without information constituting a trade secret of the owner?</p> <p>Response: No, there are not.</p>
Access to public information	<p>29. Which public information laws apply? Please explain how they may impact disclosing of WSI by the foreseen data provider.</p> <p>Response: The access to public information is regulated by the D.Lgs. n. 33, 14 March 2013, as modified by the D.Lgs. n. 97, 25 May 2016, (which implemented the Freedom of Information Act – FOIA -). However, this legislation does not add any restrictions or conditions apply to making the WSI available to the BigPicture.</p> <p>30. Please briefly describe the rules of public information access and possible restrictions and specify to which type of providers they would apply.</p> <p>Response: The law on access to public information applies when the provider is a public institution. This law introduces the generalized civic access.</p> <p>Generalized civic access guarantees anyone the right to access data and documents owned by public administrations, if there is no danger of compromising other relevant public or private interests, indicated by law (e.g. protection of personal data).</p> <p>With the FOIA legislation, the Italian legal system recognizes the freedom to access information held by public administrations as a fundamental right. The principle that guides the entire legislation is the preferential protection of the cognitive interest of all subjects of civil society: in the absence of obstacles attributable to the limits set by law, the administrations must give priority to the right of anyone to know and access information owned by the public administration.</p> <p>Unlike the procedural or documentary right of access (regulated by law no. 241/1990), the generalized civic access guarantees citizens the possibility of requesting data and documents from public administrations, without having to prove that they have a qualified interest. The generalized civic access extends to all data and documents in the possession of public administrations, on the sole condition that the public and private interests expressly indicated by the law are protected. As stated above, these rules would not apply to WSIs.</p>
Requirements for development of AI/ML	<p>31. Are there any restrictions or rules regarding use of health data or WSI in the context of development of artificial intelligence and machine learning systems (AI / ML)?</p> <p>Response: No, there are not.</p>
Requirement for contributing slides to BigPicture	<p>32. Assuming that the source of the WSI slides (see Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus) for your jurisdiction will be as provided above, please summarize the requirements, in particular (a) which of the laws are applicable to contributing the WSI, (b) what steps are required to provide</p>

	<p>them and (c) from a point of view of data protection laws, in which form (“raw”, anonymized, pseudonymized) may the WSI be submitted?</p> <p>Response:</p> <p>(a) The laws applicable are: GDPR; D.Lgs. 196/2003 (Personal Data Protection Code); The Provision of the Italian Privacy Authority (Garante) n. 146, 5 June, 2019</p> <p>(b) The first step is to ask for informed consent to the processing of personal data. However, as the original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies, sometimes it could be impossible to obtain the consent.</p> <p>If consent cannot be obtained (art. 110 D.Lgs. 196/2003), or it requires a disproportionate effort, the research project must be approved by the local ethical committee and the research project must be submitted to prior consultation with the Italian Privacy Authority.</p> <p>(c) The WSI can be submitted in pseudonymized form, but the pseudonyms mapping list would not be shared with the researchers.</p>
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Notes to the respondents

Background:

- The clinical part of the BIGPICTURE data repository will consist of digital scans of slides of human tissues or biological samples (WSI, whole slide imaging). The original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies. Those studies may have been conducted in the past or are ongoing trials. However, the primary purpose of collection of the slides will be the clinical studies or treatment of patients. Thus, the original slides will not be collected directly and primarily for the purpose of digitization for the BIGPICTURE data repository. We assume that the collection of the original slides was done in line with the requirements applicable to the such purpose.
- BIGPICTURE data repository will also reuse WSI from animal tissues that are also going to be digitized slides from existing collections. The BIGPICTURE repository will only store digital slides (WSI), not the glass originals or biological samples.
- The WSI will be accompanied by metadata (i.e. not only image will be stored). Scope of the metadata may vary, depending on the type of WSI.
- The purpose of storing the WSI is to make them available for scientific and research purposes.
- WSI will not be submitted from public health registries or electronic patient record systems.
- The data submitters will have digital pathology slides or will digitize slides generated as part of clinical diagnostic work that, in some instances, will have also been used in clinical studies. For some submitters, in case duplicate samples to the clinical samples are collected in the biobank of human tissues, DNA/RNA and body fluids, data that have been generated as part of research projects that have used these samples may be used. There may be additionally data from archives. No animal experimentation will be performed for the purpose of data collection in the project.
- Additional patient information may accompany WSI. The list will be provided at a later stage, however before month 6 of the project. Results from genomic investigation may be used as associated data in some WSI collections.

Source of WSI

At the current stage of the project, the following have been confirmed as initial data submitters:

UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT	UMC UTRECHT	Netherlands	Cancer node
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT	RUMC	Netherlands	Cancer node
Azienda Ospedaliera Per L'Emergenza Cannizzaro	AOEC	Italy	Cancer node
Technical University of Munich	TUM	Germany	Cancer node
PHILIPPS UNIVERSITAET MARBURG	UMR	Germany	Clinical trial node
THE LEEDS TEACHING HOSPITALS NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE TRUST	LHTNHS	UK	Liver node
HELSINGIN JA UUDENMAAN SAIRAANHOITOPPIIRIN KUNTAYHTYMÄ	HUS	Finland	Lung node
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT GRAZ	MUG	Austria	Lung node
DECIPHEX	DECIPHEX	Ireland	Non-clinical node
Medical University Vienna	MUW	Austria	Renal node
OSTERGOTLANDS LANS LANDSTING	RO	Sweden	Skin node
Linköping University	LiU	Sweden	Skin node
UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE	Belgium	Skin node

Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus

Instructions:

Please provide responses to the below questions based on the laws of your jurisdiction. Please use the below example as guidance as to the level of required detail. **Please note that the provided responses are for exemplary purposes only. The circumstances in your jurisdiction may be different, as well as legal basis and legal steps for contributing WSIs to the BigPicture project.**

We are looking for a practical description of issues which may impede or influence the planned collection of WSIs and their sharing with other researchers. If certain matter is regulated by GDPR, please do not explain in detail. Mere reference to GDPR rules is sufficient. If the response to certain questions is not clear under the current legal framework or the approach taken depends on the organization, please indicate this and, if possible, describe the most common approach.

Appendix 6 - The Netherlands Country Report

Responses for the Netherlands

Contributor: Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature)

Topic	Questions
National provisions on personal data processing in the context of scientific research	<p>1. Which national laws regulate use and sharing of health (“health data”), including WSIs, for research purposes? Please provide the name of the law, online reference, and relevance for the BigPicture (if not explained in other sections below)</p> <p>Response: There is no specific legislation for sharing of health data, but a few generic regulations apply for some aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uitvoeringswet Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming¹ (UAVG), i.e. General Data Protection Regulation Implementation Act, the local implementation law for the GDPR. In particular Article 24, which gives more specific conditions for scientific use without explicit consent. • Wet op de Geneeskundige Behandelingsovereenkomst² (WGBO), i.e. the Medical Treatment Contract Act. In particular Clauses 457 and 458 are largely the same as the conditions for further use of data as set out in the UAVG cited above. • Wet Medisch-wetenschappelijk Onderzoek³ (WMO), the Medical Research Regulation, dealing with intervention studies, which may apply when reusing clinical trial data. <p>2. Please describe how the databases and registers containing patient’s health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are organized in your jurisdiction and which type of data they contain. If possible, please indicate which databases or registers may be relevant for BigPicture.</p> <p>Response: Databases and registries with (fairly) direct impact for clinical care (e.g. for quality assurance or population health purposes) traditionally do not require consent of the data subject to include his/her data in their records. Research use of these data is often limited to aggregated data that can be considered anonymous. In the past, the opt-out principle (i.e. rather than consent (“opt-in”) data subjects have the opportunity to object (“opt-out”) against inclusion of their data in research studies) was quite commonly used making use of the exemptions for research in the GDPR and predecessor regulations. Recently, the interpretation of the GDPR has become more strict, and many of the procedures for accessing databases and registries with patient data on other legal bases than consent are being reconsidered. Registries specifically set up for research are usually created with a (broad) informed consent. This means that the data subjects (patients) provide their consent to include their personal data in the research registry, however they do not need to specify the purpose of research very specifically beyond e.g. a disease area or a field of research (“broad consent”).</p> <p>The most relevant register for BIGPICTURE is Palga⁴, the national pathology archive for all pathology data in The Netherlands; it is also referencing the physical slides as stored in the archives of the individual hospitals. Palga may provide the outcome</p>

¹ <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0040940/2019-02-19>

² https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0005290/2019-03-16/#Boek7_Titeldeel7_Afdeling5

³ <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0009408/2019-04-02>

⁴ <https://www.palga.nl/en/>

annotations for slides being uploaded to BIGPICTURE. Data can be requested from Palga for specific research use through the scientific and the privacy committee of Palga. It is questionable whether upload from Palga data to BIGPICTURE will be possible under its current data governance policy. Palga does not contain the digital slides themselves; these are only available from the local archives in the hospitals, but Palga can serve as a resource to locate interesting cases for which then access has to be requested through the individual hospitals.

3. Please describe general conditions on using patient's health data and WSIs of human biological samples for scientific research purposes.

Response: There is no specific legislation in the Netherlands on using patient's health data and WSIs of human biological samples for scientific research purposes except for the provisions in the Medical Treatment Contract Act (WGBO, Clauses 457 and 458) and the GDPR. According to them, scientific research without explicit consent of the patient is only allowed if such research is in the public interest and, obtaining such consent is impossible or imposes an unreasonable amount of effort and provided sufficient and proportionate safeguards are provided to protect the privacy of the individuals concerned.

The general rules on using patient's health data and WSIs for scientific research mainly relate to conditions on access to the data, i.e. who may have access to the raw (directly traceable) data and who may have access to the coded/pseudonymized (indirectly traceable) data. A national guideline⁵ has been drawn up for this by the privacy, ethics and law working group of the Dutch Federation of University Medical Centers.

Increasingly, it is the common opinion that data subject's consent is required for the reuse of the data for research unless the data can really be considered anonymous. The interpretation for anonymous data has also become more strict: data sets containing more than just a few patient-level data items are usually considered indirectly identifiable and therefore not anonymous. The debate on WSI themselves is not entirely clear, but in isolation without further information about the patient (e.g. metadata) these are usually still considered anonymous.

4. Is research subject's consent required for scientific research? Would using health data for scientific research purposes be possible, if the data was initially collected for other purpose? If yes, describe any conditions of such use.

Response: As listed above consent is usually required when more than a few patient-level data items are shared. The default in the Netherlands is usually opt-in (affirmative consent). An exception from consent is possible if it is impossible to request consent or when it requires an exceptional effort (Art 24 of the uAVG).

The data, images and biomaterial can be used for purposes other than the purpose for which it was initially collected. However, it is not the case that it can be used for health research in general. It commonly considered that the additional use should be limited to the same organ or disease area. In case of opt-in, broad consent is used in the case of biobanks and registries. Such consent is limited to an organ or disease area, but the specific research question is not yet known (and hence described in the consent).

Nowadays consents tend to be quite broad driven by the FAIR principles, but historically that is not the case. Anyhow, this needs to be reviewed on a case-by-case basis. Usually, some level of review of the anticipated research proposal will

⁵ <https://elsi.health-ri.nl/sites/elsi/files/2020-11/NFU%20Handreiking%20Handreiking%20Hergebruik%20van%20Zorggegevens%20voor%20Wetens.pdf>

	<p>be needed (e.g. by a data access committee). This review will also verify whether the intended reuse of data matches the original purpose of the data collection (including wording of the consent which was provided earlier). An agreement is needed to transfer the obligations from the data holder to the data user (e.g. a Data Transfer Agreement).</p> <p>5. From which generally applicable data protection provisions of GDPR (in particular requirements under Articles 13-21) are scientific researchers exempted and under what conditions?</p> <p>Response: Based on Clause 44 UAVG institutes or services for scientific research or statistics are exempted from articles 15, 16, and 18 GDPR provided sufficient precautions have been taken to ensure this is the only use of the data (scientific research or statistics).</p> <p>6. Are there specific provisions which relate to appropriate safeguards, including using or making available anonymous or pseudonymized health data in the context of scientific research?</p> <p>Response: No country-specific provisions, hence GDPR rules apply.</p> <p>7. What are the potential consequences of non-compliance with the rules outlined in the questions above?</p> <p>Response: The general provision in the GDPR apply, and possibly civil claims based on the WGBO. We do have the national authority for data protection (The Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens⁶), which may fine any offender as outlined in the GDPR. On top of that, the national press is quite sensitive to any offenses with respect to personal data. Non-compliances may lead to publications in the press with corresponding reputation risks. As a result, data holders are quite risk adverse and will only share data when absolutely sure that all legal requirements are fulfilled.</p>
Digitalization of original slides	<p>8. Are there any specific rules regarding digitalization of images of human tissues and biological samples? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: No, there is no such law.</p>
Ethical board approvals requirements / biomedical research projects	<p>9. Is there a regime requiring an approval of ethical board or any similar or related conditions prior to making WSIs and sharing them for research purposes? If yes, what does that regime entail? Please refer to any rules of obtaining ethical board approvals for biomedical research projects, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: There is only a legal obligation to obtain ethical approval when it involves intervention studies (then the WMO applies, the regulation on clinical trials). As for WSIs, there is not a specific regime. In practice, biobanks and cohorts typically need to seek approval from an ethical board before initiating such a collection to meet the requirements in the Medical Treatment Contact Act (WGBO). For other data collections several institutions have so-called Institutional Review Boards (IRB), which is not a legal obligation but an institutional safeguard that all procedures are followed. There is clearly a lack of consensus in this area.</p>
Animal tissues and biological samples (non-clinical WSI)	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI of animal samples may be collected in some jurisdictions.</p>

⁶ <https://www.autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/>

	<p>10. Are there any rules that regulate use of WSI of animal samples that have already been produced in another study for scientific research purposes? If yes, please describe.</p> <p>Response: There are no specific rules for WSI of animal samples, but general ethical regulations for handling of animal samples in research apply. This is regulated by the generic Law on animal experiments (<i>Wet op de Dierproeven</i>). However, the law applies to new animal experimentation performed to create slides. Assuming that the physical slides were created for the purposes of other experiments, which were in line with the Law on animal experiments, no additional considerations would apply to digitalization of such slides.</p>
Processing of genetic data	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI metadata may contain genetic information related to the data subject. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>11. How is processing of genetic data regulated? Please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: There is no specific law or regulation for genetic information. The general provisions of the GDPR for sensitive personal data apply.</p> <p>The use of genetic data is a point of discussion in connection with the chance of unsolicited findings⁷, because there are basically always unsolicited findings in genetic research. The upcoming tissue regulation (<i>Wzj</i>; ‘medical tissue act’) states that the field must come up with an unambiguous policy with regard to unsolicited findings.</p> <p>12. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained human genetic data? Are there any additional restrictions on making the human genetic data available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: No, because Article 28 of the GDPR Implementing law (UAVG) which applies to genetic data contains similar exception to article 24 of this implementation law. Accordingly, the prohibition to process genetic data is not applicable for scientific research with a public interest or statistics provided the data subject gave consent and it will not harm the data subject. An exception from this consent is possible if it is impossible to request consent or when it requires an exceptional effort.</p>
Data on rare diseases / Covid 19	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI may relate rare disease or Covid19 research. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>13. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on rare diseases? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: No specific considerations. The same rules and regulations as for common disease apply. Of course, the generic rules for unexpected findings do apply, but that is also the case for common disease.</p> <p>14. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on Covid19? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p>

⁷For example see:

https://www.bbmri.nl/sites/bbmri/files/Erasmus_MC_Handreiking_Interactieve_pdf_Engels_29_04_2020_V3.pdf

	<p>Response: No specific considerations. There has been considerable debate whether the exemptions in the GDPR for public health apply in the context of Covid19 epidemic. In its statements, the Dutch Data Protection Authority indicated that there are no reasons to treat these data differently.</p>
Clinical trials	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that the original slides may have been collected during clinical trials in the meaning of Directive 2001/20/EC⁸.</p> <p>15. Are there any additional restrictions on making the health data collected during clinical trials available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: The general rules apply: the provisions in the original informed consent of the clinical trial should be respected. If reuse is not clearly dealt with (i.e. provided for in the consent wording), a re-consent may be required.</p>
Biobanks	<p>When answering the following questions, please consider applicable requirements if the WSI were submitted by a biobank or from a biobank in your jurisdiction.</p> <p>16. How are biobanks regulated in your jurisdiction? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information</p> <p>Response: There is no specific law on biobanks in the Netherlands, however there are rules on use of human material provided in the WGBO and code of conduct. Namely, under WGBO if tissue and blood cannot be linked to the individual concerned, research use is allowed provided the individual concerned has not objected (article 7:467 Dutch Civil Code⁹).</p> <p>This is also self-regulated under the Dutch Code for proper secondary use of human tissue (<i>code goed gebruik van lichaamsmateriaal</i> 2011¹⁰). The code of conduct develops the above-stated rule into a set of concrete standards for Dutch health research that are accessible to researchers. The code of conduct thus aims to clarify which rules Dutch health research should comply with in practice. This relates to data, images and biomaterial. The code was drafted under the control of the COREON (https://www.coreon.org/about-coreon/), the foundation about regulation in health research and is accepted by the national umbrella organisation of ethical committee (CCMO: https://english.ccmo.nl/).</p> <p>The present regulations may be overwritten with the upcoming introduction of the medical tissue act ("<i>Wet Zeggenschap Lichaamsmateriaal</i>"), which is currently <u>submitted to parliament</u>.</p> <p>17. Can health data (including WSI) stored in the biobanks be shared with other parties to be used for scientific research purposes? If yes, what are the conditions of such sharing and use?</p> <p>Response: That is certainly possible. Part of the informed consent procedure at the biobank is a detailed brochure for patients. This brochure explains, among other things, what the purpose of the biobank is, what the policy is with regard to unsolicited findings, how the privacy of the patients is protected and that the data/images/biomaterial can be shared with external (commercial) partners. If material from a biobank is shared with external partners, a data/material transfer agreement (DTA/MTA) must be drawn up. A national template is available. Of course, also the GDPR applies. In the context of BigPicture, since the project does not involve new research on human subjects, the external partners applying to the</p>

⁸ DIRECTIVE 2001/20/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

⁹ The WGBO (Medical Treatment Contract Act) is part of the Dutch Civil Code.

¹⁰ <https://elsi.health-ri.nl/sites/elsi/files/Code%20Goed%20Gebruik.pdf>.

	<p>biobanks to access their submitted WSIs via the BigPicture infrastructure would not have to obtain an ethics approval. They may need to perform a DPIA when data linkage is involved.</p>
Data localization and infrastructure requirements	<p>18. What are the rules of transferring health data or human tissues for specific research projects to third parties?</p> <p>Response: There are no specific rules except the generic provisions in e.g. the GDPR (“organisational & technical measures”). Usually, an encrypted connection is used for data transfers to meet to these requirements.</p> <p>19. Are there any provisions restricting transfer of health data outside of your country?</p> <p>Response: No, nothing on top of the restrictions in the GDPR and recent case law around the GDPR (Schrems). Transfer within the EU is not restricted in any other way than transfer within the country. Also, in daily practice these transfers are well accepted when the data governance process is followed and data sharing or similar agreements are in place.</p> <p>20. Are there any specific infrastructure/security requirements for storing health data?</p> <p>Response: Only the general provisions as listed in the GDPR (“technical and organisational measures”). For personal data these are usually interpreted in such a manner that some form of well accepted audit certificate (ISO 27001 or similar national certifications NE7510, NEN7512, NEN7513) is needed to prove that the security requirements are in place. This requirement for certification is usually also included in data processing agreements related to health data.</p>
Honest broker model	<p>21. Is there a trusted third party service (“honest broker”) established in your jurisdiction, where researcher may submit a request for the data to be pseudonymized before access? If yes, please provide the name of the service, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: No, although there is a fairly commonly used commercial service for secure data linkage which has some features of an honest broker. This service is called ZorgTTP.</p> <p>22. Please describe any restrictions or limitations regarding “honest broker” of health data according to your national law.</p> <p>Response: The usage of the national social security number (BSN) is strictly regulated. Health providers are required by law to use it in clinical care records, while its usage in health research is strictly forbidden¹¹. Even encrypted usage of this BSN is usually not acceptable for research purposes (such as data linkage). This complicates data linkage and data sharing between clinical care and clinical research.</p>
Contractual limitations / limitation on	<p>23. Are there any mandatory provisions which impose specific terms of use of health data or WSI by researchers? Please include any limitations on commercial use of WSIs. In your response, please provide name of the law and explain the requirements under such provisions.</p>

¹¹ General law on the BSN: <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0022428/2018-07-28>; Specific regulation on the use of the BSN in clinical care: <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0023902/2019-03-30>

commercial use of WSIs	<p>Response: Dutch implementing legislation for GDPR allows exceptions to research use without consent only for research performed in the public interest (art 24 and 28 UAVG). Consequently, research use for commercial purposes is only allowed based on consent.</p> <p>In some institutions, patients can indicate whether or not they agree to share their data, images and biomaterial with commercial partners. In other institutes, the patient brochure indicates that collaboration with companies is possible. It is emphasized that patients will not acquire any ownership rights in the results and will not be entitled to any future financial benefit.</p>
Copyrights / database rights / data license requirements	<p>24. Under the laws of your jurisdiction, would the WSI be subject to copyright protection, database rights, any other intellectual property rights? Who would be the holder of such rights?</p> <p>Response: Yes, but only database rights in limited extent. Database rights could apply to an organized collection of slides, but technically, such database rights would apply to the infrastructure and the entirety of the database, not individual slides or individual contributions from the data providers.</p> <p>Moreover, MTAs/DTAs usually deal with the rights of the results of the research conducted with the use of the slides.</p> <p>25. Are those IP rights transferrable or could a license to use them be granted? If yes, please describe any statutory conditions, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: n/a</p>
Removal of commercially sensitive information (trade secrets)	<p>26. Are there any laws (other than GDPR/data protection laws) which would make it mandatory that certain information (e.g. commercial information) is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information must be removed.</p> <p>Response: Possibly in some exceptional cases Dutch Trade secret act (<i>Wet bescherming bedrijfsgeheimen</i>¹², <i>Wbb</i>) should be considered. It is generic i.e. does not apply to WSI in particular, but trade secrets in general. Under this act, secrecy is a requirement for trade secrets. Furthermore, if a party indicates that certain information constitutes their trade secret and should not be made public, then it would likely have to be removed. There is no requirement to remove trade secrets in the <i>Wbb</i>, this depends on the decision of the holder of the trade secret if they want to make it public.</p> <p>27. Are there any laws which would prohibit that certain information is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information cannot be removed.</p> <p>Response: n/a</p> <p>28. Are there any other limitations on the submitter of the WSIs with respect to making them available without information constituting a trade secret of the owner?</p> <p>Response: n/a</p>
Access to public information	<p>29. Which public information laws apply? Please explain how they may impact disclosing of WSI by the foreseen data provider.</p>

¹² <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0041459/2018-10-23>

	<p>Response: There are some generic public information laws that apply to transparent government like the Wet Openbaarheid Bestuur (WOB)¹³, but these don't appear to have any relation to WSIs or even private institution.</p> <p>30. Please briefly describe the rules of public information access and possible restrictions and specify to which type of providers they would apply.</p> <p>Response: As mentioned above, WOB rules are not applicable to BigPicture partners or slide contributors, as only public bodies are subject to them. In general, under WOB rules anyone may request information regarding specific governance matters. Decisions to be taken within 4 weeks, period may be extended for an additional 4 weeks. Some Exceptions (non limitative): no information needs to be provided if that would be detrimental to state security or the economic interests of certain public bodies, no trade secrets that are the property of third parties, no personal data, (see clauses 10, 1 and 10 2 of the WOB)</p>
Requirements for development of AI/ML	<p>31. Are there any restrictions or rules regarding use of health data or WSI in the context of development of artificial intelligence and machine learning systems (AI / ML)?</p> <p>Response: No, nothing at national scale. At European scale there is of course a regulation on the responsible use of AI in preparation.</p>
Requirement for contributing slides to BigPicture	<p>32. Assuming that the source of the WSI slides (see Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus) for your jurisdiction will be as provided above, please summarize the requirements, in particular (a) which of the laws are applicable to contributing the WSI, (b) what steps are required to provide them and (c) from a point of view of data protection laws, in which form ("raw", anonymized, pseudonymized) may the WSI be submitted?</p> <p>Response: It is difficult to provide an overarching answer, as many aspects rely on local interpretations of the regulations and the specifics of the data to be provided. Nevertheless, some steps could be identified that are quire commonly followed by the providers of WSIs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Determine whether the data (WSIs) are anonymous or personal; Note that GDPR already contains data minimisation principles, so if anonymisation is an option, that should be used! 2. If WSI are considered to contain personal data, ensure legal ground. Check applicability of Article 5 (1) sub b GDPR and find exception to prohibition of sharing health data. 3. Ensure that the receiving parties take appropriate organisational and technical safeguards and put in place contracts regarding use of WSIs 4. Seek permission for your data sharing according to the appropriate governance body (ethical committee, data access committee, or similar for observational data) 5. Conclude data sharing agreements or similar.

¹³ <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0005252/2018-07-28>

Notes to the respondents

Background:

- The clinical part of the BIGPICTURE data repository will consist of digital scans of slides of human tissues or biological samples (WSI, whole slide imaging). The original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies. Those studies may have been conducted in the past or are ongoing trials. However, the primary purpose of collection of the slides will be the clinical studies or treatment of patients. Thus, the original slides will not be collected directly and primarily for the purpose of digitization for the BIGPICTURE data repository. We assume that the collection of the original slides was done in line with the requirements applicable to the such purpose.
- BIGPICTURE data repository will also reuse WSI from animal tissues that are also going to be digitized slides from existing collections. The BIGPICTURE repository will only store digital slides (WSI), not the glass originals or biological samples.
- The WSI will be accompanied by metadata (i.e. not only image will be stored). Scope of the metadata may vary, depending on the type of WSI.
- The purpose of storing the WSI is to make them available for scientific and research purposes.
- WSI will not be submitted from public health registries or electronic patient record systems.
- The data submitters will have digital pathology slides or will digitize slides generated as part of clinical diagnostic work that, in some instances, will have also been used in clinical studies. For some submitters, in case duplicate samples to the clinical samples are collected in the biobank of human tissues, DNA/RNA and body fluids, data that have been generated as part of research projects that have used these samples may be used. There may be additionally data from archives. No animal experimentation will be performed for the purpose of data collection in the project.
- Additional patient information may accompany WSI. The list will be provided at a later stage, however before month 6 of the project. Results from genomic investigation may be used as associated data in some WSI collections.

Source of WSI

At the current stage of the project, the following have been confirmed as initial data submitters:

UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT	UMC UTRECHT	Netherlands	Cancer node
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT	RUMC	Netherlands	Cancer node
Azienda Ospedaliera Per L'Emergenza Cannizzaro	AOEC	Italy	Cancer node
Technical University of Munich	TUM	Germany	Cancer node
PHILIPPS UNIVERSITAET MARBURG	UMR	Germany	Clinical trial node
THE LEEDS TEACHING HOSPITALS NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE TRUST	LTHNHS	UK	Liver node
HELSINGIN JA UUDENMAAN SAIRAANHOITOPPIRIN KUNTAYHTYMÄ	HUS	Finland	Lung node
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT GRAZ	MUG	Austria	Lung node
DECIPHEX	DECIPHEX	Ireland	Non-clinical node
Medical University Vienna	MUW	Austria	Renal node
OSTERGOTLANDS LANS LANDSTING	RO	Sweden	Skin node
Linköping University	LiU	Sweden	Skin node
UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE	Belgium	Skin node

Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus

Instructions:

Please provide responses to the below questions based on the laws of your jurisdiction. Please use the below example as guidance as to the level of required detail. **Please note that the provided responses are for**

exemplary purposes only. The circumstances in your jurisdiction may be different, as well as legal basis and legal steps for contributing WSIs to the BigPicture project.

We are looking for a practical description of issues which may impede or influence the planned collection of WSIs and their sharing with other researchers. If certain matter is regulated by GDPR, please do not explain in detail. Mere reference to GDPR rules is sufficient. If the response to certain questions is not clear under the current legal framework or the approach taken depends on the organization, please indicate this and, if possible, describe the most common approach.

Appendix 7 - Sweden Country Report

Responses for Sweden

Contributors: Magdalena Kogut-Czarkowska (Timelex), review by Dino Salagic, Linnea Lundberg and Håkan Gustafsson (RÖ)

Topic	Questions
National provisions on personal data processing in the context of scientific research	<p>1. Which national laws regulate use and sharing of health (“health data”), including WSIs, for research purposes? Please provide the name of the law, online reference, and relevance for the BigPicture (if not explained in other sections below)</p> <p>Response: The following provisions regulate use and sharing of health data in Sweden:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Protection Act [Lag (2018:218) med kompletterande bestämmelser till EU:s dataskyddsförordning] containing supplementary provisions to the EU General Data Protection Regulation, https://www.svenskforfattningssamling.se/doc/2018218.html • Patient Data Act [Patientdatalag (2008:355)] which is specifically applicable to health data processing carried out by private or public healthcare providers. • Act on Biobanks within Health and Medical Care (Biobank Act) (lagen (2002:297) om biobanker i hälso- och sjukvården m.m.), https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2002297-om-biobanker-i-halso--och_sfs-2002-297, regulates biobanks, including how samples from a biobank may be accessed for research purposes • Act on Health Data Registers (lagen (1998:543) om hälsodataregister), https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-1998543-om-halsodataregister_sfs-1998-543 and several regulations, e.g. Regulation on Patient Registers with the National Board of Health and Welfare (Förordning (2001:707) om patientregister hos Socialstyrelsen), https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/forordning-2001707-om-patientregister-hos_sfs-2001-707 • Higher Education Act (1992:1434) [Högskolelag], https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/hogskolelag-19921434_sfs-1992-1434 • Genetic Integrity Act (lagen (2006:351) om genetisk integritet m.m.), https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2006351-om-genetisk-integritet-mm_sfs-2006-351 • Act on ethical review (2003: 460) on research concerning people (Ethical Review Act) [Lag (2003:460) om etikprovning av forskning som avser människor] (https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2003460-om-etikprovning-av-forskning-som_sfs-2003-460)

- Health Care Act [Hälsa- och sjukvårdslag (2017:30)] https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/halso--och-sjukvardslag-201730_sfs-2017-30

Other relevant laws include:

- Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act [Offentlighets- och sekretesslag (2009:400)], https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/offentlighets--och-sekretesslag-2009400_sfs-2009-400 stipulates requirements for healthcare providers regarding security and confidentiality, though OSL only applies to public authorities
- Freedom of the Press Act [Tryckfrihetsförordningen (1949:105)], <http://www.riksdagen.se/globalassets/07.-dokument--lagar/the-freedom-of-the-press-act-2015.pdf>

Researchers may find helpful information on access data for research purposes may at the Swedish Research Council (Vetenskapsrådet) website at <https://www.registerforskning.se/> (available in Swedish and English) and at the Biobank Sweden website <https://biobanksverige.se/english/research/> (available in Swedish and English).

2. Please describe how the databases and registers containing patient's health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are organized in your jurisdiction and which type of data they contain. If possible, please indicate which databases or registers may be relevant for BigPicture.

Response: According to the Health Care Act, within the framework of activities that constitute primary care, regions and municipalities are obligated to enable participation in the implementation of research work.¹

In the context of health data two types of registers in Sweden are of particular importance: databases kept by healthcare providers, so-called national quality registers (*kvalitetsregister*) and biobanks which can be administered by both private and public healthcare providers. The other registers are public governing registers² and registers in universities.³ For information about biobanks, please refer to question 16.

There are 108 National Quality Registers operating under the healthcare system with an authority in a county council/region as the personal data controller. These registers have been established in specific areas to systematically and continuously develop and ensure the quality of healthcare. The registers are used for improvement work and follow-up of healthcare as well as for research. The quality registers contain personal data regarding healthcare, such as diagnosis, treatment, and results of treatment.⁴

According to the Act on Health Data Registers, all health care providers are obliged to provide patient data to a health data register kept by the National board on Health and welfare, the Medical Products Agency and the Public Health Agency.⁵ The purpose of processing health data in the register are: (i) production of statistics,

¹ Health Care Act, Chapter 14

² For more information, see www.registerforskning.se.

³ Information about some of these registers is available at the Swedish National Data Service (in Swedish, SND) (www.snd.se). Information about several larger cohorts is also available at the Swedish Cohort Consortium (www.cohorts.se).

⁴ Guide to Biobanks in Sweden –Access to Samples for Research and Clinical trials (<https://biobanksverige.se/english/research/useful-resources/documentation-in-english/>)

⁵ Section 6A, Act on Health Data Registers

(ii) follow-up, evaluation and quality assurance of health care and (iii) research and epidemiological investigations.⁶

Information about samples collected for healthcare purposes is stored in the Laboratory Information System (LIS) of the county council/region in question. The LIS information is a part of a patient's medical record. The content of LIS may differ depending on the type of IT system and the clinical discipline. The county councils/regions are in the process of establishing a joint register for traceability of stored samples, called the Swedish Biobank Registry (SBR).

Information on samples collected for research purposes initiated from a research institution or a healthcare provider can be stored in the laboratory information management system (LIMS). LIMS exist at almost every university hospital/university and in some healthcare regions. Data registered in LIMS regards handling of samples from sampling until storage. There is usually no data on analysis results or diagnostics, as such data is stored in another system by the researcher.⁷

3. Please describe general conditions on using patient's health data and WSIs of human biological samples for scientific research purposes.

The rules of using patient's health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are regulated by Ethical Review Act, GDPR, Biobanks Act as well as other regulations (e.g. Higher Education Act).

- Ethical Review Act

Generally, release of patients' health data as well as identifiable samples to be used in research, requires an approval from Swedish Ethical Review Authority (regional Ethics Review Board) in accordance with the Ethical Review Act. More details on the approval process are provided in question 9.

- Data protection rules

The description of rules of GDPR will be omitted, as per instructions above.

- Biobanks Act

Information about requirements of Biobanks Act are provided in question 16.

- Higher Education Act

A general commission to perform academic research was established in the Higher Education Act.⁸ This Act applies to higher education institutions for which the Government is the accountable authority, which includes the majority of Swedish research universities. This means that the legal ground for research under this Act is public interest and not consent. In many cases also research conducted by private entities qualifies if the research is regulated by any of the legal documents types listed above or based on a government or government agency decision. In some cases private entities conduct research that does not fall under the Act, for example, some of the research by pharmaceutical companies. When that occurs, the processing of personal data may be allowed by consent or under Article 6(1)(f), i.e. legitimate interest, which entails a case-by-case weighing between the controller's legitimate interest of processing and the registered subject's right to privacy protection. Further, the so-called "Life Gene Act"⁹, enacted as a response

⁶ Section 3, Act on Health Data Registers

⁷ Guide to Biobanks in Sweden –Access to Samples for Research and Clinical trials (<https://biobanksverige.se/english/research/useful-resources/documentation-in-english/>)

⁸ 2 § Higher Education Act

⁹ Act on Certain Registries for Research on what Inheritance and the Environment Mean for

to regulatory difficulties to collect information for a major long term research infrastructure project named Life Gene, provides specific rules on collection of personal data by universities and colleges in relation to certain registers.

4. Is research subject's consent required for scientific research? Would using health data for scientific research purposes be possible, if the data was initially collected for other purpose? If yes, describe any conditions of such use.

Response: Consent may serve different functions or concern different aspects of research. The most common of these are:

- **Consent to participation.** This is the general research-ethical requirement ensuring that participation in research is informed and voluntary. For participating in clinical trials, special requirements apply.
- **Consent as a legal basis for personal data processing.** Processing of personal data must rely on a legal basis. Consent from those whose data are processed is one possible legal basis, but it is normally only recommended in cases where the research involves processing of sensitive personal data that takes place outside of Sweden.
- **Consent to the processing of biological samples.** When research involves the taking and saving of biological samples, research subjects are asked to consent to this.¹⁰

The latter consent is regulated by Section 17 Ethical Review Act. According to this provision research which:¹¹

- involves a physical intervention on a researcher,
- is carried out according to a method that aims to affect the researcher physically or mentally or that involves an obvious risk of physically harming the researcher or mentally,
- refers to studies on biological material taken from a living person and can be traced to that person
- requires consent of the research subject. Such consent must be voluntary, explicit and specific, given after receiving information on the research¹², and be documented.

Further to Ethical Review Act, exceptions to the consent requirement exist, due to for example illness or mental disorder.¹³ Even if a research person's opinion cannot be obtained, the person must, as far as possible, be personally informed about the research. Consultation shall take place with the research person's closest relatives. The research may not be carried out if the research person in any form expresses a refusal to participate or if any of those with whom the consultation has taken place opposes the execution.

If a research person is in a dependent relationship with the research principal or a researcher or if the research person can be assumed to have special difficulties in

Human Health [Lag (2013:794) om vissa register för forskning om vad arv och miljö betyder för människors hälsa ('Life Gene Act')]

¹⁰ <https://www.su.se/staff/services/research/research-ethics/how-to-inform-research-subjects-and-ask-for-their-consent-1.501340#Important%20information%20concerning%20the%20use%20of%20personal%20data%20in%20research>

¹¹ Section 13 Ethical Review Act

¹² Details about the information required are provided in Section 16 Ethical Review Act.

¹³ Exceptions are provided in Sections 20-22 Ethical Review Act.

exercising his or her right, issues of information and consent shall be given special attention in the ethics review.

Despite the consent of the guardians, research may not be carried out if a researcher who is under 15 years of age realizes what it means for him or her and opposes it being carried out. Young people between the ages of 15 and 18 give their own consent if they realize what the research means for him or her.¹⁴

A consent may be withdrawn at any time with immediate effect. However, the data that has been collected before that may be used in the research.¹⁵

In relation to the use of sensitive data for scientific research purposes, consent is only one of the possible legal basis for processing. In particular, if any part of the processing will take place outside of Sweden, consent in the meaning of GDPR may be required.¹⁶ The legal literature indicates however that according to the current Swedish interpretation, explicit consent for sensitive data “does not exclude consent given orally or by a clear affirmative action, such as knowingly participating in a clinical study.”¹⁷ Furthermore, if sensitive data will be used for scientific research purposes, the ethical vetting procedure must be followed, as detailed in question 9.

For hospitals consent rules defined in the Patient Data Act also apply since the collection and storage of samples for treatment and other medical purposes are also regulated in this Act.¹⁸ The Patient Data Act provides conditions for the patient health data to be processed in the quality registers.

For higher education institutions and universities, which are authorities, the legal basis for processing personal data for research purposes is almost without exception the legal basis of general interest that is relevant in the processing of personal data in connection with research. Since higher education institutions and universities have a constitutionally regulated task of conducting research, the processing of personal data is necessary in order to perform a task of general interest, which thus constitutes the legal basis on which the processing is based.¹⁹

5. From which generally applicable data protection provisions of GDPR (in particular requirements under Articles 13-21) are scientific researchers exempted and under what conditions?

Response: There are no explicit exceptions in the Swedish law regarding exceptions from Articles 13-21 GDPR in the context of scientific research. The Data Protection Act authorized the government may issue provisions on restrictions in accordance with Article 89(2) and 89(3) GDPR;²⁰ however no such derogation has been adopted.

As described above, the research subject is to receive information about the research.²¹ This information includes: purpose of the research, the methods used,

¹⁴ Section 17 Ethical Review Act

¹⁵ Section 19 Ethical Review Act

¹⁶ <https://www.su.se/staff/services/research/research-ethics/how-to-inform-research-subjects-and-ask-for-their-consent-1.501340#Important%20information%20concerning%20the%20use%20of%20personal%20data%20in%20research>

¹⁷ “GDPR and Biobanking” Santa Slokenberga, Olga Tzortzatou, Jane Reichel, Springer International Publishing 2021, pg. 387.

¹⁸ Chapter 4 – 5 Patient Data Act

¹⁹ <https://snd.gu.se/sv/hantera-data/planera/forskningsdata-med-personuppgifter#r%C3%A4ttsliggrund>

²⁰ Chapter 5, Section 3 Data Protection Act

²¹ Section 16 Ethical Review Act

the consequences and risks the research may entail, the responsible research body, the voluntary nature of participation and the right of the research subject to cease participation at any time.

6. Are there specific provisions which relate to appropriate safeguards, including using or making available anonymous or pseudonymized health data in the context of scientific research?

Response: Only partially. The Data Protection Act includes a general safeguard rule for purpose limitations in research according to which researchers may only use personal data collected for research purposes to take in respect of data subject, if there are particular reasons for the vital interests of the data subject.²²

Moreover, existing Swedish rules on confidentiality and professional secrecy that are generally applicable to research and statistics are also considered to be suitable safeguards. For example, Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act (Public Access Act) states that confidentiality applies to information pertaining to an individual's health or sex life, such as information about illness or abuse²³. In addition, confidentiality applies where disclosure would result in personal data being processed in a manner contrary to the provisions of the GDPR or Ethical Review Act²⁴. Public Access Act states that if an authority, as part of its research activities, receives data from another authority that is classified as confidential, this confidentiality will apply to the data at the receiving authority.²⁵

Furthermore, the Patient Data Act contains specific rules applicable to data in "quality registers". Quality register is an automated and structured collection of personal data that has been set up specifically for the purpose of systematically and continuously developing and ensuring the quality of care. According to the Patient Data Act an individual's personal identity number (in Swedish personnummer) or name may only be used in the quality registers if coded personal data, i.e. pseudonymised data, is not sufficient for the purpose of the processing.²⁶

7. What are the potential consequences of non-compliance with the rules outlined in the questions above?

Response: Intentional violation of the provisions of the Ethical Review Act can result in fines or imprisonment for a maximum of two years; minor violations will, however, not lead to any sanction.

Intentional or negligent violations of the GDPR can result in fines. Compensation can also be paid to the individual for injury and violations of personal integrity caused by any processing contrary to the provisions of both the GDPR and the Biobank Act.²⁷

In cases of violation of professional secrecy ("brott mot tystnadsplikt") Chapter 20 Section 3 of the Swedish Penal Code (Brottsbalk (1962:700)) will be applicable; this can result in fines or imprisonment for a maximum of one year.

Furthermore, the violations may result in labour law sanctions, in case the infringer is an employee.

²² Chapter 4, Section 3 Data Protection Act

²³ Chapter 21 Section 1 Public Access Act

²⁴ Chapter 21 Section 7 Public Access Act

²⁵ Chapter 11 Section 3 Public Access Act

²⁶ Chapter 7 Section 8 Patient Data Act

²⁷ Chapter 6 Section 2 Biobank Act

Digitalization of original slides	<p>8. Are there any specific rules regarding digitalization of images of human tissues and biological samples? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: No. However, Act on Quality and Security Norms when Processing Human Tissue or Cells²⁸ applies when human tissue or human cells are processed for use on humans or for the production of medicine for humans. The law also contains provisions on the import of tissue products. However, the Act does not contain specific provisions on digitalization of the images.²⁹</p>
Ethical board approvals requirements / biomedical research projects	<p>9. Is there a regime requiring an approval of ethical board or any similar or related conditions prior to making WSIs and sharing them for research purposes? If yes, what does that regime entail? Please refer to any rules of obtaining ethical board approvals for biomedical research projects, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: The Ethical Review Act, mentioned above, is the main piece of legislation relating to research in the field of health purposes in Sweden. The Ethical Review Act requires that research carried out in Sweden on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - biological material taken from a living person that can be traced to that person, - biological material taken for medical purposes from a deceased human being that can be traced to this human being - categories of personal data listed in Article 9.1 GDPR (“sensitive data”, including health data), as well as criminal convictions and offenses <p>must be approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority.³⁰</p> <p>Approval is valid for two years, meaning that the research must be commenced within this time period. For approval to be given, research must meet certain conditions, for example be conducted or supervised by a researcher with the necessary competence³¹ Research may be approved only if sufficient scientific value outweighs any risks to the research subject’s health, safety and personal integrity.³² Approval cannot be given where the anticipated result can be achieved through other means that entail fewer risks to the research subject’s health, safety or personal integrity In addition, research involving the processing of sensitive personal data may only be approved if such processing is necessary for the research to be carried out.³³</p> <p>Ethical permits cannot be received, and hence not used as safeguards, for research conducted outside of Sweden. In that case, some other safeguard must be in place.³⁴ Furthermore, the healthcare provider must make an assessment and document it in the records of the medical documentation.</p>

²⁸ In Swedish: Lagen (2008:286) om kvalitets- och säkerhetsnormer vid hantering av mänskliga vävnader och celler (vävnadslagen)]

²⁹ The Act is based on Directive 2004/23/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 March 2004 on setting standards of quality and safety for the donation, procurement, testing, processing, preservation, storage and distribution of human tissues and cells.

³⁰ Section 3-6 Ethical Review Act

³¹ Section 11 Ethical Review Act

³² Section 9 Ethical Review Act

³³ Section 10 Ethical Review Act

³⁴ “GDPR and Biobanking” Santa Slokenberga, Olga Tzortzatou, Jane Reichel, Springer International Publishing 2021, pg. 386,

	<p>An application must be made for research approval and a fee paid by the person responsible for the research. A written procedure is generally used by the boards. At the meetings, any one of three decisions can be made: an application may be approved, approved subject to certain conditions or rejected. The regional boards should normally make a decision within sixty (60) days of receiving a fully completed application. More on the process: https://etikprovningmyndigheten.se/for-forskare/sa-gar-det-till/.</p>
Animal tissues and biological samples (non-clinical WSI)	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI of animal samples may be collected in some jurisdictions.</p> <p>10. Are there any rules that regulate use of WSI of animal samples that have already been produced in another study for scientific research purposes? If yes, please describe.</p> <p>Response: With regard to animal testing, the Animal Welfare Act contains conditions on animal testing, including requirements of approval of regional animal experiment ethics committee. Ethical approval is needed for experiments on living mammals, birds, reptiles, anura, fish, and cyclostomes. In many cases, this includes embryos.³⁵ However, this requirement would <u>not</u> apply for use of WSI of animal samples which were previously produced in an approved study.</p>
Processing of genetic data	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI metadata may contain genetic information related to the data subject. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>11. How is processing of genetic data regulated? Please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: The Genetic Integrity Act³⁶ deals specifically with the use of genetic investigations, genetic information and gene therapy. The Act contains provisions on e.g. whether genetic information can be requested by insurance companies and stipulates requirements for genetic investigation. The Act also deals with pre-natal and pre-implantation genetic diagnosis, research using human eggs, insemination, and fertilisation outside the body.</p> <p>12. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained human genetic data? Are there any additional restrictions on making the human genetic data available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: According to Genetic Integrity Act, no one may, without the support of law, make it a condition of an agreement that the other party shall undergo a genetic examination or provide genetic information about himself. No one may, without the support of law in connection with an agreement, investigate or use genetic information about the other. No one may illegally provide access to genetic information about anyone else.³⁷</p>
Data on rare diseases / Covid 19	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI may relate rare disease or Covid19 research. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>13. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on rare diseases? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p>

³⁵ <https://snd.gu.se/en/manage-data/plan/ethical-review>

³⁶ An unofficial translation is available at <http://www.smer.se/news/the-genetic-integrity-act-2006351/>

³⁷ Chapter 2, Section 1 Genetic Integrity Act

	<p>Response: If the data concerns very rare diseases, this can affect the rules regarding keeping the data in accordance with secrecy and confidentiality rules, because in case of such diseases it may be difficult or impossible to de-identify the data to the extent that it is made anonymous.</p> <p>14. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on Covid19? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: N/A</p>
Clinical trials	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that the original slides may have been collected during clinical trials in the meaning of Directive 2001/20/EC³⁸.</p> <p>15. Are there any additional restrictions on making the health data collected during clinical trials available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: No, general conditions apply i.e. whenever health data or any other information is to be shared the Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act must be considered. More information about clinical trials in Sweden https://www.kliniskastudier.se/english.html#.</p> <p>Please note that the Swedish law on clinical trial will be replaced by Clinical Trial Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 536/2014) when it comes into application. The legislation is planned to be applicable in the end of January 2022. According to Article 28 (2), the sponsor may ask the subject for consent to use the data outside the protocol of the clinical trial exclusively for scientific purposes.</p>
Biobanks	<p>When answering the following questions, please consider applicable requirements if the WSI were submitted by a biobank or from a biobank in your jurisdiction.</p> <p>16. How are biobanks regulated in your jurisdiction? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information</p> <p>***Please note that the comments below are not applicable for RÖ since no information originates from biobanks.</p> <p>Response:</p> <p>The Biobank Act regulates how human tissue can be collected, stored and used. Biobanks can only be established for healthcare, treatment and other medical purposes as well as quality assurance, training, research, clinical trials, development or other equivalent activities.³⁹ If the biobank is mainly to be used for research and clinical trials, it may only be established after approval by the Ethical Review Board or the Board of Appeal for Ethics Review.⁴⁰</p> <p>Biobanks have to be reported to Health and Social Care Inspectorate⁴¹ (IVO) (Inspektionen för vård och omsorg)⁴² which also manages a register of all biobanks in Sweden. Biobank Sweden coordinates the various biobanks in the country and administers a catalogue over research sample collections. It also publishes guidelines and templates for contracts for access to the biobanks.⁴³ Contact</p>

³⁸ DIRECTIVE 2001/20/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

³⁹ Chapter 2 Section 2 Biobank Act

⁴⁰ Chapter 2 Section 3 Biobank Act

⁴¹ <https://www.ivo.se/om-ivo/other-languages/english/>

⁴² Chapter 2 Section 5 Biobanks Act

⁴³ <http://biobanksverige.se/forskning/nationell-katalog-over-forskningsprovsamlingar/>. More information in English at Biobank Sweden <http://biobanksverige.se/research/basic-information-in-english/>

	<p>information can be found at www.biobanksverige.se. In 2018, there were around 450 biobanks registered in the official registry for biobanks that held samples taken in a health care setting.⁴⁴</p> <p>Biobank Act applies to biobanks established in Sweden in healthcare sector. However, it does <u>not</u> apply to:⁴⁵</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Routine samples for medical care (intended as a basis for diagnosis and ongoing care and treatment of the sample donor and which are not saved for a longer period of time) - Anonymized samples (if they cannot directly or indirectly be linked to the donor) - Samples that are intended for research and that are analysed within six months after the time of sampling and destroyed immediately after the analysis. <p>According to the Biobank Act, tissue samples may only be collected and preserved in the biobank with the donor's consent after being informed of the intention and the purpose(s) for which they may be used.⁴⁶ Accordingly, the samples may not be used for purposes other than those covered by prior information and consent without the donor being informed and consenting to the new purpose, unless permission has been granted by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority.⁴⁷ Specific rules apply to samples collected from the minors, foetal samples and samples from the deceased⁴⁸. Moreover, the donor may withdraw consent for use of the sample at any time. If the withdrawal applies to all types of use, the sample must be destroyed or anonymized [deidentified] immediately.⁴⁹</p> <p>Tissue samples that are shared must be deidentified or coded⁵⁰. The code keys shall be stored with the healthcare provider that collected the data initially and that stores the tissue samples in a biobank. Code keys shall be stored securely. The usage of code keys can be viewed as an example of pseudonymisation. A medical record document in individual health care concerning a particular patient may be disclosed at the request of the person who has had access to coded human biological material from that patient, following an approval of the responsible biobank person, if the patient has consented to the medical record document being disclosed.</p> <p>Biobank Act also regulates transfer of tissue samples from a biobank. Such samples may be handed out to a recipient in another country for research purposes, only if a Swedish research institution submits an application to this effect. If this application is granted, in relation to the consignee abroad, it shall be a condition that the samples are returned or destroyed when they are no longer needed for the purpose for which they were handed out.⁵¹</p> <p>Further to information provided in the Guide to Biobanks Sweden, if samples for research purposes are to be sent for analysis abroad, the donor must be informed and consent to this. If coded samples are to be sent to a country within the EU/EEA,</p>
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⁴⁴ "GDPR and Biobanking" Santa Slokenberga, Olga Tzortzatou, Jane Reichel, Springer International Publishing 2021, pg. 390.

⁴⁵ Chapter 1 Section 3 Biobank Act

⁴⁶ Chapter 1, Section 5 Biobank Act.

⁴⁷ Chapter 3, Section 5 Biobank Act.

⁴⁸ Chapter 3, Section 2-4 Biobank Act

⁴⁹ Chapter 3, Section 6A Biobank Act

⁵⁰ Chapter 4 Section 4 Biobank Act

⁵¹ Chapter 4, Section 3 Biobank Act,

	<p>it may be enough to provide information that samples may be sent abroad for analysis. However, if samples are to be sent to third countries, it is required that the information clearly states that samples may be sent for analysis to countries outside the EU/EEA.⁵² Furthermore, for certain purposes, samples may be sent for analysis, from both primary and secondary sample collections to a recipient in Sweden or abroad without it being considered a release of samples. The samples are sent to the recipient for a specific purpose, and are not placed at the disposal of the recipient.⁵³</p> <p>Tissue samples or parts of tissue samples stored in a biobank may not be transferred or handed out for profit.⁵⁴ However, the biobank or the research sample collection controller may have a charge to cover its costs. Samples from the biobank can be made available either by releasing the samples to the research principal's biobank in Sweden or by letting the samples remain in the healthcare principal's biobank. Access to samples is regulated in the biobank agreement.</p> <p>As a general rule, research on identifiable human biological samples obtained from a biobank must obtain ethical approval before it can be conducted. Ethical review is conducted by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority (more details about the approval process in question 9).⁵⁵</p> <p>In relation to BigPicture it is important to note that the Biobank Act distinguishes between tissue samples and personal data connected to the samples. Although not an explicit exemption, the common interpretation of the Biobank Act has been that storing tissue samples in biobanks does <u>not</u> amount to processing of personal data as such.⁵⁶ The databases that are connected to the biobanks do contain personal data and therefore must be processed in accordance with the GDPR. Furthermore, the Biobank Act applies to sharing tissue samples, it would <u>not</u> be directly applicable to sharing the digital images of those samples (WSI).</p> <p>17. Can health data (including WSI) stored in the biobanks be shared with other parties to be used for scientific research purposes? If yes, what are the conditions of such sharing and use?</p> <p>Response: Under the Biobank Act, the samples and data may only be used for the purposes for which they have been collected and received consent, unless it is for a research purpose which has been approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority or is located within an approved clinical trial.⁵⁷</p> <p>Samples can be made available for research or clinical trials by remaining in the biobank and being analysed on site, by being sent for analysis or investigation, or by being released from the healthcare principal's biobank to the principal in whose project the research will be conducted.</p> <p>Tissue samples that are shared shall be deidentified or coded.⁵⁸ Personal details may not be linked to the tissue samples if both are shared at the same time.⁵⁹ In addition, conditions for sharing samples with another country are also provided.⁶⁰</p>
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⁵² Guide to Biobanks in Sweden –Access to Samples for Research and Clinical trials

⁵³ Guide to Biobanks in Sweden –Access to Samples for Research and Clinical trials

⁵⁴ Chapter 4, Section 8 Biobank Act

⁵⁵ Section 4 p. 3 and Section 6 Ethical Review Act

⁵⁶ SOU 2018:4, p 93 with further references, including Article 29 Working Party Opinion N° 4/2007 - WP 136

⁵⁷ Chapter 3 Section 5 Biobank Act

⁵⁸ Chapter 4 Section 4 Biobank Act

⁵⁹ Chapter 4 Section 10 Biobank Act

⁶⁰ Chapter 4 Section 3 and 5 Biobank Act

Data localization and infrastructure requirements	<p>18. What are the rules of transferring health data or human tissues for specific research projects to third parties?</p> <p>Response: As regards human tissues, conditions of Act on Quality and Security Norms when Processing Human Tissue or Cells apply. However, those rules would not apply to digital images (WSI). General GDPR rules regarding <i>inter alia</i> ensuring security of transferred personal data will apply.</p> <p>19. Are there any provisions restricting transfer of health data outside of your country?</p> <p>Response: Transfer of health data outside of Sweden is subject to GDPR requirements.</p> <p>Additional provisions apply to transfer of tissue samples. Please see specific comments in question 16 above.</p> <p>20. Are there any specific infrastructure/security requirements for storing health data?</p> <p>Response: Public Access Act stipulates requirements for healthcare providers regarding security and confidentiality, though Public Access Act only applies to public authorities. Also the Patient Data Act and regulations from the National Board of Health and Welfare (Socialstyrelsens föreskrifter och allmänna råd (HSLF-FS 2016:40) om journalföring och behandling av personuppgifter i hälso- och sjukvården) stipulates some specific requirements for healthcare providers regarding security requirements for storing health data.</p>
Honest broker model	<p>21. Is there a trusted third party service (“honest broker”) established in your jurisdiction, where researcher may submit a request for the data to be pseudonymized before access? If yes, please provide the name of the service, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: The honest broker model is not defined in the Swedish law.</p> <p>22. Please describe any restrictions or limitations regarding “honest broker” of health data according to your national law.</p> <p>Response: N/A</p>
Contractual limitations / limitation on commercial use of WSIs	<p>23. Are there any mandatory provisions which impose specific terms of use of health data or WSI by researchers? Please include any limitations on commercial use of WSIs. In your response, please provide name of the law and explain the requirements under such provisions.</p> <p>Response: Not specifically applicable to WSI.</p>
Copyrights / database rights / data license requirements	<p>24. Under the laws of your jurisdiction, would the WSI be subject to copyright protection, database rights, any other intellectual property rights? Who would be the holder of such rights?</p> <p>Response: It is not appropriate to discuss the ownership of or copyrights to the WSI, as they constitute personal data of the patients.</p> <p>In theory, the Swedish law provides a neighbouring right which protects the authors of photographs. Article 49a of the Law on Copyright⁶¹ states that the</p>

⁶¹ Law (1960: 729) on copyright in literary and artistic works (Copyright Act) [Lag (1960:729) om upphovsrätt till litterära och konstnärliga verk]

	<p>author of a photograph has the exclusive right to reproduce that photograph and to make it available to the public. The right applies regardless of whether the image is used in its original form or in a modified form and irrespective of the technique used. By photographic image is also meant an image that has been produced by a procedure comparable to photography. The right applies for fifty years from the year in which the image was produced.</p> <p>The neighbouring rights to the photographs would typically be vested in the institution (employer) rather than individual employees, by way of employment contract. Thus, if the WSI were submitted by an entitled institution, the neighbouring rights to WSIs as photographs would not be infringed.</p> <p>25. Are those IP rights transferrable or could a license to use them be granted? If yes, please describe any statutory conditions, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: Please see above.</p>
<p>Removal of commercially sensitive information (trade secrets)</p>	<p>26. Are there any laws (other than GDPR/data protection laws) which would make it mandatory that certain information (e.g. commercial information) is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information must be removed.</p> <p>Response: No, however if certain information contained in the WSI or its metadata would constitute a trade secret of the data submitter, this submitter may chose to remove it.</p> <p>In Sweden, the Trade Secret Law⁶² implements the Directive 2012/943/EU. The Trade Secret Law, inter alia: (i) provides definition of the trade secret (ii) indicates the scope of prohibited acts subject to the "infringement of trade secrets"; (iii) imposes measures and remedies such as injunctions, compensation for damages and penalties; (iv) strengthens the protection of secrecy for trade secrets during court proceedings.</p> <p>According to the Trade Secret Law, "trade secret" refers to information:⁶³</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - on business or operating conditions in a trader's business or in the activities of a research institution, - which are not generally known to or easily accessible to the person which normally has access to information of the type in question, neither as a whole nor in the form in which its components are arranged and assembled, are, - which the holder has taken reasonable measures to keep secret, and - whose disclosure is likely to cause damage to competition for the holder. <p>It is not required to register the information, which the holder wants protected as trade secret – this protection occurs automatically. However, the existence of a trade secret assumes that the holder takes reasonable steps to keep the know-how secret. Trade secret protection is thus first and foremost a matter of actually keeping the information secret by minimizing the dissemination of the information to employees and others.</p> <p>The WSI, especially the metadata connected to the WSI, may constitute a trade secret of the data submitter. In such case, the data submitter may consider that including this information in the WSI shared within the project, may lead to</p>

⁶² Law (2018: 558) on trade secrets [Lag (2018:558) om företagshemligheter]

⁶³ Section 2 Trades Secret Law

	<p>disclosure of its confidential information, leading to loss of protection under Trade Secret Law. Thus, it may chose to remove this information from the WSIs.</p> <p>Notwithstanding the above, the requirements regarding protection of personal data and patient confidentiality apply (as described in previous questions).</p> <p>27. Are there any laws which would prohibit that certain information is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information cannot be removed.</p> <p>Response: No.</p> <p>28. Are there any other limitations on the submitter of the WSIs with respect to making them available without information constituting a trade secret of the owner?</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Access to public information	<p>29. Which public information laws apply? Please explain how they may impact disclosing of WSI by the foreseen data provider.</p> <p>Response: The principle of public access to information is a fundamental principle in Sweden. One of the fundamental laws, the Freedom of the Press Act, contains provisions on the right to access official documents, which is a manifestation of the principle of public access to information. There are, however, provisions on secrecy that restrict the right to access official documents. These provisions are found in the Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act.⁶⁴</p> <p>The provisions on public access to information would however not apply to data submitter’s own participation in a research project and its submission of data to such project. They would only be applicable if a third party researcher requested data from an institution, which was subject to public access of information laws.</p> <p>30. Please briefly describe the rules of public information access and possible restrictions and specify to which type of providers they would apply.</p> <p>Response: The provisions on duties of confidentiality for public functionaries are consolidated in the Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act. Secrecy provisions are primarily to be applied by public authorities. Furthermore, state-owned limited companies, for-profit associations and foundations are only obliged to apply the principle of public access to information and the Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act if the body in question is listed in the appendix to the Act and, in such cases, only for the activities listed in the appendix.</p> <p>If a researcher, who has obtained an approval from the Ethical Review Authority applies to a public care provider, this provider is obliged to make data accessible to anyone who asks for it, if no regulation on secrecy applies. This follows from the Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act as well as general Swedish interpretation of the GDPR. Such interpretation puts a strong emphasis on public interest as the default legal ground for processing personal data in research and other publicly-motivated activities. However, if the data is subject to medical secrecy, which is the case for patient’s health data, secrecy rules would apply.</p> <p>Moreover, depending on the quantity of data requested, it may be disputable whether they can be requested under Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act. This is due to special rules which apply to compilations of information from a recording for automated processing. Such compilations are only considered to be held by the authority if the authority can extract them using routine measures. If</p>

⁶⁴ <https://www.government.se/4a72cf/contentassets/2ca7601373824c8395fc1f38516e6e03/public-access-to-information-and-secrecy.pdf>

	<p>there is a large quantity of data requested, a public authority can argue that preparation of this data would go beyond “routine measure”. Furthermore, such compilations of information stored on computers are not considered to be held by the authority if they contain personal data and, under an act or ordinance, the authority does not have the power to make the compilation available. The underlying purpose of this provision of the Freedom of the Press Act is to ensure that the public cannot use the principle of public access to information to request compilations of personal data that, for reasons of personal privacy protection, the authority cannot produce.</p> <p>Private care provider, may transfer data for research after an approval from the Ethical Review Authority, but is not obliged to do so under Freedom of the Press Act. However, in practice it appears as very unlikely that a private care provider would block the data, particularly if the patient consented.</p>
Requirements for development of AI/ML	<p>31. Are there any restrictions or rules regarding use of health data or WSI in the context of development of artificial intelligence and machine learning systems (AI / ML)?</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Requirement for contributing slides to BigPicture	<p>32. Assuming that the source of the WSI slides (see Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus) for your jurisdiction will be as provided above, please summarize the requirements, in particular (a) which of the laws are applicable to contributing the WSI, (b) what steps are required to provide them and (c) from a point of view of data protection laws, in which form (“raw”, anonymized, pseudonymized) may the WSI be submitted?</p> <p>Response: In the context of BIGPICTURE the slides from Region Östergötland (RO):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • will be provided from RO pathology image and information system (pathology PACS and laboratory information/journal system); • will be provided based on an ethical approval obtained in accordance with the Ethical Review Act; • will be provided in an anonymous manner, thus not constituting personal data of the patients, thus the requirements of GDPR will not apply; • will <u>not</u> be obtained from a biobank. Thus, the above comments on the rules of Biobank Act would not be applicable in the context of this data; • will be submitted by RO from its own database, thus the Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act does <u>not</u> apply to such disclosure of information; • will not include non-clinical WSIs, thus considerations under Animal Welfare Act were not considered.

Notes to the respondents

Background:

- The clinical part of the BIGPICTURE data repository will consist of digital scans of slides of human tissues or biological samples (WSI, whole slide imaging). The original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies. Those studies may have been conducted in the past or are ongoing trials. However, the primary purpose of collection of the slides will be the clinical studies or treatment of patients. Thus, the original slides will not be collected directly and primarily for the purpose of digitization for the BIGPICTURE data repository. We assume that the collection of the original slides was done in line with the requirements applicable to the such purpose.
- BIGPICTURE data repository will also reuse WSI from animal tissues that are also going to be digitized slides from existing collections. The BIGPICTURE repository will only store digital slides (WSI), not the glass originals or biological samples.
- The WSI will be accompanied by metadata (i.e. not only image will be stored). Scope of the metadata may vary, depending on the type of WSI.
- The purpose of storing the WSI is to make them available for scientific and research purposes.
- WSI will not be submitted from public health registries or electronic patient record systems.
- The data submitters will have digital pathology slides or will digitize slides generated as part of clinical diagnostic work that, in some instances, will have also been used in clinical studies. For some submitters, in case duplicate samples to the clinical samples are collected in the biobank of human tissues, DNA/RNA and body fluids, data that have been generated as part of research projects that have used these samples may be used. There may be additionally data from archives. No animal experimentation will be performed for the purpose of data collection in the project.
- Additional patient information may accompany WSI. The list will be provided at a later stage, however before month 6 of the project. Results from genomic investigation may be used as associated data in some WSI collections.

Source of WSI

At the current stage of the project, the following have been confirmed as initial data submitters:

UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT	UMC UTRECHT	Netherlands	Cancer node
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT	RUMC	Netherlands	Cancer node
Azienda Ospedaliera Per L'Emergenza Cannizzaro	AOEC	Italy	Cancer node
Technical University of Munich	TUM	Germany	Cancer node
PHILIPPS UNIVERSITAET MARBURG	UMR	Germany	Clinical trial node
THE LEEDS TEACHING HOSPITALS NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE TRUST	LTHNHS	UK	Liver node
HELSINGIN JA UUDENMAAN SAIRAANHOITOPPIIRIN KUNTAYHTYMÄ	HUS	Finland	Lung node
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT GRAZ	MUG	Austria	Lung node
DECIPHEX	DECIPHEX	Ireland	Non-clinical node
Medical University Vienna	MUW	Austria	Renal node
OSTERGOTLANDS LANS LANDSTING	RO	Sweden	Skin node
Linköping University	LiU	Sweden	Skin node
UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE	Belgium	Skin node

Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus

Instructions:

Please provide responses to the below questions based on the laws of your jurisdiction. Please use the below example as guidance as to the level of required detail. **Please note that the provided responses are for**

exemplary purposes only. The circumstances in your jurisdiction may be different, as well as legal basis and legal steps for contributing WSIs to the BigPicture project.

We are looking for a practical description of issues which may impede or influence the planned collection of WSIs and their sharing with other researchers. If certain matter is regulated by GDPR, please do not explain in detail. Mere reference to GDPR rules is sufficient. If the response to certain questions is not clear under the current legal framework or the approach taken depends on the organization, please indicate this and, if possible, describe the most common approach.

Appendix 8 - The UK Country Report

Responses for the UK

Contributor: Nathan Lea, European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD)

Topic	Questions
National provisions on personal data processing in the context of scientific research	<p>1. Which national laws regulate use and sharing of health (“health data”), including WSIs, for research purposes? Please provide the name of the law, online reference, and relevance for the BigPicture (if not explained in other sections below)</p> <p>Response: The UK is comprised of four distinct jurisdictions (England, Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland) which each have their own provision for several statutory and common law instruments described.</p> <p>UK law in general comprises statute (written in Acts approved by Parliament) and Common Law (applying legal principle against preceding rulings by the courts). The Common Law tradition functions differently across the four jurisdictions but is designed to achieve the same result.</p> <p>Please see https://www.legislation.gov.uk to get the definitive provision of the laws mentioned below. It is best to search for them rather than look at the links.</p> <p>Law applicable across the UK jurisdictions includes the UK GDPR¹ and Data Protection Act of 2018 (Implementing GDPR) where some variations exist across jurisdictions.</p> <p>In England and predominantly Wales, the Health and Social Care Act 2012² establishes the Health and Social Care Information Centre (AKA NHS Digital) and certain public health and health service information requirements (for managing health data). Scotland and Northern Ireland have separate arrangements but broadly achieve the same goals. NHS Digital does not have oversight of Scotland and Northern Ireland, there are separate bodies that handle this.</p> <p>In England and predominantly Wales, the Care Act 2014³ establishes in statute the lawfulness of research including data driven research and the central bodies that regulate it (including the Health Research Authority and Care Quality Commission). Again Scotland and Northern Ireland have separate provisions but are designed to reach the same results overall.</p> <p>In England and Wales the NHS Act of 2006⁴ establishes under Section 251 the ability of the Secretary of State for Health and Social Care to make regulation to set aside the duty of confidence in cases where consent would be impossible, seriously undermine research or other purpose and that purpose is overwhelmingly in the public interest. This is overseen by the Confidentiality Advisory Group at the Health Research Authority (HRA)⁵. In Scotland this is handled by the Council of Caldicott Guardians and in Northern Ireland it is the Chair of the Patient Privacy Committee.</p>

¹ UK GDPR a separate legal instrument to be read alongside the Data Protection Act 2018. For further information see: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/dp-at-the-end-of-the-transition-period/data-protection-and-the-eu-in-detail/the-uk-gdpr/>

² <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2012/7/contents/enacted>

³ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/contents/enacted>

⁴ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2006/41/contents>

⁵ <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/>

The Human Tissue Act 2004⁶ governs use of biological samples.

The UK operates on the Common Law Duty of Confidence⁷ which covers medical and research records. In the main, the health providers owe a patient a duty of confidence and cannot breach that without patient consent. The Duty of Confidence survives the deceased (except in Northern Ireland).

There are also the Caldicott Reviews⁸ that cover England and Wales broadly that are conclusions drawn from reviews led by Dame Fiona Caldicott. Whilst not Statute or Common Law, they are considered legally binding as they have received ministerial ascent.

In the UK, Statute has primacy over Common Law, and they both have primacy over professional practice guidelines, standards and reviews like the Caldicott Reviews. Judges will defer to these other instruments where they cannot draw a conclusion from Statute or precedent.

2. Please describe how the databases and registers containing patient's health data and biological samples for scientific research purposes are organized in your jurisdiction and which type of data they contain. If possible, please indicate which databases or registers may be relevant for BigPicture.

Response: There are a great many registries that have been established either as national resources or individual institutional or research projects. These will all have an application process and require review by a Data Access Committee.

WSIs are not to my knowledge widely available but individual care providers can be approached to share under ethical approval granted by one of the Research Ethics Committees (REC) within the Health Research Authority established for each of the four constituent countries. There is divergence in the rules for obtaining the approval depending on the authority. There are more than 80 different RECs⁹, which vary in their expertise.

It may be also mentioned that in England the national data opt-out¹⁰ was introduced on 25 May 2018, enabling patients to opt out from the use of their data for research or planning purposes. "Opt out" applies only to identifiable data held by the NHS (not anonymous information¹¹) and does not impact research studies which are carried out based on consent of the subjects.

3. Please describe general conditions on using patient's health data and WSIs of human biological samples for scientific research purposes.

Response: The collection of health data directly from a patient will constitute the processing of special category / sensitive data. Such processing is lawful only if it complies with the data protection principles and at least one of the conditions in each of Schedules 2 and 3 of the Data Protection Act 2018 (DPA) is satisfied. According to the UK's Data Protection Act, processing of personal data that is 'necessary for scientific ... research purposes' is lawful. This includes personal data in one of the GDPR's 'special categories', which include genetic data and data concerning health. However, where the data processing is necessary for 'the

⁶ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2004/30/contents>

⁷ More: <https://www.health-ni.gov.uk/articles/common-law-duty-confidentiality>

⁸ Please see

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/251750/731-2901141-TSO-Caldicott-Government_Response_ACCESSIBLE.PDF

⁹ <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/about-us/committees-and-services/res-and-recs/research-ethics-committees-overview/>

¹⁰ <https://digital.nhs.uk/services/national-data-opt-out>

¹¹ Although the practice varies between the hospitals, some hospitals are even applying it to anonymous data.

purposes of approved medical research', then it is compliant with the Data Protection Act. 'Approved medical research' requires ethical clearance, either under the Devolved Nation Authority RECs within Health Research Authority (HRA), or a body appointed by the NHS.

In the context of BigPicture, an entity being a UK submitter of the WSIs will almost always require an approval from a Research Ethics Committee (REC) run by the HRA or Devolved Nations equivalents.

4. Is research subject's consent required for scientific research? Would using health data for scientific research purposes be possible, if the data was initially collected for other purpose? If yes, describe any conditions of such use.

Response: Consent is always required unless the Duty of Confidence is set aside as per answer in point 1. Data can be reused for scientific research provided consent or exemption (based on the Control of Patient Information Regulation¹² and Section 251 of the NHS Act 2006, for e.g., in case of pandemic, for public concern, in regard to specific cancer types, for secret research) is in place and a REC review is favourable. Data will usually only be shared where security and data protection matters are assured (either via ISO 27001 or the Data Security and Protection Toolkit run by NHS Digital, and the Devolved Nation Equivalents). Where data is anonymised, REC approval is required and security is still expected.

5. From which generally applicable data protection provisions of GDPR (in particular requirements under Articles 13-21) are scientific researchers exempted and under what conditions?

Response: No exemptions exist for scientific research.

6. Are there specific provisions which relate to appropriate safeguards, including using or making available anonymous or pseudonymized health data in the context of scientific research?

Response: No, but there are proposals for a new Health Bill¹³ that will facilitate this for NHS Digital (an anonymous data store). Furthermore, there is an ongoing debate when techniques of anonymization or the use of pseudonyms might suffice to separate data from a linkage with identifiable individuals and thereby take it outside the category of personal data. Generally speaking, whether the data should be considered anonymous is evaluated from the perspective of the recipient of the data. Ultimately, it is the hospital which decides whether the data is anonymous or not, in which case CAG support is required. The data must go to assured environment.¹⁴

In some cases, such as in the field of biobanking research, it is recognized that it is not possible to reach a complete anonymization, and therefore the threshold is limited to the pseudonymization requirements.¹⁵

7. What are the potential consequences of non-compliance with the rules outlined in the questions above?

Response: Fines, criminal prosecutions and a ban from accessing data sets (for a defined period or indefinitely). There are no custodial sentences but individuals

¹² COPI Regulations do not apply to Scotland and Northern Ireland.

¹³ <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-9232/>

¹⁴ Fulfilling ISO 20701 on information security management or NHS Data security and protection toolkit and devolved nations equivalents

¹⁵ Kaye, J., Bell, J., Briceno, L., & Mitchell, C. (2016). Biobank Report: United Kingdom. Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics, 44(1), 96-105. doi:10.1177/1073110516644202

	found guilty at magistrates court are publicly named by the DPA and retain a criminal record.
Digitalization of original slides	<p>8. Are there any specific rules regarding digitalization of images of human tissues and biological samples? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: Human Tissue Act and UK GDPR provisions around Genetic Data.</p>
Ethical board approvals requirements / biomedical research projects	<p>9. Is there a regime requiring an approval of ethical board or any similar or related conditions prior to making WSIs and sharing them for research purposes? If yes, what does that regime entail? Please refer to any rules of obtaining ethical board approvals for biomedical research projects, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: The Care Act 2014 defines the role of the Health Research Authority (HRA) and RECs (where Scotland and Northern Ireland have their own equivalents).</p> <p>If personal data must be used, and the patient's consent is genuinely not practicable, then in England and Wales, approval may be obtained from the Secretary of State for Health under Section 251 of the National Health Service Act 2006, on the recommendation of the Confidentiality Advisory Group (CAG) of the Health Research Authority (HRA). Thus, if a researcher intends to access confidential patient information without consent in England and Wales they should apply to the CAG. CAG provides independent expert advice on the appropriate use of confidential information. It reviews applications for the use of person-identifiable information for research and other secondary purposes, and advises the HRA on whether the use is sufficiently justified. Its key purpose is to protect and promote the interests of patients and the public whilst at the same time facilitating appropriate use of confidential information for purposes beyond direct care. In Scotland the Council of Caldicott Guardians or Public Benefits and Privacy Panel applies the same exemptions to the Duty of Confidence.¹⁶ For NI it is the Privacy Advisory Committee¹⁷ that review research applications and give an opinion about whether the research is ethical. They look at areas such as the proposed participant involvement and are entirely independent of research sponsors (that is, the organisations which are responsible for the management and conduct of the research), funders and investigators. This enables them to put participants at the centre of their review. For most applicants to the Health Research Authority (HRA), the REC review forms part of the overall HRA Approval process. For some projects that do not require HRA Approval, such as research tissue banks and research databases, or research taking place outside the NHS such as Phase 1 trials in healthy volunteers, REC review may still be required.¹⁸</p>
Animal tissues and biological samples (non-clinical WSI)	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI of animal samples may be collected in some jurisdictions.</p> <p>10. Are there any rules that regulate use of WSI of animal samples that have already been produced in another study for scientific research purposes? If yes, please describe.</p>

¹⁶ See <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/policies-standards-legislation/data-protection-and-information-governance/gdpr-guidance/gdpr-and-use-confidential-patient-information-without-consent/>

¹⁷ <http://www.privacyadvisorycommittee.hscni.net>; <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/about-us/committees-and-services/res-and-recs/research-ethics-committees-overview/>

¹⁸ <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/approvals-amendments/what-approvals-do-i-need/research-ethics-committee-review/>

	<p>Response: Should be checked with the specific site. There may be restrictions based on use of specified purpose, including standard research ethics guidelines.</p>
Processing of genetic data	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI metadata may contain genetic information related to the data subject. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>11. How is processing of genetic data regulated? Please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: The rules are interpreted from the Human Tissue Act (HTA).</p> <p>12. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained human genetic data? Are there any additional restrictions on making the human genetic data available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: Usually across UK jurisdictions any reuse of such data must receive explicit consent of the concerned individual and be handled in line with REC Approvals and the Human Tissue Act.</p>
Data on rare diseases / Covid 19	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that WSI may relate rare disease or Covid19 research. Please take into consideration collection, use and sharing of the respective data with other scientific researchers.</p> <p>13. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on rare diseases? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: If the data concerns very rare diseases, this can affect the rules regarding keeping the data in accordance with secrecy and confidentiality rules, because in case of such diseases it may be difficult or impossible to de-identify the data to the extent that it is made anonymous.</p> <p>14. Are there any additional considerations if the WSI or their metadata contained data on Covid19? If yes, please describe and provide name of the law and its online reference.</p> <p>Response: These may well have been processed without consent under the Control of Patient Regulations Notice (which operates under the NHS Act 2006). The COVID COPI Notice will expire at the end of September 2021 most likely.</p>
Clinical trials	<p>When answering the following questions, please note that the original slides may have been collected during clinical trials in the meaning of Directive 2001/20/EC¹⁹.</p> <p>15. Are there any additional restrictions on making the health data collected during clinical trials available to other researchers?</p> <p>Response: This must be in line with existing consents to participate in a research project or be rendered anonymous.</p>
Biobanks	<p>When answering the following questions, please consider applicable requirements if the WSI were submitted by a biobank or from a biobank in your jurisdiction.</p> <p>16. How are biobanks regulated in your jurisdiction? Please provide name of the law, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information</p> <p>Response: In the United Kingdom, there is no specific legal framework for the governance of biobanks. This means that there is no single piece of legislation that</p>

¹⁹ Directive 2001/20/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

	<p>provides a framework for medical research on human beings. Instead, there exists a fragmented patchwork of law that applies to medical research on humans.²⁰ Moreover, there is a distinction between human material (samples) and information relating to individuals (data). Human Tissue Act 2004 (HTA), enforced by the Human Tissue Authority, regulates removal, storage, use and disposal of human tissue. The Human Tissue Authority provides licences to organisations that collect and remove human tissue used in research and is thus responsible for licensing biobanks. Issues regarding processing of data are regulated by GDPR and laws mentioned above in point 1.</p> <p>17. Can health data (including WSI) stored in the biobanks be shared with other parties to be used for scientific research purposes? If yes, what are the conditions of such sharing and use?</p> <p>Response: Yes, but only with Data Trust Committee or Data Access Committee (DTC) approval and REC approval as appropriate.</p> <p>For access to the actual samples, typically there are different stages: (1) registration, (2) application, and (3) material transfer agreement. In some cases, access may be limited to non-profit institutions (such as universities, charities, public bodies) while others allow access to commercial companies. Most biobanks have a body appointed to review access applications, and the composition and the nature of the Data Access Committees may vary across the different biobanks. HTA will not apply to WSI. The data protection laws will apply to genetics data as defined in the Human Tissue Act, but the HTA may also have coverage of the data relating to samples as well. Biobanks apply restrictions to use of genetics data, there is some ownership law.</p>
Data localization and infrastructure requirements	<p>18. What are the rules of transferring health data or human tissues for specific research projects to third parties?</p> <p>Response: Materials Transfer Agreement is needed for the transfer of the tissues and it can cover data transfers as well.</p> <p>19. Are there any provisions restricting transfer of health data outside of your country?</p> <p>Response: Yes – adequacy to the EU and UK SCCs are needed that are Schrems 2 compliant.</p>
Honest broker model	<p>20. Is there a trusted third party service (“honest broker”) established in your jurisdiction, where researcher may submit a request for the data to be pseudonymized before access? If yes, please provide the name of the service, online reference, brief description and specific relevant information.</p> <p>Response: No.</p> <p>21. Please describe any restrictions or limitations regarding “honest broker” of health data according to your national law.</p> <p>Response: N/A</p>
Contractual limitations / limitation on commercial use of WSIs	<p>22. Are there any mandatory provisions which impose specific terms of use of health data or WSI by researchers? Please include any limitations on commercial use of WSIs. In your response, please provide name of the law and explain the requirements under such provisions.</p>

²⁰ Kaye, Jane & Bell, Jessica & Briceno, Linda & Mitchell, Colin. (2016). Biobank Report: United Kingdom. Journal of Law, Medicine and Ethics. 44. 96-105. 10.1177/1073110516644202.

	<p>Response: Not specifically applicable to WSI.</p>
Copyrights / database rights / data license requirements	<p>23. Under the laws of your jurisdiction, would the WSI be subject to copyright protection, database rights, any other intellectual property rights? Who would be the holder of such rights?</p> <p>Response: Existing IP (specifically the IP relating to records) remains with the Health Care Trust / Health Board that are the Data Controllers of the Records. Arising IP is negotiated in a per case basis.</p> <p>24. Are those IP rights transferrable or could a license to use them be granted? If yes, please describe any statutory conditions, if applicable.</p> <p>Response: Yes – on a per case basis.</p>
Removal of commercially sensitive information (trade secrets)	<p>25. Are there any laws (other than GDPR/data protection laws) which would make it mandatory that certain information (e.g. commercial information) is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information must be removed.</p> <p>Response: Data about abortions, certain sexual health conditions (including but not limited to HIV and Female Genital Mutilation) are held separately from the record by statute and would require special review from RECs and approvals from specialist centres (specialist treatment centres for conditions like HIV or interventions relating to FGM) to be shared.</p> <p>26. Are there any laws which would prohibit that certain information is removed from the WSI? If yes, please provide reference and describe which information cannot be removed.</p> <p>Response: No.</p> <p>27. Are there any other limitations on the submitter of the WSIs with respect to making them available without information constituting a trade secret of the owner?</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Access to public information	<p>28. Which public information laws apply? Please explain how they may impact disclosing of WSI by the foreseen data provider.</p> <p>Response: Freedom of Information (where confidential data is not shared) and the Digital Economies Act (this is more about protections of data). WSIs would be covered under confidential data and would not be shared under Freedom of Information. The Digital Economies Act tends to cover any data generally, but not directly health care data.</p> <p>29. Please briefly describe the rules of public information access and possible restrictions and specify to which type of providers they would apply.</p> <p>Response: The rules mentioned above would not apply to providers in the context of sharing WSI for the purpose of the BigPicture project.</p>
Requirements for development of AI/ML	<p>30. Are there any restrictions or rules regarding use of health data or WSI in the context of development of artificial intelligence and machine learning systems (AI / ML)?</p> <p>Response: No.</p>
Requirement for contributing slides to BigPicture	<p>31. Assuming that the source of the WSI slides (see Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus) for your jurisdiction will be as provided above, please summarize the requirements, in particular (a) which of the laws are applicable to contributing the WSI, (b) what steps are required to provide</p>

	<p>them and (c) from a point of view of data protection laws, in which form (“raw”, anonymized, pseudonymized) may the WSI be submitted?</p> <p>Response: Each UK site will have to address the requirements. Generally REC approval is needed and data must be minimised and held securely.</p>
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Notes to the respondents

Background:

- The clinical part of the BIGPICTURE data repository will consist of digital scans of slides of human tissues or biological samples (WSI, whole slide imaging). The original slides were collected either for clinical care purposes or in the context of clinical studies. Those studies may have been conducted in the past or are ongoing trials. However, the primary purpose of collection of the slides will be the clinical studies or treatment of patients. Thus, the original slides will not be collected directly and primarily for the purpose of digitization for the BIGPICTURE data repository. We assume that the collection of the original slides was done in line with the requirements applicable to the such purpose.
- BIGPICTURE data repository will also reuse WSI from animal tissues that are also going to be digitized slides from existing collections. The BIGPICTURE repository will only store digital slides (WSI), not the glass originals or biological samples.
- The WSI will be accompanied by metadata (i.e. not only image will be stored). Scope of the metadata may vary, depending on the type of WSI.
- The purpose of storing the WSI is to make them available for scientific and research purposes.
- WSI will not be submitted from public health registries or electronic patient record systems.
- The data submitters will have digital pathology slides or will digitize slides generated as part of clinical diagnostic work that, in some instances, will have also been used in clinical studies. For some submitters, in case duplicate samples to the clinical samples are collected in the biobank of human tissues, DNA/RNA and body fluids, data that have been generated as part of research projects that have used these samples may be used. There may be additionally data from archives. No animal experimentation will be performed for the purpose of data collection in the project.
- Additional patient information may accompany WSI. The list will be provided at a later stage, however before month 6 of the project. Results from genomic investigation may be used as associated data in some WSI collections.

Source of WSI

At the current stage of the project, the following have been confirmed as initial data submitters:

UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT	UMC UTRECHT	Netherlands	Cancer node
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT	RUMC	Netherlands	Cancer node
Azienda Ospedaliera Per L'Emergenza Cannizzaro	AOEC	Italy	Cancer node
Technical University of Munich	TUM	Germany	Cancer node
PHILIPPS UNIVERSITAET MARBURG	UMR	Germany	Clinical trial node
THE LEEDS TEACHING HOSPITALS NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE TRUST	LHTNHS	UK	Liver node
HELSINGIN JA UUDENMAAN SAIRAANHOITOPPIIRIN KUNTAYHTYMÄ	HUS	Finland	Lung node
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT GRAZ	MUG	Austria	Lung node
DECIPHEX	DECIPHEX	Ireland	Non-clinical node
Medical University Vienna	MUW	Austria	Renal node
OSTERGOTLANDS LANS LANDSTING	RO	Sweden	Skin node
Linköping University	LiU	Sweden	Skin node
UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE	Belgium	Skin node

Table 1: Data Providers and Disease Focus

Instructions:

Please provide responses to the below questions based on the laws of your jurisdiction. Please use the below example as guidance as to the level of required detail. **Please note that the provided responses are for**

exemplary purposes only. The circumstances in your jurisdiction may be different, as well as legal basis and legal steps for contributing WSIs to the BigPicture project.

We are looking for a practical description of issues which may impede or influence the planned collection of WSIs and their sharing with other researchers. If certain matter is regulated by GDPR, please do not explain in detail. Mere reference to GDPR rules is sufficient. If the response to certain questions is not clear under the current legal framework or the approach taken depends on the organization, please indicate this and, if possible, describe the most common approach.